

Report 2014

Trends and Sources of Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents in Humans, Foodstuffs, Animals and Feedingstuffs

Austria

Including information on foodborne outbreaks,
antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic agents and some
pathogenic microbiological agents

AUSTRIA

The Report referred to in Article 9 of Directive 2003/99/EC

**TRENDS AND SOURCES OF ZONOSSES AND ZONOTIC AGENTS
IN HUMANS, FOODSTUFFS, ANIMALS AND FEEDINGSTUFFS**

**Including information on foodborne outbreaks, antimicrobial
resistance in zoonotic agents and some pathogenic microbiological
agents**

IN 2014

1. Information on the Reporting and Monitoring System

Country: Austria

Reporting Year: 2014

This report was prepared by the Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment of the AGES. Following Institutions and Laboratories were involved:

Institutions and laboratories involved in monitoring

Authorities		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Central Veterinary Services	Federal Ministry of Health	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals; Revision of the draft of the Trend Report; Approval of the Trend Report for Submission
Food Office	Federal Ministry of Health	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
DG Public Health	Federal Ministry of Health	Validation of data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks; revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Feed Office	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, the Environment and Water management	Revision of the draft of the Trend Report
Provincial Veterinary Services	9 provinces, one Veterinary Service per province	Data concerning notifiable zoonoses in animals
Local/District health authorities	Part of each local administration authority ("Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde"); one physician per district	Collection and entry of the data concerning notifiable zoonoses in humans and food borne outbreaks

Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Statistics and the Department for Data Management of the Business Area Data, Statistics and Risk Assessment (DSR)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Compilation, validation, preparation, data entry and submission of the Zoonoses Trend Report (Reporting officer, national reporter); Analysis of laboratory results for antimicrobial resistance of <i>Salmonella</i> spp., <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., and <i>E. coli</i> ; Mapping of food and feed data; Creation of xml-files
Statistics Austria	The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions.	Demographic and livestock census data

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Infectious Epidemiology Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning notifiable zoonotic diseases in humans and food borne outbreaks
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Centre for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial susceptibility testing
National Reference Laboratory for antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Centre for Tuberculosis, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Vienna	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in humans
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in humans
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Toxoplasmoselabor und Nachsorgeambulanz Toxoplasrose, Diagnostik in der Schwangerschaft und kindliches Follow-up, The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, Klinische Abteilung für Neonatologie, pädiatrische Intensivmedizin und Neuropädiatrie, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Medical University of Vienna	Data concerning toxoplasmosis in humans

Human Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Toxoplasmosis, Echinococcosis, Toxocarosis and other Parasitic Diseases; Department of Medical Parasitology; Institute of Specific Prophylaxis and Tropical Medicine; Center for Physiology, Pathophysiology and Immunology	Medical University of Vienna	Laboratory data concerning parasitic diseases in humans

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Official Food Control Laboratories (ILMU)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Graz, Innsbruck, Linz, Salzburg and Vienna	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Food Safety Department of the City of Vienna	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Institute for Environment and Food Safety of the State of Vorarlberg	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
Carinthian Institute for Food Analysis and Quality Control	Regional Food Laboratory	Data concerning investigations in foodstuffs
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals

Food Control Institutes		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Listeria</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning listeriosis in food
National Reference Centre for <i>Yersinia</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning yersiniosis in food

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning monitoring programmes in animals
National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning tuberculosis in animals
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans and antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for <i>Campylobacter</i> , Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning campylobacteriosis in humans, speciation of <i>Campylobacter</i> from food and animals, antimicrobial resistance testing
National Reference Laboratory for Antimicrobial resistance, Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Testing for antimicrobial resistance of <i>E. coli</i> from animals
National Reference Centre for <i>E. coli</i> including VTEC Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Typing of VTEC from humans, food and animals

Veterinary Medicine		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning brucellosis in humans and animals
National Reference Laboratory for Trichinellosis in Animals, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, (IVET), Innsbruck	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning trichinellosis in animals
Institutes for Veterinary Disease Control (IVET)	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES; Laboratories in Innsbruck, Linz and Moedling	Data concerning investigations in animals; bacteriological investigation in slaughtered animals
National Reference Laboratory for Rabies, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, Moedling	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning rabies in humans and animals
Austrian Poultry Health Data (PHD)	Association installed by law, running different programs e.g. <i>Salmonella</i> control and hygiene programs, Control of veterinarians and poultry farmers	Data concerning the Austrian poultry industry

Feed Control Institute		
Name of Institute or Laboratory	Organisation	Contribution to the Report
Institute for Animal Nutrition and Feed, Linz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Data concerning feeding stuff
National Reference Centre for <i>Salmonella</i> Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, (IMED), Graz	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES	Laboratory data concerning salmonellosis in feedingstuff, animals, foodstuff and humans, and antimicrobial resistance testing

PREFACE

This report is submitted to the European Commission in accordance with Article 9 of Council Directive 2003/99/EC1. The information has also been forwarded to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The report contains information on trends and sources of zoonoses and zoonotic agents in Austria during the year 2013. The information covers the occurrence of these diseases and agents in humans, animals, foodstuffs and in some cases also in feedingstuffs. In addition the report includes data on antimicrobial resistance in some zoonotic agents and commensal bacteria as well as information on epidemiological investigations of foodborne outbreaks. Complementary data on susceptible animal populations in the country is also given.

The information given covers zoonoses that are important for public health in the whole European Community as well as zoonoses which are relevant on the basis of the national epidemiological situation.

The report describes the monitoring systems in place and the prevention and control strategies applied in the country. For some zoonoses this monitoring is based on legal requirements laid down by the Community Legislation, while for the other zoonoses national approaches are applied.

The report presents the results of the examinations carried out in the reporting year. A national evaluation of the epidemiological situation, with special reference to trends and sources of zoonotic infections, is given. Whenever possible, the relevance of findings in foodstuffs and animals to zoonoses cases in humans is evaluated.

The information covered by this report is used in the annual European Union Summary Report on zoonoses that is published each year by EFSA.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AGES	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety
BMSK	Federal Ministry for Social Security, Generations and Consumer Protection
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i>
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EMS	Epidemiological Notification System for human notifiable diseases ("epidemiologisches Meldesystem")
FMH	Federal Ministry of Health
ILMU	Official Food Control Laboratories, AGES
IMED	Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, AGES
IVET	Institute for Veterinary Disease Control, AGES
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
OIE	World organisation for animal health
PHD	Poultry Health Data
TESSy	the European Surveillance System
VIS	Veterinary Information System
VTEC	Verotoxin producing <i>E. coli</i>

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3. Animal Populations

3.1. Information on susceptible animal population

Sources of information

The independent and non-profit-making federal institution, Statistics Austria, provides data on the economy, demography, environment and social and cultural situation in Austria to federal bodies. Federal agencies can then implement controlling measures in the scientific community, business and public institutions. The data for this report are available from an online database established by Statistics Austria.

Herds, flocks, holdings, stocks

Cattle: The number of holdings and animals is based on the official database for cattle.

Equids, Pigs, Sheep, Goats and Farmed Deer: The number of holdings and animals is based on the yearly full survey for pig, sheep and goats of the Veterinary Information System (VIS).

Poultry: The number of holdings, flocks and animals is based on the Poultry Health Data. All holdings, flocks and animals are part of the *Salmonella* control program.

Slaughters

Cattle, Equids: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), performed by Statistics Austria.

Pigs: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly statistic of all examined slaughters (reported by veterinarians), combined with not-examined slaughters (out of pig-random-sample-surveys) performed by Statistics Austria.

Sheep & Goats: The number of slaughters is based on an expert-model carried out by Statistics Austria.

Poultry: The number of slaughters is based on a monthly/yearly full survey in main poultry-slaughterhouses performed by Statistics Austria.

Dates the figures relate to and the content of the figures

Data are received from Statistics Austria, only poultry data from Poultry Health Data.

Definitions used for different types of animals, herds, flocks and holdings as well as the types covered by the information

Cattle: BGBl. II Nr. 147/2009 (Statistiken über den Viehbestand)

Swine, Sheep and Goats: BGBl. II Nr. 291/2009 (Tierkennzeichnungs- und Registrierungsverordnung 2009)

Poultry: BGBl. II Nr. 310/2007 (Erstellung der Statistik über die Agrarstruktur und den Viehbestand im Jahr 2007); BGBl. II Nr. 356/2003 (Erhebung der Geflügelschlachtungen in Betrieben mit min. 5000 Vorjahres-Geflügelschlachtungen)

Geographical distribution and size distribution of the herds, flocks and holdings

Pigs: 97.46 % of all pigs are kept in 84.41 % of the holdings that are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria;

Sheep: 72.75 % of the sheep holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 75.72 % of the sheep are kept there.

Goats: 70.13 % of the goat holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 77.71 % of the goats are kept there.

Solipeds: 66.63 % of the soliped holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and the Tyrol; 71.03 % of the solipeds are kept there.

Deer: 89.48 % of the deer holdings are located in the 4 provinces Carinthia, Lower Austria, Upper Austria and Styria; 90.47% of the deer are kept there.

Cattle: 74.34 % of the cattle holdings are located in the 4 provinces Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Styria and Tirol; 77.53% of the cattle are kept there.

Additional information

Nil

Table 1 Susceptible animal populations: number of herds and holdings rearing animals, 2014

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2014	holding	65209	
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	01.04.2014	animal	1953201	
in total	Cattle (bovine animals)	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	675905	(including calves)
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	01.04.2014	animal	620494	
	Cattle (bovine animals) - calves (under 1 year)	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	67203	
in total	Pigs	01.04.2014	holding	25945	
in total	Pigs	01.04.2014	animal	2894848	
in total	Pigs	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	5409578	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2014	holding	6057	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	01.04.2014	animal	249221	
	Pigs - breeding animals - unspecified - sows	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	89936	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2014	holding	19715	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	01.04.2014	animal	1077089	
	Pigs - fattening pigs	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	5319642	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2014	holding	15224	
in total	Sheep	01.04.2014	animal	410699	
in total	Sheep	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	282625	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2014	holding	14795	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	01.04.2014	animal	235402	
	Sheep - animals over 1 year	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	65437	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2014	holding	12359	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	01.04.2014	animal	175297	
	Sheep - animals under 1 year (lambs)	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	217188	
in total	Goats	01.04.2014	holding	10056	
in total	Goats	01.04.2014	animal	91663	
in total	Goats	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	55894	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2014	holding	9821	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	01.04.2014	animal	61988	
	Goats - animals over 1 year	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	12215	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2014	holding	4199	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	01.04.2014	animal	29675	
	Goats - animals under 1 year	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	43679	

Animal Populations

	Animals species	date	Unit	Number	comments
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2014	holding	14720	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	01.04.2014	animal	72439	
in total	Solipeds, domestic	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	943	
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2014	holding	1493	
in total	Deer - farmed	01.04.2014	animal	33355	
in total	Gallus gallus (fowl)	2014	slaughter animal (heads)	69818206	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	holding	55	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	animal	869926	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	herd/flock	107	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	holding	14	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	animal	220430	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	herd/flock	26	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2014	holding	475	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2014	animal	61797654	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - broilers	2014	herd/flock	3868	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2014	holding	1080	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2014	animal	9284405	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - laying hens	2014	herd/flock	2759	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	holding	54	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	animal	869926	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for broiler production line	2014	herd/flock	107	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	holding	14	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	animal	220430	
	Gallus gallus (fowl) - parent breeding flocks for egg production line	2014	herd/flock	26	
in total	Turkeys	2014	holding	130	
in total	Turkeys	2014	animal	2037260	
in total	Turkeys	2014	herd/flock	365	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2014	holding	130	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2014	animal	2037260	
	Turkeys - meat production flocks	2014	herd/flock	365	

4. Information on Specific Zoonoses and Zoonotic Agents

The World Health Organization defines zoonoses as “those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man.” Foodstuffs often serve as vehicles of zoonotic infections. Zoonotic agents include viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites or other biological entities that are likely to cause zoonoses.

Collection of human cases

Starting with January 1st 2009 a new reporting system, the **epidemiological reporting system** (Epidemiologisches Meldesystem, EMS) has been put in operation at the MOH. The physicians report all notifiable diseases (case based) to the local health authorities which are part of the local administration authorities (“Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde”). The physicians working at the local health authorities (public health officers) have to enter the data of the human cases of all notifiable diseases in the data base EMS including all relevant variables and laboratory results (case based). Also the laboratories enter the results of their laboratory work in EMS via a gateway to streamline the process.

EMS is the one and only database for notifiable diseases in the human sector in Austria. This system is also the standard gateway for reporting to ECDC (TESSy). A short report is also extracted and compiled using EMS which is published nationwide monthly and once a year by the Federal Ministry of Health online on the BMG-homepage:

http://bmg.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Krankheiten/Uebertragbare_Krankheiten/Statistiken/Monatliche_Statistik_meldepflichtiger_Infektionskrankheiten_ab_2010).

Additionally data of primary isolates from patients typed in the national reference centres are available. The responsible reference centres for zoonotic diseases published the numbers of microbiologically typed primary isolates from humans; due to the fact that more than one bacterial strain could be isolated from single patients these figures may differ from the case numbers notified to the Federal Ministry.

In this report it is indicated which data source has been used for the reporting of human cases for each respective zoonosis.

General Information about the Food Sampling Strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples

and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

4.1. Salmonellosis

4.1.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human salmonellosis remains a major health problem in Austria. In 2014, the number of notified salmonellosis cases increased compared to 2013 by 12 % and remained the second highest reported food-borne pathogen after campylobacteriosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined since the peak in 1998/1999. The salmonella-contamination of raw poultry meat has declined from 30 % in 1999 to less than 5.5 % in 2009, and increased in 2012 to 9.3 % and in 2013 to 10 % and in 2014 to 11.5 % due to the fact that *S. Infantis* prevalence increased in poultry meat (10 %). The consumption of eggs and egg products that are contaminated with *Salmonella* is presumably the main cause of human infection (*S. Enteritidis*). The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report (table 2) reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS, n = 1,608 cases. This number shows an increase compared to the previous year.

As compared to the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis (see chapter campylobacteriosis), salmonella is the second most important cause for enteric diseases in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The incidence of human salmonellosis has significantly declined within the last years. Different foodstuffs (e.g. poultry meat, eggs, or mixed foodstuffs) may pose a certain risk therefore kitchen hygiene is of utmost importance.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

There were EU programs implemented to control the contamination of *Salmonella* in poultry, most programs involved meat and egg production. The effort of the intervention is directed toward improving the sanitation of breeding flocks and laying flocks, broiler flocks and turkey flocks according to EU legislation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started, especially to improve harmonization of monitoring and control programs along the food chain and update the target serovars in the different poultry populations, e.g. *S. Infantis* in broiler flocks or *S. Stanley* in turkey flocks..

Additional information

If zoonotic agents, which are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obligated to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.1.2. Salmonellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of salmonellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following four symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Fever
- Abdominal pain
- Vomiting

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Salmonella* (other than *S. Typhi* and *S. Paratyphi*) from stool or blood

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Sample material is processed as described in „Richtlinien für die Diagnostik von Salmonellen (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 11-12)“.

At the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* (NRC *Salmonella*) all isolates are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor Scheme. And further all *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally the antimicrobial resistance testing by disk diffusion method is performed with each isolate.

Notification system in place

Notification of salmonellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 1989 and 1990, human infections with salmonella increased markedly in Austria. After a peak in 1992, the incidence of salmonella illness decreased, but the number of infections has remained at a high level until 2002. Since that year the number of laboratory confirmed cases of human *Salmonella* cases has decreased by 81 % (2002: 8,403 cases, 2014: 1,608 notified cases).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, the number of human laboratory confirmed cases of salmonellosis notified to EMS increased compared to 2013.

The proportion of *S. Enteritidis* isolates out of all *Salmonella* cases increased in 2014 to 49 % (2013: 42.4 %). The most frequently identified *Enteritidis* phage types in 2014 were: PT 8, PT 14b, and PT 21.

The proportion of *S. Typhimurium* isolates reported increased to 12 % (2013: 7.2 %; 2012: 13.9 %). Most frequent definitive type was DT 120. 63 isolates of monophasic *S. group B* (1,4,[5],12:i:-) were found in humans (2013: 68 cases).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2014, the number of notified human laboratory confirmed cases of campylobacteriosis again exceeded the number of salmonellosis cases.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria on monthly and yearly basis. The yearly report is published on the Website of the FMH.

Table 2 Salmonellosis cases from humans - serotype distribution (EMS/NRC), 2014

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1,608	18.91	1,210	307	91
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	793	9.32	591	159	43
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	196	2.30	168	23	5
<i>S. Stanley</i>	128	1.50	117	6	5
<i>S. Infantis</i>	63	0.74	50	11	2
<i>S. Typhimurium, monophasic</i>	63	0.74	47	10	6
<i>S. Agona</i>	29	0.34	26	0	3
<i>S. serotype unspecified</i>	26	0.31	21	2	3
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	22	0.26	8	12	2
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	17	0.20	13	3	1
<i>S. Indiana</i>	14	0.16	9	3	2
<i>S. Virchow</i>	13	0.15	4	9	0
<i>S. Newport</i>	12	0.14	4	8	0
<i>S. Derby</i>	9	0.11	4	4	1
<i>S. group B, monophasic strain</i>	8	0.09	4	2	2
<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	8	0.09	5	1	2
<i>S. Coeln</i>	7	0.08	6	0	1
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	7	0.08	4	3	0
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	7	0.08	4	3	0
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	7	0.08	5	2	0
<i>S. Braenderup</i>	6	0.07	4	2	0
<i>S. Bredeney</i>	6	0.07	4	0	2
<i>S. group C1, monophasic strain</i>	6	0.07	3	2	1
<i>S. Napoli</i>	6	0.07	5	0	1
<i>S. Rissen</i>	6	0.07	3	2	1
<i>S. subspecies IIIb (diarizonae)</i>	6	0.07	6	0	0
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	6	0.07	6	0	0
<i>S. Thompson</i>	6	0.07	5	1	0
<i>S. Goldcoast</i>	5	0.06	4	1	0
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>	5	0.06	2	3	0
<i>S. Bareilly</i>	4	0.05	4	0	0
<i>S. Cerro</i>	4	0.05	3	0	1
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	4	0.05	0	4	0
<i>S. Hadar</i>	4	0.05	2	1	1
<i>S. Heidelberg</i>	4	0.05	1	3	0
<i>S. Muenchen</i>	4	0.05	3	1	0
<i>S. Abony</i>	3	0.04	3	0	0
<i>S. Albany</i>	3	0.04	2	1	0
<i>S. Anatum</i>	3	0.04	2	1	0
<i>S. Blockley</i>	3	0.04	3	0	0
<i>S. Give</i>	3	0.04	1	2	0
<i>S. Javiana</i>	3	0.04	2	1	0
<i>S. Mikawasima</i>	3	0.04	2	1	0

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1,608	18.91	1,210	307	91
<i>S. Montevideo</i>	3	0.04	2	1	0
<i>S. Panama</i>	3	0.04	2	0	1
<i>S. Schwarzengrund</i>	3	0.04	1	2	0
<i>S. Stanleyville</i>	3	0.04	3	0	0
<i>S. Brandenburg</i>	2	0.02	2	0	0
<i>S. Emek</i>	2	0.02	1	0	1
<i>S. Fluntern</i>	2	0.02	1	0	1
<i>S. Isangi</i>	2	0.02	1	1	0
<i>S. Kenya</i>	2	0.02	1	1	0
<i>S. Litchfield</i>	2	0.02	1	1	0
<i>S. Livingstone</i>	2	0.02	2	0	0
<i>S. London</i>	2	0.02	2	0	0
<i>S. Monschau</i>	2	0.02	0	0	2
<i>S. Paratyphi</i>	2	0.02	2	0	0
<i>S. Potsdam</i>	2	0.02	0	2	0
<i>S. Weltevreden</i>	2	0.02	1	1	0
<i>S. Adelaide</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Altona</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Amager</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Bispebjerg</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Bonn</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Chester</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Chicago</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Choleraesuis</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Concord</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Durham</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Ealing</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. enterica (Subsp I)</i>	1	0.01	0	0	1
<i>S. Glostrup</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. group C2, monophasic strain</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. group D2, monophasic strain</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Guinea</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Havana</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Houston</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Hvittingfoss</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Ibadan</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Jangwani</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Johannesburg</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Manhattan</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Meleagridis</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Muenster</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Ordonez</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Orientalis</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Poona</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Reading</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Richmond</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. San Diego</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Sendai</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Singapore</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0

Serotype	Cases				
	N	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
	1,608	18.91	1,210	307	91
<i>S. subspecies II (salamae)</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. subspecies IV (houtenae)</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Telelkebir</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Uganda</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Umbilo</i>	1	0.01	1	0	0
<i>S. Wangata</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>S. Zanzibar</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0

Data source: EMS, NRC 26.02.2015

Table 3 Salmonellosis isolates in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC), 2014

age groups	Salmonellosis			S. Enteritidis		S. Typhimurium		S. Stanley		S. Infantis		S. Typhimurium, monophasic		other and unknown serotypes	
	all	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F
< 1 year	45	25	20	4	6	5		1	1	2	3	0	4	13	6
1 to 4 years	195	113	82	67	52	20	13	5	2	4	1	3	5	14	9
5 to 14 years	261	150	111	100	65	17	16	9	11	2		6	5	16	14
15 to 24 years	233	143	90	56	48	15	7	24	5	7	5	8	3	33	22
25 to 44 years	339	183	156	83	67	19	17	27	16	8	5	5	3	41	48
45 to 64 years	294	151	143	63	66	21	17	9	8	6	4	3	8	49	40
65 years and older	241	114	127	51	65	18	11	5	5	7	9	6	4	27	33
All age groups	1,608	879	729	424	369	115	81	80	48	36	27	31	32	193	172

Data source: EMS, NRC 26.02.2015

Table 4 Salmonellosis isolates in humans – seasonal distribution (EMS/NRC), 2014

Month	Salmonellosis	S. Enteritidis	S. Typhimurium	S. Stanley	S. Infantis	S. Typhimurium, monophasic	other and unknown serotypes
January	80	23	15	11	2	8	21
February	70	15	16	2	7	3	27
March	106	17	10	47	9	2	21
April	89	19	5	23	5	3	34
May	100	45	10	13	6	3	23
June	121	69	12	7	1	6	26
July	201	130	26	3	8	4	30
August	254	175	24	7	7	6	35
September	260	159	23	3	6	11	58
October	171	74	29	8	5	10	45
November	92	41	14	3	1	5	28
December	64	26	12	1	6	2	17
Total	1,608	793	196	128	63	63	365

Data source: EMS, NRC 26.02.2015

4.1.3. *Salmonella* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, minced meat, eggs, vegetables, etc.

Defintion of positive finding

A positive sample is a sample from which *Salmonella* has been isolated.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 6579:2002 + Cor.1:2004 + Amd.1:2007.

The amount of tested food in general is 25 g. Some exceptions exist, according to the Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005, as indicated in tables 5-8.

All *Salmonella* isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for Salmonella in Graz and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK. Additionally all isolates are tested for their antibiotic susceptibility according to EUCAST.

In case of an outbreak situation the stored isolates may be further investigated with pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) or multiple-locus variable-number of tandem-repeats analysis (MLVA).

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Whenever *Salmonella* is detected the isolates are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored. Investigation into the source of the contamination is initiated if indicated.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions (e.g. new regulations, new control programs, etc) taken.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

All *Salmonella* serotypes should be covered by monitoring programs and/or microbiological criteria.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Salmonella spp. was detected in fresh broiler meat samples in 18.5% (27 out of 146) and in 3.3% of fresh turkey meat samples (2 out of 61). In the remaining fresh meat samples (n=9) from duck meat, geese meat and unspecified poultry meat no *Salmonella* have been detected.

Meat preparations, raw but intended to be eaten cooked contained *Salmonella* in 15.1% (CI:9-24%) of broiler meat, whereas 27 of 213 poultry meat preparations (broiler, turkey, unspecified) were tested positive (12.7%; CI:9-18%,). All poultry meat products, no matter if cooked or raw, contained *Salmonella* in 2 of 76 samples (2.6%; CI 1-9%). Seggregating the data for processing plant and slaughter house (fresh broiler meat), one sample was tested positive for *Salmonella* at a processing plant (20 samples tested). In total 1,080 samples of meat, minced meat, meat products and meat preparations (poultry not included) were tested, with 5 positive sample for *Salmonella*, 3 in pig meat preparations, (out of 188 samples tested), one in fresh venison (3 samples tested) and one in minced meat from bovine animals, intended to be eaten cooked (74 samples tested).

No *Salmonella* were found in 1,113 samples of milk, dairy products and cheeses, as in the years 2007-2013. 1,951 samples of different matrices were tested for *Salmonella*, resulting in two positive findings in the category "vegetables – leaves" and "other processed food products and prepared dishes".

95 samples of egg products have been tested for *Salmonella* without any positive findings. Out of the 114 samples from packing centres, farms, retail, catering or wholesale no sample was tested positive for *Salmonella* in table eggs.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks. Since January 2012, the Outbreak Detection System (ODS) for the early detection of Salmonellosis has been installed in Austria. Within this tool realtime data on *Salmonella* isolates are utilized to determine a threshold value. If the number of *Salmonella* cases of the current week exceeds this threshold, a signal indicates a possible outbreak. This signal enables an early start of outbreak investigations.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-020-14: *Salmonella* spp. in food – bakery products - pastry or cakes (containing raw cream) - at catering - surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants, cafes etc., preferably from buffets or from glass cabinets.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - June

Type of specimen taken

Cakes or pastry, with special focus on products with “raw” fillings (not baked).

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: at least 200g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

58 samples tested: *Salmonella* was not detected in any sample

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria*.

Austrian food experts do not recommend further specific campaigns on cakes and pastry containing raw cream, due to the low rate of positive results.

Campaign A-023-14: *Salmonella* spp. in food – vegetables - leaves & vegetables - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

Vegetables, especially salad (pre-cut, ready to eat), pre-cut vegetables and sprouted seeds (6 samples)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: at least 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

55 samples tested: *Salmonella* was detected in 1 sample (*S. Mbandaka* in Rucola).

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria*, VTEC, Hepatitis A Virus.

Austrian food experts do recommend further specific campaigns, focussing on microbiological hazards in food of non-animal origin.

Campaign A-036-14: *Salmonella* spp. in food – fruits - frozen or ready-to-eat - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - September

Type of specimen taken

Berries (frozen and ready-to-eat) and pre-cut melons (ready-to-eat only) have been sampled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

60 samples tested: *Salmonella* was not detected in any sample

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria*, pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (VTEC), Norovirus and Hepatitis A Virus.

Austrian food experts suggest further campaigns concerning food of non animal origin and microbiological hazards. Therefore in 2015 another campaign in fruits and vegetables is planned.

Campaign A-801-14: *Salmonella* spp. in food – Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) – meat products and fermented sausages – at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February to March

Type of specimen taken

Red meat - meat products and fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

95 samples were tested: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes* and VTEC

Campaign A-802-14: *Salmonella* spp. in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled- at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April to June

Type of specimen taken

Ready-to-eat salads with or without mayonnaise, spreads

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Salmonella* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

39 samples tested: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Table 5 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry meat and meat products, 2014

Food	Sampling Details Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin Sampling Unit	Sample Weight Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Derby	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT Z1	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. group B, monophasic strain	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Mbandaka	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Schwarzengrund	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Stanley	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Thompson	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcase	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
		EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
		XX single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Farm	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT single (food/feed)	10 Gram	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	10 Gram	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
			25 Gram	82	15	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
		EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	16	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
		XX single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Slaughterhouse	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	EU single (food/feed)		25 Gram	12	6	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	1
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX single (food/feed)	25 Gram	85	14	0	1	0	13	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from duck - fresh	Retail	EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from duck - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	XX single (food/feed)	25 Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from geese - fresh	Retail	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Catering	AT single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 5 cont.

Food	Sampling Details		Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Derby	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT Z1	Salmonella - S. group B, monophasic strain	Salmonella - S. infantis	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - S. Schwarzengrund	Salmonella - S. Stanley	Salmonella - S. Thompson	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified
	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin Sampling Unit													
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	73	11	1	0	1	9	0	0	1	0
Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	38	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	
Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0		
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from turkey - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	2	0	0	0	2	0	0		

Table 6 *Salmonella* spp. in red meat and products thereof, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. group B, monophasic strain	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Infantis	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - DT 193	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 Gram	8				0	0	0	0	0	0				
Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					10 Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)				10 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					10 Gram	26	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	43	1	0	0	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	70	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from bovine animals and pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					10 Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0				
Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. group B, monophasic strain	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 193	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	Salmonella spp., unspecified	
Meat from pig - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	67	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Slaughterhouse	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	Gram						3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Processing plant	AT			single (food/feed)	10	Gram	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Retail	XX			single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	114	1	0	0	1	1	
					25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	10	2	0	1	1	0	0					
Meat from pig - meat products		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
					Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from pig - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram			2	0	0	0	0	0		
		25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0					
Meat from sheep - fresh		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from sheep - meat preparation		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from sheep - minced meat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from wild boar - meat products		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat from wild game - birds - fresh		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0		
					Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0			
					XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0			
					EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0				

Table 6 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella	Salmonella - S. group B, monophasic strain	Salmonella - S. Infantis	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 193	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	Salmonella spp., unspecified
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	75	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Slaughterhouse	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
campaign A-801-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
campaign A-801-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	50	0	0	0	0	0	0		
EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0			

Table 7 *Salmonella* spp. in milk and dairy products, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Cheeses made from cows milk		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	73	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - soft and semi-soft		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0

Table 7 cont.

Food	Sampling Details		Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified
	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin						
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	41	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	196	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	226	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	183	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	175	0	0
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
	Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of pasteurised/UHT products	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0

Table 8 *Salmonella* spp. in other food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Bredeney	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Mbandaka	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified
Bakery products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Bakery products - bread		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	43	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Bakery products - cakes - containing raw cream	campaign A-020-14	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	90	0	0	0	0	0
	EU		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	
	campaign A-020-14	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	27	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
Beverages, non-alcoholic - soft drinks		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cereals and meals		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	49	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cocoa and cocoa preparations, coffee and tea		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	55	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	42	0	0	0	0	0	
		XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
XX		single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bredeney	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified
Crustaceans		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
XX	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
Crustaceans - shrimps		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
Egg products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Egg products - dried		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Egg products - liquid		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
			Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Egg products - ready-to-eat		Packing centre	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Eggs - table eggs		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	298	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
					300	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
					300	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	300	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
					300	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	23	0	0	0	0	
					300	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	
					328	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
					350	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
350	Gram				1	0	0	0	0			

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bredeley	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Catering	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fish - smoked		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - raw		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - smoked		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Fruits		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - non-pre-cut	campaign A-036-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	campaign A-036-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut - ready-to-eat	campaign A-036-14	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	0	0	0	0	0
Fruits - products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Fruits and vegetables		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bredeney	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified		
Infant formula		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0		
Juice - fruit juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Juice - fruit juice - unpasteurised		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Juice - mixed juice		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Live bivalve molluscs - mussels		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Mushrooms		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Nuts and nut products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	42	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	32	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	41	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0		
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0		
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0		
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0		
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Nuts and nut products - roasted		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Other food		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)				25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Processing plant	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0		
Retail	AT			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0		
	EU			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
	XE			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
	XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bredeney	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified
Other food of non-animal origin		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
			Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
					25	Gram	308	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	36	1	1	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	68	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	162	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	74	0	0	0	0	0
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	30	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	22	0	0	0	0	0
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled	campaign A-802-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	33	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - frozen		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Ready-to-eat salads		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	
			AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	34	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Sauce and dressings		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	

Table 8 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Salmonella spp.	Salmonella - S. Bredeney	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	Salmonella - S. Mbandaka	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	
Seeds, dried		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0			
Seeds, sprouted		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Spices and herbs		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	29	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
XE	single (food/feed)		25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0			
Spices and herbs - dried		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0		
Sweets		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		campaign A-023-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0
EU	single (food/feed)			25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0		
Vegetables - non-pre-cut		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		campaign A-023-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	1	0	0	1	0
				XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - pre-cut		Processing plant	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables - products		Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	

4.1.4. *Salmonella* spp. in animals

A. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - breeding flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are only parent flocks in Austria. The permanent monitoring plan performed by a national program takes place at hatcheries and on farm level; each flock is tested regularly as well by the farmer as by the Veterinary Authorities.

If *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Hadar* and *S. Virchow* or *S. Pullorum Gallinarum* is isolated from breeding flocks at the hatchery the flock is banned and sampled for confirmation on the farm: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens are pooled.

If a parent flock tests positive for other salmonella serotypes, official veterinarians are required to investigate the source of infection to optimise biosecurity.

Frequency of the sampling

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Every flock is tested at day one

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

1. Routine testing: Every flock is tested at the age of 4 and 12 weeks and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit.

2. Confirmation: If routine testing reveals positive Salmonella test results then follow-up test must be performed from the identical flock.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! Monitoring is performed according the national program and takes place at the hatchery and on the farm: at the hatchery: each flock is tested every two weeks by the industry, and every 16 weeks by the Veterinary Authorities; on the farm: each flock ist tested every two weeks by the farmer and 3 times by the Veterinary Authorities (at beginning of production, in the middle of the production period and within the last 8 weeks before slaughter).

Type of specimen taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: drag swabs, pooled faeces.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: Boot swabs, pooled faeces; in the hatchery: dust, meconium, broken eggshells and hatched eggs.

For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs or 200 to 300 pooled droppings of 1 gram per flock, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Breeding flocks: Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: 5 pairs of boot swabs, pooled faeces, collection of dust.

For confirmation: For confirmation: 300 faeces samples and inner organs of 5 chickens or intestinal content of 5 chickens were pooled.

Case definition

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Routine testing: *Salmonella* spp. isolated from samples taken

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Day-old chicks

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like XLD or SM2. All isolates are sent to the NRC Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Rearing period

Other: See day old chicks

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Production period

Other: See day old chicks

Vaccination policy

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The national program for parent flocks made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks! The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Breeding flocks (separate elite, grand parent and parent flocks when necessary)

There are no separate elite and grand parent flocks in Austria, only parent flocks!

Measures according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation:

- Banning of the incriminated sector of the holding
- Culling of the infected flock
- Disposal of the hatched eggs
- Abolishing of the restriction after cleaning and disinfection
- If necessary prescriptions of GMP to prevent re-infection

Notification system in place

All positive results from parent flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health (BMG).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, 133 parent flocks of *Gallus gallus* were in production. *Salmonella* spp. was detected in one parent flock. The *Salmonella* isolated from the parent flock for egg production was *S. Oranienburg*. None of the target serotypes was detected in the Austrian parent flocks, therefore the EU-target was achieved in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Salmonella* spp. in *Gallus gallus* - flocks of laying hens

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Laying hens flocks

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks sampling two pairs of boot swabs, at least one testing per year is done by an official veterinarian (boot swabs, dust samples and faeces for residue testing are taken) according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

At the earliest 3 weeks prior to slaughter, two pairs of boot swabs must be taken from each flock. Since May 2007, every flock has been tested in accordance to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Frequency of the sampling

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Chickens are tested at day one.

Laying hens: Rearing period

3 times (at day one, week 8 to 12) and two weeks before moving to laying phase or laying unit

Laying hens: Production period

Each flock is tested every 15 weeks with two pairs of boot swabs; an official veterinarian samples every flock at least once a year according to Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter with two pairs of boot swabs at farm

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

According to the program of the cooperatives voluntary surface swabs (e.g. every eight weeks)

Type of specimen taken

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces

Laying hens: Production period

Boot swabs, pooled faeces in holdings with enriched cages; official controls: additional dust samples and pooled faeces for antimicrobial testing

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Voluntary e.g. surface swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Laying hens: Day-old chicks

Visibly soiled hatcher basket liners, dead chicks if available

Laying hens: Rearing period

2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: Production period

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 25 g of dust and 60 pooled faeces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

No legal requirements, e.g. surface swabs

Case definition**Laying hens: Day-old chicks**

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated from samples taken

Laying hens: Production period

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs or dust or detection of antimicrobials or bacterial growth inhibitory effect in feces samples

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Laying hens: At slaughter

No sampling

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Salmonella spp. isolated from surface swabs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Laying hens: Day-old chicks**

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like XLD or SM2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Laying hens: Rearing period

Day old chicks.

Laying hens: Production period

Day old chicks.

Laying hens: Before slaughter at farm

Day old chicks.

Laying hens: At slaughter

Day old chicks.

Eggs at packing centre (flock based approach)

Day old chicks.

Vaccination policy**Laying hens flocks**

The national program made vaccination against *Salmonella* Enteritidis mandatory for all flocks.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place**Laying hens flocks**

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Laying hens flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 517/2011.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

All actions according to EU- and national legislation

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target Serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Laying hens flocks

No class A eggs or culling in case of association with a food borne outbreak; EU regulation No 1237/2007 is in force

Notification system in place

All positive results from laying flocks must be reported to the local authorities and via the Poultry Health Data to the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH).

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014 2,759 laying hen flocks were in production. *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 44 flocks. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* (including the monophasic variant) were identified in 10 flocks (0.4 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. Salmonella spp. in *Gallus gallus* - broiler flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Broiler flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not intended, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Within 3 weeks before slaughter at farm 2 pairs of boot swabs have to be taken. 10 % of the flocks have to be tested by the competent authority. Commission Regulation (EC) No 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EC) No 200/2012 is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

No sampling

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

No legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled faeces

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 646/2007, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012, is in force since 01.01.2009

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

Salmonella spp. isolated

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Salmonella spp. isolated

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from sample material

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used**Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks**

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like XLD or SM2. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

See day-old chicks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no testing

Vaccination policy

Broiler flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Broiler flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Broiler flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 200/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Broiler flocks: Day-old chicks

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Rearing period

Competitive exclusion strategies take place.

Broiler flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Competitive exclusion strategies take place. Logistic Slaughtering is permitted for *Salmonella* spp. positive flocks

Broiler flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission regulation 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in broiler flocks had to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014 3,868 broiler flocks were in production. *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 112 flocks. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* (no monophasic variant) were identified in 15 flocks (0.4 %). The EU-target was achieved in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Salmonella* spp. in turkey - meat production flocks

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Meat production flocks

Within 3 weeks prior to slaughter boot swabs have to be taken. Other programs are not foreseen, only voluntary sampling by the farmer or sampling according to private cooperatives is performed.

Frequency of the sampling

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. at day one each flock

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Type of specimen taken

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

no legal requirements, e.g. visibly soiled hatcher basket liners

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

no legal requirements, e.g. pooled feces

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Industry sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock

Official sampling: 2 pairs of boot swabs per flock, 60 pooled faeces samples (150g)

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

no sampling

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No sampling

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Two pairs of boot swabs per flock; 10 % of the flocks sampled by competent authority, Regulation EU 584/2008, followed by Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012, is in force since 01.01.2010

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Case definition

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Rearing period

No legal requirements

Meat production flocks: Before slaughter at farm

Salmonella spp. isolated from boot swabs

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

No sampling

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Meat production flocks: Day-old chicks

Sample material is incubated in liquid medium. Modification of ISO 6579 (2002), where a semi solid medium (MSRV) is used as the single selective enrichment medium. The semi solid medium is incubated at 41.5+/- 1°C for 2-times 24 hours. Suspected samples are subcultured on solid media like XLD or SM. All isolates are sent to the NRL Salmonella and serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lyso-typed according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

see day-old chicks

Vaccination policy

Meat production flocks

Neither legal requirements nor recommendations

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Meat production flocks

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Meat production flocks

The Austrian control program is conducted according to the National Poultry Hygiene Regulation (BGBl. II 2007/100, Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007 as amended). This Regulation is in line with Commission Regulation (EU) No 1190/2012.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Review of the target serovars

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Meat production flocks: At slaughter (flocks based approach)

According to Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005

Notification system in place

All positive findings in turkey broiler flocks have to be notified to the local authority and via the Poultry health data (PHD) to the Federal Ministry of Health.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, 365 turkey meat production flocks existed in Austria. *Salmonella* spp. was detected in 12 flocks. *S. Enteritidis* or *S. Typhimurium* was not identified in any turkey flock. The EU-target was achieved in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 9 *Salmonella* spp. in poultry breeding flocks (*Gallus gallus*), 2014

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Oranienburg</i>
Gallus gallus (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	11	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling	ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock			11	0	0	0	0
Gallus gallus (fowl), parent breeding flocks for egg production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	26	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock			26	1	0	0	1
Gallus gallus (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, during rearing period, control and eradication programmes	59	PHD	Objective sampling	Official and industry sampling	ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	No	herd/flock			59	0	0	0	0
Gallus gallus (fowl), parent breeding flocks for broiler production line, adult, control and eradication programmes	107	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	ISO 6579:2002/ Amd 1:2007	Yes	herd/flock			107	0	0	0	0

PHD: Poultry Health Data; A = animal sample

Table 10 *Salmonella* spp. in other commercial poultry, 2014

Animal species	No of flocks under control programme	Source of information	Sampling strategy	Sampler	Sample type	Analytical method	Target verification	Sampling unit	Comment	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i> and <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Enteritidis</i>	Total units positive for <i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Agona</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Anatum</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Coeh</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Dublin</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 14b	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 21	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 21c	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 4	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Enteritidis</i> - PT 8	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Infantis</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Kentucky</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Kottbus</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Llandoff</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Mbandaka</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Montevideo</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Putten</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Rissen</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Saintpaul</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Salmonella</i> - <i>S. group B, monophasic strain</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Senftenberg</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Stanley</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Tennessee</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Thompson</i>	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 104L	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium</i> - DT 46a	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Typhimurium, monophasic</i> - DT 193	<i>Salmonella</i> - <i>S. Worthington</i>	
Gallus gallus (fowl), Laying hens																																										
During rearing period, control and eradication programmes	424	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		424	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,759	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	1)	2,759	42	10	6	4	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	4	0	0	1	5	15	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	1	1	1	2	0
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,759	PHD	Census sampling	Industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd	2)	2,527	29	5	4	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	3	0	0	1	4	11	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,759	PHD	Objective sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		1,598	17	5	2	3	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	3	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Adult: at farm, control and eradication programmes	2,759	PHD	Suspect sampling	Official sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	No	flock/herd		15	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Gallus gallus (fowl); Broilers																																										
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	3,868	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	3)	3,868	112	17	16	1	3	1	3	0	1	0	0	0	15	56	1	3	1	2	8	1	0	0	3	12	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	
Turkeys; Breeding flocks																																										
Adult, at farm, control and eradication programmes	0	PHD																																								
Turkeys; Fattening flocks																																										
Before slaughter, at farm, control and eradication programmes	365	PHD	Census sampling	Official and industry sampling	animal sample	ISO 6579:2002/Amd 1:2007	Yes	flock/herd	4)	365	12	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	4	5	0	0	0	0	

PHD: Poultry Health Data

- 1) one flock harbouring three different serotypes (*S. Infantis*, *S. Montevideo*, *S. Tennessee*) and one flock two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT 21 and PT21c)
- 2) one flock harbouring two different serotypes (*S. Infantis* and *S. Montevideo*) and one flock two different *S. Enteritidis* phage types (PT 21 and PT21c)
- 3) one flock harbouring two different strains of *S. group B, monophasic*
- 4) two flocks harbouring two strains each of *S. Stanley* and *S. Senftenberg*

4.1.5. *Salmonella* spp. in feeding stuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Official monitoring based on risk assessment, own check programme by the industry based on HACCP.

Frequency of the sampling

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Assigned sampling plan, random samples are collected based on an official surveillance programme.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Type of specimen taken

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Feed material of cereal grain and oil seed or fruit origin

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Imported feed material of plant origin

Oil seed meals and cakes

Imported feed material of animal origin

Fish meal, dried animal by-products for pets

Process control in feed mills

Not applicable (n. a.)

Compound feeding stuffs

Feed for farm animals (mainly poultry) and pets

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Sampling is performed according EC-Directive 152/2009/EEC applying special hygiene requirements or sampling of original packaged products.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Definition of positive finding

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Domestic feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of plant origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Imported feed material of animal origin

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Process control in feed mills

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Compound feeding stuffs

Salmonella spp. isolated from the sample

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Domestic feed material of plant origin

Bacteriological method: ISO 6579:2002; sample weight: 25 g (samples related to suspected lots or cases are analysed by testing several subsamples in parallel); all isolates are sent to the NRC Salmonella are serotyped according to the White-Kauffmann-Le-Minor-Scheme. All *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* isolates are lysotyped according to the methods used by PHE, Colindale, UK.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

as above

Imported feed material of plant animal

as above

Imported feed material of animal origin

as above

Process control in feed mills

as above

Compound feeding stuffs

as above

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

National legislation: BGBl. Nr. 139/1999, as last amendet by BGBl. Nr. 87/2005 (Futtermittelgesetz 1999, § 3) and BGBl. Nr. 316/2010 (Futtermittelverordnung 2010) containing general requirements for feedingstuffs and BGBl. II Nr. 100/2007 (Geflügelhygieneverordnung 2007).

EC: VO (EG) 183/2005 (Futtermittelhygieneverordnung) and VO (EG) 882/2004 (Kontrollverordnung) with regard to *Salmonella* monitoring, general requirements for feed material and compound feed, coordinated annual control program

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings

Domestic feed material of plant origin

In the event of a positive result, the notification results in the confiscation of the infected feedingstuffs according to official measures. This includes the withdrawal of the feedingstuffs from the market, the recall of feed, decontamination of the feed, disposal or other use of the feed, exploration and elimination of the sources of contamination and operational measures to prevent future contaminations.

Domestic feed material of animal origin

See above

Imported feed material of plant origin

See above

Imported feed material of animal origin

See above

Process control in feed mills

See above

Compound feeding stuffs

See above

Notification system in place

The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) notifies the local authorities and the system has been in place since 1979. The legal basis of the RASFF is Regulation EC/178/2002.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the last 20 years, the quality of feed has improved due to the increase of numbers of farms, processing plants and retailer using HACCP concepts, traceability of contaminated feed/components of feed and palletizing feed/contaminated feed.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 11 *Salmonella* spp. in feed material of animal origin, 2014

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sampling Origin	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.
Feed material of land animal origin - protein meal	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0
Feed material of marine animal origin - fish meal	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 12 *Salmonella* spp. in compound feeding stuff, 2014

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sampling Origin	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Anatum	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Brandenburg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Cerro	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Derby	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Goettingen	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. group B, monophasic strain	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Kentucky	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Livingstone	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Rissen	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Typhimurium - DT 193
Compound feedingstuffs for cattle - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for pigs - final product - pelleted	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - broilers - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	27	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens - final product - pelleted	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for poultry (non specified) - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs for turkeys - final product - pelleted	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Compound feedingstuffs, not specified - final product - non-pelleted/meal	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pet food	Retail	single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pet food - dog snacks (pig ears, chewing bones)	Farm	single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	single (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
			EU	25	Gram	66	10	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	0	
	Retail	single (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	17	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
			XE	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Premixtures	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

Table 13 *Salmonella* spp. in other feed matter, 2014

Feed	Sampling Stage	Sampling Unit	Sampling Origin	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Agona	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. enterica subsp. diarizonae	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Llandoff	<i>Salmonella</i> - S. Senftenberg
Feed material of cereal grain origin - other cereal grain derived - by-products of brewing and distilling	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of cereal grain origin - wheat derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - linseed derived	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	1
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - other oil seeds derived	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - palm kernel derived	Retail	batch (food/feed)	EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - rape seed derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	19	0	0	0	0	0
EU			25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - soya (bean) derived	Farm	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	8	1	0	0	1	0
			EU	25	Gram	33	1	1	0	0	0
Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin - sunflower seed derived	Feed mill	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
			EU	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	1	1	0	0	0
	Retail	batch (food/feed)	AT	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0

Sampling context: Surveillance - official control - objective sampling

4.1.6. *Salmonella* serovars and phage type distribution

The methods of collecting, isolating and testing of *Salmonella* isolates are described in the chapters above respectively for each animal species, foodstuffs and in humans. The serotype and phage type distributions can be used to investigate the sources of the *Salmonella* infections in humans. Findings of same serovars and phagetypes in human cases and in foodstuffs or animals may indicate that the food category or animal species in question serves as a source of human infections. However, as information of the potential source of infection is not available, conclusions have to be made with caution.

Table 14 *Salmonella* serovars in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC), 2014

Serotype	human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	1,608	42	4	14	6	1	1	112	45	14	13	2	5
<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	793	1			1			16	7				
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	196				1			1	2		1		
<i>S. Stanley</i>	128		1	1						5			
<i>S. Typhimurium</i> - monophasic	63				1				2				
<i>S. Infantis</i>	63	38	2	11	2			56	4				
<i>S. Agona</i>	29							3	1	1			2
<i>Salmonella</i> spp., unspecified	26	1											
<i>S. Kentucky</i>	22							1			1		
<i>S. Bovismorbificans</i>	17												
<i>S. Indiana</i>	14												
<i>S. Virchow</i>	13												
<i>S. Newport</i>	12												
<i>S. Derby</i>	9			1							3		
<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	8							12	2	4	1	2	1
<i>S. group B, monophasic strain</i>	8			1	1			3			1		
<i>S. Coeln</i>	7							3	1				
<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	7	1					1	2	5				
<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	7									4			
<i>S. Kottbus</i>	7							3					
<i>S. Braenderup</i>	6												
<i>S. Napoli</i>	6												
<i>S. Thompson</i>	6	1						1	1				
<i>S. group C1, monophasic strain</i>	6												
<i>S. Rissen</i>	6								1		1		
<i>S. Bredeney</i>	6					1							
<i>S. subspecies IIIb (diarizonae)</i>	6												1
<i>S. Tennessee</i>	6								2				
<i>S. Goldcoast</i>	5												
<i>S. Oranienburg</i>	5												
<i>S. Corvallis</i>	4												
<i>S. Muenchen</i>	4												
<i>S. Hadar</i>	4												
<i>S. Heidelberg</i>	4												

Serotype	human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
Salmonella spp.	1,608	42	4	14	6	1	1	112	45	14	13	2	5
S. Bareilly	4												
S. Cerro	4										1		
S. Blockley	3												
S. Give	3												
S. Schwarzengrund	3		1										
S. Panama	3												
S. Stanleyville	3												
S. Javiana	3												
S. Albany	3												
S. Abony	3												
S. Anatum	3							1			1		
S. Montevideo	3							8	15				
S. Mikawasima	3												
S. Paratyphi	2												
S. Isangi	2												
S. Weltevreden	2												
S. Kenya	2												
S. Emek	2												
S. Brandenburg	2										1		
S. Potsdam	2												
S. Litchfield	2												
S. London	2												
S. Fluntern	2												
S. Monschau	2												
S. Livingstone	2										1		
S. Glostrup	1												
S. Bonn	1												
S. Chicago	1												
S. Meleagridis	1												
S. subspecies II (salamae)	1												
S. group C2, monophasic strain	1												
S. Umbilo	1												
S. group D2, monophasic strain	1												
S. Jangwani	1												
S. Guinea	1												
S. Altona	1												
S. Durham	1												
S. subspecies IV (houtenae)	1												
S. Muenster	1												
S. Chester	1												
S. Havana	1												
S. Wangata	1												
S. Ealing	1												
S. Manhattan	1												

Serotype	human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
Salmonella spp.	1,608	42	4	14	6	1	1	112	45	14	13	2	5
S. Houston	1												
S. Sendai	1												
S. Ordonez	1												
S. Singapore	1												
S. Orientalis	1												
S. Johannesburg	1												
S. Hvitvingfoss	1												
S. Concord	1												
S. Ibadan	1												
S. Teitelkebir	1												
S. Poona	1												
S. Amager	1												
S. Choleraesuis	1												
S. Uganda	1												
S. Reading	1												
S. Bispebjerg	1												
S. Richmond	1												
S. Zanzibar	1												
S. enterica (Subsp I)	1												
S. Adelaide	1												
S. Sandiego	1												
S. Dublin									1				
S. Goettingen											1		
S. Putten								1					
S. Llandoff								1	1				1
S. Worthington								1					

Data source: EMS/NRC as of February 2nd, 2015

Table 15 S. Enteritidis phage types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC), 2014

Phage type	human	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
All S. Enteritidis	793	1	0	0	1	0		16	7	0	0	0	0
PT 8	279				1			15	1				
PT 14b	158							1	2				
PT 21	110	1							1				
PT 4	69								2				
PT 1	23												
PT 29	18												
PT 2	16												
PT 13a	16												
PT U	14												
PT 6	10												
PT 6a	9												
phage type unspecified	8												
PT 11	7												
PT 4b	7												
PT 21c	7								1				
RDNC	6												
PT 12	6												
PT 6c	6												
PT 15a	5												
PT 3	4												
PT 30	2												
PT 5	2												
PT 20a	2												
PT 23	2												
PT 62	1												
PT 15	1												
PT 53	1												
PT 6e	1												
PT 14c	1												
PT 13	1												
PT 1b	1												

Data source: EMS/NRC Salmonella as of April 30, 2014

Table 16 S. Typhimurium definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC), 2014

Definitive type	human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
S. Typhimurium	196	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0
DT 120	45												
DT 104	27												
RDNC	25												
DT 1	22												
DT 193	20				1						1		
DT U311	9												
DT U	8												
DT 8	8												
DT U277	3												
DT U302	3												
DT 85	3												
DT 12	3												
definitive type unspecified	2												
DT 194	2												
DT 3	2												
DT 2	2												
DT 41	2												
DT U310	1												
DT 7a	1												
DT 75	1												
DT 208	1												
DT U291	1												
DT 20a	1												
DT U323	1												
DT 93	1												
DT 189	1												
DT 30	1												
DT 46A									1				
DT 104L								1	1				

Data source: EMS/NRC as of February 2nd, 2015

Table 17 S. Typhimurium, monophasic, definitive types in humans, food, animals and feed (EMS/NRC), 2014

Definitive types	human	Meat from broilers (Gallus gallus)	Meat from turkey	Meat from poultry, unspecified	Red meat	Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Spices and herbs	broiler flock	laying hen flock	turkey flock	Pet feed	Compound feedingstuffs for poultry - laying hens	Feed material of oil seed or fruit origin
S. Typhimurium - monophasic	63	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
DT 193	48				1				2				
DT U311	11												
definitive type unspecified	3												
DT U302	1												

Data source: EMS/NRC as of February 2nd, 2015

4.1.7. Antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates

Antimicrobial resistance is the ability of certain microorganisms to survive or grow in the presence of a given concentration of antimicrobial agent that usually would kill or inhibit the microorganism species in question. Antimicrobial resistant *Salmonella* strains may be transferred from animals or foodstuffs to humans.

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2014 all 1,716 isolates from humans (primary, secondary isolates, from infected person without clinical signs) were tested in the National Reference Centre for *Salmonella* for their antimicrobial susceptibility using the diffusion test – or for certain isolates of special interest the ϵ -test – and applying EUCAST clinical breakpoints or if not available those from CLSI. To identify low-level resistance to ciprofloxacin, pefloxacin was tested; in suspicion of high-level resistance to ciprofloxacin the ϵ -test was performed.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Resistance rates increased in the last years. In 2014, resistance rates to certain antimicrobials (ampicillin, sulfonamides, tetracycline) were above 10%. The reason for the increase in resistance rates is due to the higher incidence of multiresistant *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Infantis*, and *S. Kentucky* strains.

In 2014, 25 isolates with high-level resistance to ciprofloxacin were observed (19 times *S. Kentucky*, 2 times *S. Litchfield*, one time each *S. Corvallis*, *S. Mbandaka*, *S. Typhimurium* – monophasic, and *S. Infantis*); 16 isolates showed resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines (3 times each *S. Schwarzengrund* and *S. Stanley*, 2 times each *S. Enteritidis* PT21 and *S. Typhimurium* DT193, and one time each *S. Emek*, *S. Infantis*, *S. Kentucky*, *S. Ordonez*, *S. Uganda* and one isolate of monophasic strain of group B).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the target serovars in poultry and add new serovars of importance, e.g. those with (multi)resistant phenotypes

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRC-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES)

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *Salmonella* spp. in poultry

Description of sampling designs

All poultry flocks were subjected to the the national control program, established in accordance with Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (see chapter salmonella in animals). All salmonella isolated from poultry flocks (the flock is the epidemiological unit) at primary production or from carcasses of both broilers and fattening turkeys sampled for testing and verification of compliance, in accordance with point 2.1.5 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 were sent to the NRC-S for typing and for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Stratification procedures per animal population

Animals at farm

All salmonella isolated from poultry flocks were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility using the Sensititre® system. If a certain strain of salmonella was identified several times in one flock it was tested only once.

Slaughter house

Slaughter batches are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Randomisation procedures per animal population

Animals at farm

All flocks of laying hens, broilers and fattening turkeys produced in Austria in 2014 were part of the program.

Slaughter house

Slaughter batches are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Animals at farm

All nationally produced flocks of laying hens, broilers and turkeys are part of the national control program and were sampled according to Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 (census sampling). The sampling was performed by the competent authorities or by the industry. The samples were taken at primary production at the farm. Laying hens were tested for the first time at the age of 22-26 weeks and following every 15 weeks, and all flocks (also broilers and turkeys) within the last 3 weeks prior to slaughter. The sampling was part of the control program in accordance with Article 5(1) of Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm

Laying hens were tested every 15 weeks and all poultry flocks within the last 3 weeks prior to slaughter.

Slaughter house

Slaughter batches are sampled according to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 (HACCP and own checks, objective sampling)

Type of specimen taken

For animals and food see chapters "*Salmonella* spp. in animals".

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

For animals and food see chapters "*Salmonella* spp. in animals".

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

All *Salmonella* spp. isolated in veterinary and food laboratories as well as all primary isolates from humans were sent to the NRC-S where the susceptibility testing was performed using the disk diffusion method. According to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU all unique strains isolated in the course of the control program (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

For animals and food see chapters "*Salmonella* spp. in animals".

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Laboratory for Salmonella, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1). In case of resistance to 3rd-generation-cephalosporines or meropenem the testing with panel 2 (Table 4) was performed.

Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Control programs/strategies in place

Animals at farm

The control program is a national program, based on the national Poultry Hygiene Regulation, approved by the Commission and co-financed by the EU based on Regulation (EU) No 652/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014.

Slaughter house

The samples for testing and verification of compliance is performed by the industry in accordance with point 2.1.5 of Chapter 2 of Annex I to Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005.

Measures in case of positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Result of the investigation

Animals at farm

In 2014, a further decline of the proportion of the wild type population in salmonella isolated from laying hens, broilers and turkeys could be observed. But these effects are due to the appearance of resistant or multiresistant serotypes, as *S. Infantis*, *S. Stanley*, *S. Typhimurium* including the monophasic strains, *S. Saintpaul* and *S. Senftenberg*. The observed increase of resistant *S. Enteritidis*-isolates is due to the new ECOFF for Colistin that was reduced from > 8 mg/L to 2 mg/L (that value changed only for *S. Enteritidis*, for the other serotypes the ECOFF was in the > 2 mg/L). Although *S. Enteritidis* isolated in previous years showed lower MIC-distributions. Two out of 4 isolates of *S. Saintpaul* and 3 out of 4 *S. Senftenberg* (all from turkeys) showed resistance to gentamicin.

Slaughter house

In 2014, 24 isolates from broiler slaughter batches were obtained, no isolate from turkey slaughter batches. 62.5% of isolates showed resistance to quinolones, sulphonamides and tetracycline (all 15 *S. Infantis*-isolates). No resistance was found in the other serotypes (*S. Coeln*, *S. Montevideo*).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See above (results)

Relevance of the findings in feedingstuffs/animals/foodstuffs to human cases

In the last years, the number of human cases of *S. Infantis* remained similar (40-70 cases per year), although out of those the proportion of multiresistant *S. Infantis* steadily increased. This multiresistant *S. Infantis* is the most prevalent serotype in broilers in Austria but can also be found in laying hens and rarely in turkeys.

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the NRC-S Report (Jahresbericht) and the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 18 Breakpoints for antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* spp., 2014

antimicrobial	ECOFF	Range tested		zone diameter	
	concentration (µg/ml)			(mm)	
	wild type <=	lowest	highest	resistant <=	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,5	32	13	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128	16	
carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16	15	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,5	0,25	4	16	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,5	8	18	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0,06	0,016	8	23	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,25	8	14	
macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64	-	
penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64	13	
polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16	-	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128	13	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	256	8	1024	12	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64	11	
trimethoprim	2	0,25	32	14	
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0,06	0,016	2	21
	carbapenems - imipenem	1	0,12	16	15
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16	15
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0,12	0,06	32	20
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,5	0,25	64	16
	cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	8	0,5	64	18
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,25	128	18
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	*	0,06	64	***
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	**	0,12	128	****
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0,5	128	-

presumptive ESBL: *CTX/CTXCL >= 8 **CAZ/CAZCL >= 8 *** Ø CTXCL at least 5mm > Ø CTX **** Ø CAZCL at least 5mm > Ø CAZ

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *Salmonella* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 19 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. in humans and food (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1716	1,9	33	82	1,2	1	52	1,9	1	73	0	0	176	0	0	30	13,3	4	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1716	2,8	48	82	1,2	1	52	1,9	1	73	0	0	176	0,6	1	30	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	1716	0	0	82	0	0	52	0	0	73	0	0	176	0	0	30	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1716	0,9	16	82	2,4	2	52	3,8	2	73	0	0	176	0	0	30	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1716	0,9	15	82	0	0	52	3,8	2	73	0	0	176	0	0	30	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1716	18,5	317	82	93,9	77	52	59,6	31	73	8,2	6	176	50,6	89	30	76,7	23	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1716	0,5	8	82	13,4	11	52	0	0	73	1,4	1	176	4,5	8	30	6,7	2	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	1716	14,6	250	82	3,7	3	52	32,7	17	73	5,5	4	176	1,1	2	30	46,7	14	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1716	18,8	322	82	93,9	77	52	59,6	31	73	9,6	7	176	58,5	103	30	76,7	23	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1716	16,7	287	82	79,3	65	52	13,5	7	73	16,4	12	176	57,4	101	30	30	9	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1716	17,4	299	82	79,3	65	52	36,5	19	73	28,8	21	176	58	102	30	33,3	10	
trimethoprim	1716	3,5	60	82	0	0	52	3,8	2	73	0	0	176	0,6	1	30	23,3	7	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	1716	67,5	1159	82	6,1	5	52	36,5	19	73	69,9	51	176	38,6	68	30	16,7	5	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	1716	13,2	226	82	12,2	10	52	23,1	12	73	15,1	11	176	4	7	30	30	9	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	1716	3,1	54	82	2,4	2	52	1,9	1	73	0	0	176	0,6	1	30	3,3	1	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	1716	10,2	175	82	63,4	52	52	30,8	16	73	15,1	11	176	52,8	93	30	6,7	2	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	1716	3,7	63	82	14,6	12	52	3,8	2	73	0	0	176	4	7	30	43,3	13	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	1716	2,3	39	82	1,2	1	52	3,8	2	73	0	0	176	0	0	30	0	0	

Table 20 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* in humans, animals and food (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	829	0,1	1	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	829	0,1	1	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	829	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	829	0,2	2	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	829	0,2	2	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	829	4,6	38	2	50	1	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	829	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	829	1,2	10	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	829	5,2	43	2	50	1	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	829	0,2	2	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	5,6	1	24	0	0	1	0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	829	0,7	6	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
trimethoprim	829	0,4	3	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	829	93,6	776	2	50	1	-	-	-	18	94,4	17	24	100	24	1	100	1	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	829	5,3	44	2	50	1	-	-	-	18	5,6	1	24	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	829	0,5	4	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	829	0,5	4	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	829	0,1	1	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	829	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	18	0	0	24	0	0	1	0	0	

Table 21 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	203	1	2	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	203	14,3	29	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	100	1	-	-	-
carbapenems - meropenem	203	0	0	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	203	0,5	1	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	203	0,5	1	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	203	6,4	13	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	203	0	0	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
macrolides - azithromycin																		
penicillins - ampicillin	203	50,7	103	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	100	1	-	-	-
polymyxins - colistin																		
quinolones - nalidixic acid	203	4,9	10	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	203	51,2	104	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	100	1	-	-	-
tetracyclines - tetracycline	203	46,8	95	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	100	1	-	-	-
trimethoprim	203	5,9	12	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	203	37,4	76	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	100	4	1	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	203	10,8	22	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	203	8,9	18	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	203	26,6	54	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	203	14,3	29	-	-	-	1	0	0	4	0	0	1	100	1	-	-	-
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	203	2	4	-	-	-	1	100	1	4	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-

Table 22 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* monophasic strain in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	67	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	67	4,5	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
carbapenems - meropenem	67	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	67	1,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	67	1,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	67	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	67	1,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	67	91	61	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	100	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	67	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	67	91	61	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	100	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	67	92,5	62	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	100	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	67	4,5	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	67	1,5	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	67	7,5	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	67	4,5	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	67	80,6	54	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	100	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	67	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	67	3	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Table 23 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	146	4,1	6	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	146	0,7	1	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	146	0	0	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	146	2,1	3	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	146	2,1	3	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	146	86,3	126	-	-	-	10	90	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	100	10	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	146	0	0	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	146	10,3	15	-	-	-	10	10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	20	2	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	146	96,6	141	-	-	-	10	100	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	100	10	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	146	2,1	3	-	-	-	10	10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	146	2,1	3	-	-	-	10	10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	10	1	
trimethoprim	146	0,7	1	-	-	-	10	10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	146	2,7	4	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	146	86,3	126	-	-	-	10	90	9	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	80	8	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	146	4,8	7	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	10	1	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	146	2,7	4	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	10	1	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	146	2,7	4	-	-	-	10	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	146	0,7	1	-	-	-	10	10	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	

Table 24 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	70	0	0	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	70	0	0	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	70	0	0	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	70	1,4	1	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	70	1,4	1	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	70	71,4	50	70	100	70	3	100	3	7	85,7	6	101	85,1	86	2	100	2	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	70	8,6	6	70	15,7	11	3	0	0	7	14,3	1	101	7,9	8	2	50	1	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	70	2,9	2	70	2,9	2	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	70	75,7	53	70	100	70	3	100	3	7	100	7	101	98	99	2	100	2	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	70	80	56	70	91,4	64	3	100	3	7	100	7	101	98	99	2	100	2	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	70	77,1	54	70	92,9	65	3	100	3	7	100	7	101	98	99	2	100	2	
trimethoprim	70	8,6	6	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	70	18,6	13	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	2	2	2	0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	70	0	0	70	5,7	4	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	70	4,3	3	70	2,9	2	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	70	62,9	44	70	74,3	52	3	100	3	7	85,7	6	101	92,1	93	2	50	1	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	70	14,3	10	70	17,1	12	3	0	0	7	14,3	1	101	5,9	6	2	50	1	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	70	0	0	70	0	0	3	0	0	7	0	0	101	0	0	2	0	0	

Table 25 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested			micro-biological resistant			total units tested			micro-biological resistant			total units tested			micro-biological resistant			
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	12,5	1	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	12,5	1	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	33	3	1	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	33	3	1	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
trimethoprim	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	33	97	32	-	-	-	8	87,5	7	-	-	-	2	100	2	1	100	1	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	12,5	1	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	33	3	1	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	33	0	0	-	-	-	8	0	0	-	-	-	2	0	0	1	0	0	

Table 26 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	50	2	
trimethoprim	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	8	100	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	100	4	13	100	13	4	50	2	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	25	1	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	8	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0	0	13	0	0	4	0	0	

Table 27 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* in humans, food and (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n										
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	33,3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	33,3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	3	66,7	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	100	16	12	100	12	-	-	-	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	3	33,3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	3	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	0	0	12	0	0	-	-	-	

Table 28 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n										
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	14,3	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	28,6	2	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	14,3	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	14,3	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	76,9	10	2	100	2	-	-	-	
trimethoprim	7	14,3	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	7	85,7	6	1	100	1	-	-	-	13	23,1	3	2	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	76,9	10	2	100	2	-	-	-	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	7	0	0	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	7	14,3	1	1	0	0	-	-	-	13	0	0	2	0	0	-	-	-	

Table 29 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

		humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	
	N	%R	n																
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	30	3	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
carbapenems - meropenem	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	9	33,3	3	-	-	-	5	80	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	90	9	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin																			
penicillins - ampicillin	9	44,4	4	-	-	-	5	40	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	100	10	
polymyxins - colistin																			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	9	33,3	3	-	-	-	5	80	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	90	9	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	9	33,3	3	-	-	-	5	40	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	70	7	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	9	11,1	1	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	40	4	
trimethoprim	9	33,3	3	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	70	7	
Panel 1																			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	
fully sensitive	9	55,6	5	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	40	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	9	11,1	1	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	9	33,3	3	-	-	-	5	20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	100	10	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	9	0	0	-	-	-	5	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0	0	

Table 30 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before in humans, food and animals (Diffusion method, clinical breakpoint), 2014

antimicrobial	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	341	6,5	22	9	11,1	1	25	4	1	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	341	3,8	13	9	11,1	1	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	341	0	0	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	341	2,3	8	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	341	2,1	7	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	341	24	82	9	66,7	6	25	52	13	7	0	0	21	14,3	3	2	50	1
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	341	0,3	1	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	50	1
macrolides - azithromycin																		
penicillins - ampicillin	341	16,1	55	9	11,1	1	25	52	13	7	0	0	21	4,8	1	2	50	1
polymyxins - colistin																		
quinolones - nalidixic acid	341	20,2	69	9	66,7	6	25	48	12	7	0	0	21	19	4	2	50	1
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	341	16,4	56	9	11,1	1	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	4,8	1	2	0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline	341	22,3	76	9	0	0	25	52	13	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	50	1
trimethoprim	341	9,1	31	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	4,8	1	2	0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n	N	%	n
fully sensitive	341	69,2	236	9	33,3	3	25	48	12	7	100	7	21	71,4	15	2	50	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	341	8,2	28	9	55,6	5	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	23,8	5	2	0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	341	5	17	9	0	0	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	4,8	1	2	0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	341	4,4	15	9	0	0	25	48	12	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	341	4,1	14	9	0	0	25	4	1	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	50	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	341	9,1	31	9	11,1	1	25	0	0	7	0	0	21	0	0	2	0	0

Table 31 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>Salmonella</i> spp.	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	24			0			45			113			14		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	35,7	5
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	24	0,0	0				45	2,2	1	113	0,9	1	14	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	24	62,5	15				45	8,9	4	113	50,4	57	14	71,4	10
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	24	8,3	2				45	0,0	0	113	1,8	2	14	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,9	1	14	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin	24	0,0	0				45	6,7	3	113	1,8	2	14	50,0	7
polymyxins - colistin	24	0,0	0				45	17,8	8	113	19,5	22	14	7,1	1
quinolones - nalidixic acid	24	62,5	15				45	8,9	4	113	50,4	57	14	71,4	10
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	24	62,5	15				45	17,8	8	113	49,6	56	14	14,3	2
tetracyclines - tetracycline	24	62,5	15				45	24,4	11	113	50,4	57	14	35,7	5
trimethoprim	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	14,3	2
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	24	37,5	9				45	55,6	25	113	29,2	33	14	7,1	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	24	0,0	0				45	28,9	13	113	20,4	23	14	42,9	6
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	1,8	2	14	7,1	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	24	54,2	13				45	13,3	6	113	44,2	50	14	7,1	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	24	8,3	2				45	2,2	1	113	4,4	5	14	28,6	4
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	24	0,0	0				45	0,0	0	113	0,0	0	14	7,1	1

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 32 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Enteritidis</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			7			16			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested														
	N	%R	n												
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
polymyxins - colistin							7	85,7	6	16	100,0	16			
quinolones - nalidixic acid							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							7	14,3	1	16	0,0	0			
tetracyclines - tetracycline							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
trimethoprim							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n												
fully sensitive							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							7	100,0	7	16	100,0	16			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							7	0,0	0	16	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 33 Qualitative table: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			2			1			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							2	50,0	1	1	100,0	1			
carbapenems - meropenem							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin							2	50,0	1	1	100,0	1			
polymyxins - colistin							2	50,0	1	1	0,0	0			
quinolones - nalidixic acid							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							2	50,0	1	1	100,0	1			
tetracyclines - tetracycline							2	50,0	1	1	100,0	1			
trimethoprim							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							2	50,0	1	1	0,0	0			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							2	50,0	1	1	100,0	1			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	1	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 34 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			2			0			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested														
	N	%R	n												
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							2	0,0	0						
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							2	0,0	0						
carbapenems - meropenem							2	0,0	0						
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							2	0,0	0						
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							2	0,0	0						
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							2	0,0	0						
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							2	0,0	0						
macrolides - azithromycin							2	0,0	0						
penicillins - ampicillin							2	100,0	2						
polymyxins - colistin							2	0,0	0						
quinolones - nalidixic acid							2	0,0	0						
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							2	100,0	2						
tetracyclines - tetracycline							2	100,0	2						
trimethoprim							2	0,0	0						
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n												
fully sensitive							2	0,0	0						
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							2	0,0	0						
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0						
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							2	100,0	2						
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0						
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 35 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Agona</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			1			3			1		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
polymyxins - colistin							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
trimethoprim							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive							1	100,0	1	3	100,0	3	1	100,0	1
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							1	0,0	0	3	0,0	0	1	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 36 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Infantis</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	15			0			4			56			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	15	100,0	15				4	100,0	4	56	96,4	54			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	15	13,3	2				4	0,0	0	56	3,6	2			
macrolides - azithromycin	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	1,8	1			
penicillins - ampicillin	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
polymyxins - colistin	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	3,6	2			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	15	100,0	15				4	100,0	4	56	96,4	54			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	15	100,0	15				4	100,0	4	56	96,4	54			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	15	100,0	15				4	100,0	4	56	96,4	54			
trimethoprim	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	3,6	2			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	15	86,7	13				4	100,0	4	56	89,3	50			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	15	13,3	2				4	0,0	0	56	7,1	4			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	15	0,0	0				4	0,0	0	56	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 37 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Mbandaka* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Mbandaka</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			5			2			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
polymyxins - colistin							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
quinolones - nalidixic acid							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
tetracyclines - tetracycline							5	80,0	4	2	100,0	2			
trimethoprim							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive							5	20,0	1	2	0,0	0			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							5	80,0	4	2	100,0	2			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							5	0,0	0	2	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 38 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Montevideo</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	6			0			15			8			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
polymyxins - colistin	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
trimethoprim	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	6	100,0	6				15	100,0	15	8	100,0	8			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	6	0,0	0				15	0,0	0	8	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 39 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Saintpaul* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Saintpaul</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			0			0			4		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n
	N	%R	n												
aminoglycosids - gentamicin													4	50,0	2
amphenicols - chloramphenicol													4	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem													4	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime													4	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime													4	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin													4	100,0	4
glycylcyclines - tigecycline													4	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin													4	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin													4	100,0	4
polymyxins - colistin													4	25,0	1
quinolones - nalidixic acid													4	100,0	4
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol													4	50,0	2
tetracyclines - tetracycline													4	50,0	2
trimethoprim													4	50,0	2
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n												
fully sensitive													4	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial													4	0,0	0
resistant to 2 antimicrobials													4	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials													4	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials													4	75,0	3
resistant to >4 antimicrobials													4	25,0	1

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 40 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Senftenberg* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Senftenberg</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			2			12			4		
antimicrobial	total units tested														
	N	%R	n												
aminoglycosids - gentamicin							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	75,0	3
amphenicols - chloramphenicol							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	25,0	1
glycylcyclines - tigecycline							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	25,0	1
polymyxins - colistin							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	25,0	1
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol							2	0,0	0	12	8,3	1	4	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	50,0	2
trimethoprim							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n												
fully sensitive							2	0,0	0	12	91,7	11	4	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial							2	0,0	0	12	8,3	1	4	75,0	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
resistant to 3 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0
resistant to 4 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	25,0	1
resistant to >4 antimicrobials							2	0,0	0	12	0,0	0	4	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 41 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Stanley* derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>S. Stanley</i>	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	0			0			0			0			5		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested											
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n									
aminoglycosids - gentamicin													5	0,0	0
amphenicols - chloramphenicol													5	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem													5	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefotaxime													5	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime													5	0,0	0
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin													5	100,0	5
glycylcyclines - tigecycline													5	0,0	0
macrolides - azithromycin													5	0,0	0
penicillins - ampicillin													5	40,0	2
polymyxins - colistin													5	0,0	0
quinolones - nalidixic acid													5	100,0	5
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol													5	0,0	0
tetracyclines - tetracycline													5	20,0	1
trimethoprim													5	0,0	0
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n									
fully sensitive													5	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial													5	60,0	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials													5	20,0	1
resistant to 3 antimicrobials													5	20,0	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials													5	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials													5	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 42 Qualitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other *S. serotypes* than the ones mentioned before, derived from AMR-monitoring (Dilution method, ECOFF), 2014

<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes	carcasses broilers			carcasses turkey			layer flocks			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	3			0			7			15			0		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	20,0	3			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
macrolides - azithromycin	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	6,7	1			
polymyxins - colistin	3	0,0	0				7	14,3	1	15	26,7	4			
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	20,0	3			
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
trimethoprim	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	3	100,0	3				7	85,7	6	15	60,0	9			
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	3	0,0	0				7	14,3	1	15	26,7	4			
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	13,3	2			
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	3	0,0	0				7	0,0	0	15	0,0	0			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 44 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 7 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
						n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0,0	7	0,0	0							7													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	0,0	7	0,0	0											7									
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0,0	7	0,0	0		7																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0,0	7	0,0	0					7															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0,0	7	0,0	0						7														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	0,0	7	0,0	0		6	1																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	7	0,0	7	0,0	0						4	3													
macrolides - azithromycin	7	0,0	7	0,0	0										3	4									
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0,0	7	0,0	0								1	6											
polymyxins - colistin	7	85,7	7	85,7	6									1	5	1									
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0,0	7	0,0	0										7										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	14,3	7	14,3	1												2	4						1	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	0,0	7	0,0	0									7											
trimethoprim	7	0,0	7	0,0	0						5	2													

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 45 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Typhimurium
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 2 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0							2													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	2	50,0	2	50,0	1											1					1				
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0	2	0,0	0			2																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						2														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,0	2	0,0	0							2													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0		1	1																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						2														
macrolides - azithromycin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0										2										
penicillins - ampicillin	2	50,0	2	50,0	1								1								1				
polymyxins - colistin	2	50,0	2	50,0	1									1	1										
quinolones - nalidixic acid	2	0,0	2	0,0	0										2										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	2	50,0	2	50,0	1												1							1	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	2	50,0	2	50,0	1									1				1							
trimethoprim	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						1	1													

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 46 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 2 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0							1	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	2	0,0	2	0,0	0											2									
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0	2	0,0	0			2																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						2														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,0	2	0,0	0							2													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0		1	1																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						2														
macrolides - azithromycin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0										2										
penicillins - ampicillin	2	100,0	2	100,0	2																2				
polymyxins - colistin	2	0,0	2	0,0	0									2											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	2	0,0	2	0,0	0										2										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	2	100,0	2	100,0	2																				2
tetracyclines - tetracycline	2	100,0	2	100,0	2																2				
trimethoprim	2	0,0	2	0,0	0						2														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 47 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Agona</i>
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 1 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1	0,0	0									1													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1	0,0	0													1									
carbapenems - meropenem	1	0,0	0				1																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	0,0	0							1															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	0,0	0								1														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1	0,0	0				1																		
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,0	0								1														
macrolides - azithromycin	1	0,0	0												1										
penicillins - ampicillin	1	0,0	0											1											
polymyxins - colistin	1	0,0	0											1											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1	0,0	0												1										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1	0,0	0															1							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1	0,0	0											1											
trimethoprim	1	0,0	0							1															

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 48 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Infantis derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Infantis
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 4 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	4	0,0	4	0,0	0							2	2												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	4	0,0	4	0,0	0											4									
carbapenems - meropenem	4	0,0	4	0,0	0		4																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	4	0,0	4	0,0	0					4															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	4	0,0	4	0,0	0						2	2													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	4	100,0	4	100,0	4						4														
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	4	0,0	4	0,0	0						4														
macrolides - azithromycin	4	0,0	4	0,0	0										2	2									
penicillins - ampicillin	4	0,0	4	0,0	0									4											
polymyxins - colistin	4	0,0	4	0,0	0									4											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	4	100,0	4	100,0	4																4				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	4	100,0	4	100,0	4																			4	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	4	100,0	4	100,0	4																4				
trimethoprim	4	0,0	4	0,0	0						4														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 49 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Mbandaka derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Mbandaka
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 5 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	5	0,0	0										5												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	5	0,0	0													5									
carbapenems - meropenem	5	0,0	0				5																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	5	0,0	0							5															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	5	0,0	0								4	1													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	5	0,0	0			4	1																		
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	5	0,0	0							4	1														
macrolides - azithromycin	5	0,0	0												2	3									
penicillins - ampicillin	5	0,0	0										5												
polymyxins - colistin	5	0,0	0											5											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	5	0,0	0																						
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	5	0,0	0														1	4							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	5	80,0	4											1								4			
trimethoprim	5	0,0	0							5															

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 50 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Montevideo derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Montevideo
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 15 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	15	0,0	0									15													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	15	0,0	0													15									
carbapenems - meropenem	15	0,0	0			15																			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	15	0,0	0							15															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	15	0,0	0								15														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	15	0,0	0			15																			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	15	0,0	0							12	3														
macrolides - azithromycin	15	0,0	0												11	4									
penicillins - ampicillin	15	0,0	0										3	12											
polymyxins - colistin	15	0,0	0										1	14											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	15	0,0	0												15										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	15	0,0	0														5	10							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	15	0,0	0											15											
trimethoprim	15	0,0	0								14	1													

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 51 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Senftenberg derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Senftenberg
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 2 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,0	0									1	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	2	0,0	0													2									
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0	0				2																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	0,0	0							2															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,0	0								2														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	2	0,0	0			2																			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	2	0,0	0							2															
macrolides - azithromycin	2	0,0	0												2										
penicillins - ampicillin	2	0,0	0										2												
polymyxins - colistin	2	0,0	0										1	1											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	2	0,0	0												2										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	2	0,0	0														1	1							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	2	0,0	0											2											
trimethoprim	2	0,0	0							2															

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 52 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before derived from control program in laying hens (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)
matrix	laying flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 7 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	7	0,0	0									4	2	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	7	0,0	0														7									
carbapenems - meropenem	7	0,0	0				6	1																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	7	0,0	0							7																
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	7	0,0	0								7															
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	7	0,0	0				7																			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	7	0,0	0							4	3															
macrolides - azithromycin	7	0,0	0											1	3	3										
penicillins - ampicillin	7	0,0	0										6	1												
polymyxins - colistin	7	14,3	1											6		1										
quinolones - nalidixic acid	7	0,0	0												7											
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	7	0,0	0														1	6								
tetracyclines - tetracycline	7	0,0	0											7												
trimethoprim	7	0,0	0							6	1															

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 53 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 113 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	113	0,0	0						72	30	11												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	113	0,9	1											102	10			1					
carbapenems - meropenem	113	0,0	0		109	4																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	113	0,0	0					110	3														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	113	0,0	0						90	23													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	113	50,4	57	27	29			6	50	1													
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	113	1,8	2					19	49	43	2												
macrolides - azithromycin	113	0,9	1									3	65	41	3	1							
penicillins - ampicillin	113	1,8	2								27	68	16					2					
polymyxins - colistin	113	19,5	22								3	88	16	6									
quinolones - nalidixic acid	113	50,4	57										50	6									
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	113	49,6	56												10	40	7						56
tetracyclines - tetracycline	113	50,4	57									54	2			1	1	55					
trimethoprim	113	0,0	0						74	38	1												

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 55 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Typhimurium
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 1 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				N	%R	n																	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1	0,0	0								1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1	100,0	1															1					
carbapenems - meropenem	1	0,0	0			1																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	0,0	0					1															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	0,0	0						1														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1	0,0	0			1																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,0	0						1														
macrolides - azithromycin	1	0,0	0										1										
penicillins - ampicillin	1	100,0	1																1				
polymyxins - colistin	1	0,0	0									1											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1	0,0	0											1									
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1	100,0	1																				1
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1	100,0	1													1							
trimethoprim	1	0,0	0						1														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 56 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium, monophasic strain derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Typhimurium, monophasic
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																								
carbapenems - meropenem																								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																								
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																								
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																								
macrolides - azithromycin																								
penicillins - ampicillin																								
polymyxins - colistin																								
quinolones - nalidixic acid																								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																								
tetracyclines - tetracycline																								
trimethoprim																								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 57 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Agona
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory **3** **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0,0	0						2	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0,0	0										3									
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0,0	0		3																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0,0	0					3														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0,0	0						3													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	0,0	0		3																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	0,0	0						2	1												
macrolides - azithromycin	3	0,0	0								2	1										
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0,0	0							2	1											
polymyxins - colistin	3	0,0	0								3											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	0,0	0									3										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	0,0	0										1	2								
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	0,0	0								3											
trimethoprim	3	0,0	0						2	1												

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 60 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Montevideo derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Montevideo
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 8 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	8	0,0	0									4	2	2											
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	8	0,0	0														8								
carbapenems - meropenem	8	0,0	0				8																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	8	0,0	0							8															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	8	0,0	0								8														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	8	0,0	0				5	3																	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	8	0,0	0							1	5	2													
macrolides - azithromycin	8	0,0	0												7	1									
penicillins - ampicillin	8	0,0	0										3	5											
polymyxins - colistin	8	0,0	0											8											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	8	0,0	0												7	1									
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	8	0,0	0														1	5	2						
tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	0,0	0											8											
trimethoprim	8	0,0	0							7	1														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 61 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Senftenberg derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Senftenberg
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 12 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	12	0,0	0									7	4	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	12	0,0	0													12										
carbapenems - meropenem	12	0,0	0					10	2																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	12	0,0	0								12															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	12	0,0	0									12														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	12	0,0	0				2	10																		
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	12	0,0	0							4	7	1														
macrolides - azithromycin	12	0,0	0											1	11											
penicillins - ampicillin	12	0,0	0										8	4												
polymyxins - colistin	12	0,0	0										2	10												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	12	0,0	0												11	1										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	12	8,3	1														1	10						1		
tetracyclines - tetracycline	12	0,0	0											10	2											
trimethoprim	12	0,0	0								9	3														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 62 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before derived from control program in broilers (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 15 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048			
	N	%R	n																						
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	15	0,0	0						10	4	1														
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	15	0,0	0									15													
carbapenems - meropenem	15	0,0	0			14	1																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	15	0,0	0							15															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	15	0,0	0							15															
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	15	20,0	3		3	9			3																
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	15	0,0	0					5	10																
macrolides - azithromycin	15	0,0	0								2	13													
penicillins - ampicillin	15	6,7	1							10	4								1						
polymyxins - colistin	15	26,7	4						1	10	4														
quinolones - nalidixic acid	15	20,0	3									11	1								3				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	15	0,0	0											7	7	1									
tetracyclines - tetracycline	15	0,0	0								15														
trimethoprim	15	0,0	0									11	4												

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 64 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Enteritidis* derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Enteritidis</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasse - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																								
carbapenems - meropenem																								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																								
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																								
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																								
macrolides - azithromycin																								
penicillins - ampicillin																								
polymyxins - colistin																								
quinolones - nalidixic acid																								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																								
tetracyclines - tetracycline																								
trimethoprim																								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 65 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium* derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Typhimurium</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasse - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																								
carbapenems - meropenem																								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																								
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																								
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																								
macrolides - azithromycin																								
penicillins - ampicillin																								
polymyxins - colistin																								
quinolones - nalidixic acid																								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																								
tetracyclines - tetracycline																								
trimethoprim																								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 66 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Typhimurium*, monophasic strain derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Typhimurium</i> , monophasic
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasse - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	resistant n	= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																							
carbapenems - meropenem																							
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																							
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																							
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																							
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																							
macrolides - azithromycin																							
penicillins - ampicillin																							
polymyxins - colistin																							
quinolones - nalidixic acid																							
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																							
tetracyclines - tetracycline																							
trimethoprim																							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 67 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Infantis* derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Infantis</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcase - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 15 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512
	N	%R	n																
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	15	0,0	0																
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	15	0,0	0																
carbapenems - meropenem	15	0,0	0																
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	15	0,0	0																
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	15	0,0	0																
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	15	100,0	15																
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	15	13,3	2																
macrolides - azithromycin	15	0,0	0																
penicillins - ampicillin	15	0,0	0																
polymyxins - colistin	15	0,0	0																
quinolones - nalidixic acid	15	100,0	15																
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	15	100,0	15																
tetracyclines - tetracycline	15	100,0	15																
trimethoprim	15	0,0	0																

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 68 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Montevideo* derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Montevideo</i>
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasse - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 6 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	6	0,0	0								5	1												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	6	0,0	0												6									
carbapenems - meropenem	6	0,0	0			6																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	6	0,0	0						6															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	6	0,0	0							6														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	6	0,0	0		6																			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	6	0,0	0							6														
macrolides - azithromycin	6	0,0	0										3	3										
penicillins - ampicillin	6	0,0	0									6												
polymyxins - colistin	6	0,0	0									6												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	6	0,0	0											6										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	6	0,0	0													6								
tetracyclines - tetracycline	6	0,0	0										6											
trimethoprim	6	0,0	0						6															

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 69 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other *Salmonella* serotypes than mentioned before derived from broiler carcasses at slaughterhouse (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)
matrix	Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - carcasse - chilled
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 3 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n		=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	3	0,0	0								3													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	3	0,0	0												3									
carbapenems - meropenem	3	0,0	0			3																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	3	0,0	0							3														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	3	0,0	0								3													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	3	0,0	0		3																			
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	3	0,0	0							1	2													
macrolides - azithromycin	3	0,0	0										3											
penicillins - ampicillin	3	0,0	0									3												
polymyxins - colistin	3	0,0	0									3												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	3	0,0	0											3										
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	3	0,0	0													3								
tetracyclines - tetracycline	3	0,0	0										3											
trimethoprim	3	0,0	0							3														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 70 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Salmonella* spp. derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> spp.
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 14 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	14	35,7	5									7		2	2				2	1						
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	14	0,0	0																							
carbapenems - meropenem	14	0,0	0					13	1																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	14	0,0	0								14															
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	14	0,0	0									14														
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	14	71,4	10				2	2		5	3	1	1													
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	14	0,0	0								11	3														
macrolides - azithromycin	14	0,0	0												11	3										
penicillins - ampicillin	14	50,0	7										6	1											7	
polymyxins - colistin	14	7,1	1										1	12	1											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	14	71,4	10												3	1		1			2	7				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	14	14,3	2														4	8							2	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	14	35,7	5											9						2	3					
trimethoprim	14	14,3	2								8	4								2						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 71 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Enteritidis derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Enteritidis
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
			N	%R	n																		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																							
carbapenems - meropenem																							
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																							
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																							
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																							
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																							
macrolides - azithromycin																							
penicillins - ampicillin																							
polymyxins - colistin																							
quinolones - nalidixic acid																							
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																							
tetracyclines - tetracycline																							
trimethoprim																							

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 72 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Typhimurium
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048		
	N	%R	n																					
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																								
carbapenems - meropenem																								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																								
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																								
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																								
macrolides - azithromycin																								
penicillins - ampicillin																								
polymyxins - colistin																								
quinolones - nalidixic acid																								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																								
tetracyclines - tetracycline																								
trimethoprim																								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 73 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Typhimurium, monophasic strain derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Typhimurium, monophasic
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																								
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																								
carbapenems - meropenem																								
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																								
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																								
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																								
macrolides - azithromycin																								
penicillins - ampicillin																								
polymyxins - colistin																								
quinolones - nalidixic acid																								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																								
tetracyclines - tetracycline																								
trimethoprim																								

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 74 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *S. Agona* derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>S. Agona</i>
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 1 Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
						n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	1	0,0	0									1													
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	1	0,0	0														1								
carbapenems - meropenem	1	0,0	0				1																		
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	1	0,0	0								1														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	1	0,0	0									1													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	1	0,0	0				1																		
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,0	0									1													
macrolides - azithromycin	1	0,0	0													1									
penicillins - ampicillin	1	0,0	0										1												
polymyxins - colistin	1	0,0	0											1											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	1	0,0	0													1									
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	1	0,0	0															1							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	1	0,0	0											1											
trimethoprim	1	0,0	0								1														

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 76 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Senftenberg derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Senftenberg
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 4 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested		micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
	N	%R		n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	4	75,0	3							1			2					1							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	4	0,0	0											4											
carbapenems - meropenem	4	0,0	0			4																			
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	4	0,0	0					4																	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	4	0,0	0						4																
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	4	25,0	1		1	2				1															
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	4	0,0	0						3	1															
macrolides - azithromycin	4	0,0	0										3	1											
penicillins - ampicillin	4	25,0	1								2	1								1					
polymyxins - colistin	4	0,0	0									4													
quinolones - nalidixic acid	4	25,0	1										2	1			1								
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	4	0,0	0													4									
tetracyclines - tetracycline	4	50,0	2									2						1	1						
trimethoprim	4	0,0	0					1	3																

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 77 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of S. Stanley derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	S. Stanley
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 5 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				N	%R																		
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	5	0,0	0							3		2											
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	5	0,0	0												5								
carbapenems - meropenem	5	0,0	0			5																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	5	0,0	0						5														
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	5	0,0	0							5													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	5	100,0	5					3	1		1												
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	5	0,0	0						4	1													
macrolides - azithromycin	5	0,0	0										5										
penicillins - ampicillin	5	40,0	2								3							2					
polymyxins - colistin	5	0,0	0									5											
quinolones - nalidixic acid	5	100,0	5																5				
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	5	0,0	0												2	3							
tetracyclines - tetracycline	5	20,0	1									4						1					
trimethoprim	5	0,0	0						4	1													

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 78 Quantitative tables: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of other serotypes than mentioned before derived from control program in turkeys (Dilution method), 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>Salmonella</i> other serotypes (than mentioned before)
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	salmonella control program

Panel 1

Number of isolates available in the laboratory 0 **Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:**

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																						
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048			
	N	%R	n																						
aminoglycosids - gentamicin																									
amphenicols - chloramphenicol																									
carbapenems - meropenem																									
cephalosporines - cefotaxime																									
cephalosporines - ceftazidime																									
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin																									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline																									
macrolides - azithromycin																									
penicillins - ampicillin																									
polymyxins - colistin																									
quinolones - nalidixic acid																									
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol																									
tetracyclines - tetracycline																									
trimethoprim																									

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

4.2. Campylobacteriosis

4.2.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases exceeded for the first time the number of notified salmonellosis cases in Austria. Since then, the gap between the number of cases of human campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis has been widening.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In recent years, the number of notified cases of campylobacteriosis steadily increased, reaching a new peak of 6,520 cases in 2014. The number of *Campylobacter* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to EMS.

The sources of infection are still unclear. The few published outbreaks in Austria were due to contaminated cow's raw milk or chicken meat. Pets may be considered another possible source.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Feedings stuff has no obvious relevance. Animals are diversly infected: broiler flocks around 50%, cattle approx. 25%. The actual source of infection in human cases is unknown, chicken meat may account for approx. 40% of human infections.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

On January 1st, 2006, the Federal Zoonoses Act (128. Bundesgesetz: Zoonosengesetz, published on 18th November 2005) was implemented. The subject of this Act is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation to enable the collection of the information necessary in the EU. According to this Zoonoses Act, to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria, a Federal Commission for Zoonoses (Zoonoses Commission) has been founded to advise the Federal Minister. The first meeting took place on May 3rd, 2006. The tasks of this Zoonoses Commission are

- Securing of effective and continuous teamwork of special fields concerned
- Cooperation based on free exchange of general information and where necessary, of specific data
- Determination of measures in case of Austrian-wide food borne outbreaks (concerning several provinces by one outbreak)
- Issues the annually report on trends and sources of zoonoses in Austria
- Preparation of risk based, integrated monitoring and surveillance programmes

The Austria-wide monitoring program on the trends of *Campylobacter*-prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* in broilers and turkey was performed according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU of the European Parliament and the Council and the Federal Zoonoses Act. The sampling was carried out from January to December 2014.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue to work for harmonization of monitoring programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference laboratory for typing and comparative analysis.

4.2.2. Campylobacteriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of *Campylobacter*-cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain
- Fever

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of *Campylobacter* spp. from stool or blood
- Differentiation of *Campylobacter* spp. should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Stool samples are plated on selective media and incubated in microaerobic atmosphere at 37–42 °C for a minimum of 36 hours (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123-126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 13). *Campylobacter* is confirmed by observing the typical colony morphology and characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope. For typing and differentiation of isolates to species level biochemical and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF) were applied. The differentiation to species level is not performed in each laboratory.

Notification system in place

Notification of campylobacteriosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2006, the number of notified human campylobacteriosis cases in Austria for the first time exceeded the number of notified salmonellosis cases. Since that year campylobacteriosis has remained the most frequently reported bacterial enteritis in humans in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, campylobacteriosis (n = 6,520) was the most frequently notified food borne enteric disease. It seems that the main sources of infection are chicken meat and raw milk (Feierl G. 2007. Jahresbericht 2006 der Nationalen Referenzzentrale für Campylobacter. Mitteilungen der Sanitätsverwaltung 4/2007).

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In 2014, campylobacteriosis remained the most frequently notified food borne disease in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via reports published by the Federal Ministry of Health (FMH) on a monthly and yearly basis and the annual report of the National Reference Centre. The yearly report is published on the Website of the FMH.

Table 79 Campylobacteriosis in humans - species distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

Campylobacteriosis	N	Cases			
		Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
Cases	6,520	76,64	5607	596	317
<i>C. jejuni</i>	5,368	63,10	4631	474	263
<i>C. coli</i>	626	7,36	526	69	31
<i>C. fetus</i>	1	0,01	1	0	0
<i>C. lari</i>	2	0,02	2	0	0
<i>C. upsaliensis</i>	3	0,04	3	0	0
<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified	520	6,11	444	53	23

Data source: EMS/NRL as of February 17, 2015

Table 80 Campylobacteriosis in humans - age and gender distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

age groups	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp.			<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>			<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified			other species		
	All *	M	F	All **	M	F	All	M	F	All **	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	98	69	29	75	52	23	7	4	3	16	13	3	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	410	231	179	375	212	163	9	4	5	26	15	11	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	593	362	231	505	311	194	45	26	19	43	25	18	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	1,189	648	540	985	534	451	120	66	54	82	47	34	2	1	1
25 to 44 years	2,044	1080	964	1,678	891	787	212	104	108	151	84	67	3	1	2
45 to 64 years	1,269	677	591	1,034	547	486	131	69	62	104	61	43	0	0	0
65 years and older	917	443	474	716	354	362	102	45	57	98	44	54	1	0	1
All age groups	6,520	3510	3008	5,368	2,901	2,466	626	318	308	520	289	230	6	2	4

* in 2 cases sex unknown

** in 1 case sex unknown

Table 81 Campylobacteriosis in humans - seasonal distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

Month	<i>Campylobacter</i>				
	<i>Campylobacter</i> spp. cases	<i>C. jejuni</i> cases	<i>C. coli</i> cases	<i>Campylobacter</i> not specified cases	other species cases
January	463	394	43	26	0
February	374	316	28	29	1
March	430	370	32	28	0
April	322	271	30	21	0
May	586	486	66	34	0
June	639	538	57	44	0
July	793	661	78	54	0
August	718	577	69	70	2
September	692	570	74	45	3
October	562	459	65	38	0
November	522	414	53	55	0
December	419	312	31	76	0
Total	6,520	5,368	626	520	6

4.2.3. *Campylobacter* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat and meat preparations from poultry and other foodstuffs.

Definition of positive finding

Isolation of thermotolerant *Campylobacter* from the sample independent of the microbiological method (quantitative or qualitative) used.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: ISO 10272-1:2006 and 10272-2:2006. Isolates were sent to the National Reference Centre. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were differentiated into *Campylobacter jejuni* or

Campylobacter coli with matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All other species were identified by additional biochemical and molecular methods including 16S rDNA sequencing. Pulsed field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) is available for outbreak detection and all isolates are stored for epidemiological investigations.

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter* – a concern to everyone” was closed in June 2013. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. were assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria. The result of this platform has been published in: “Konsensuspapier der bundesweiten Plattform *Campylobacter*, 17.1.2014” (German only).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Campylobacter should be added to microbiological criteria.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Fresh meat from broilers have been tested at different sampling stages. At processing plants and slaughterhouses 18 samples have been tested for *Campylobacter*, with 10 positive results (5 *C. jejuni*, 4 *C. coli*, 1 thermotolerant *Campylobacter*). This is a prevalence of 55.6% (CI: 33-76%). Due to the different amount of samples in the years 2012 to 2014 at processing plants and slaughterhouses a comparison between the years is not applicable.

At the sampling stage retail 62 (42 *C. jejuni*, 18 *C. coli*, 2 thermotolerant *Campylobacter*) out of 90 samples have been positive for *Campylobacter* (68.9%, CI: 59-78%) in fresh broiler meat. In 2013, at retail the *Campylobacter* prevalence in fresh broiler meat was 61% (61 positive in 100 samples) compared to 68.9% (62 positive in 90 samples) in 2014.

Fresh meat from turkey (at retail and wholesale) had a positivity rate of 18% (CI: 8-36%; 5 positive samples out of 28). In total, 45 meat preparations from unspecified poultry meat have been tested at retail, with a prevalence of 44.6% (CI:32-58%).

In total, 23 samples were tested for *Campylobacter* in non-poultry meat, meat preparations and meat products. In fresh pig meat one thermotolerant *Campylobacter* was detected, the other samples where negative.

One *Campylobacter jejuni* was detected in raw milk from cows, and one *Campylobacter coli* was detected in raw milk from sheep, whereas in cheeses and dairy products as well as in 50 other food samples of divers food categories (processed food, salad, sauce, ...) no *Campylobacter* was found.

In total, 97 fresh broiler meat samples from retail and wholesale have been tested quantitatively. Only in 1 sample > 1,000 CFU/g *Campylobacter* could be detected, which is 3.3% of the tested samples (CI: 1-6%), and 5 samples where between 500 CFU/g and 1,000 CFU/g (5.2%, CI: 2-12%).

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the respective chapter for foodborne outbreaks.

In 2014, in total 6,520 cases were reported in Austria. The species *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* account for 99.5% of human cases. In general the source of infection is mostly unknown. In a project whole genome sequencing of 85 foodstuff *Campylobacter* isolates from 2014 is performed to get more information on these isolates.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 82 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in poultry meat, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - fresh	Catering		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	1	0	0
	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	5	2	3	1
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	71	50	12	38	2
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	16	8	5	3	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	1	1	0
	Slaughterhouse		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	4	2	2	0
	Wholesale		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	2	1	1	0
EU			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	4	3	1	0	
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	5	3	0	3	0
Meat from broilers (<i>Gallus gallus</i>) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	2	0	2	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	84	9	2	3	4
Meat from duck - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail		XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - fresh	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	0	1	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	8	1	0	1	0
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	3	1	2	1
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	44	22	5	17	1
	Retail		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	7	1	0	1	0
XX			single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	1	0	1	0	
Meat from turkey - fresh	Catering		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	11	3	0	2	1
			XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	15	1	0	0	1
	Wholesale		EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
Meat from turkey - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	1	0
Meat from turkey - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Retail		AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
			EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0

Table 83 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* spp. in food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. coli</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>C. jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter</i> - <i>Campylobacter</i> spp., unspecified
Bakery products - pastry		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cereals and meals		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Retail	XE	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - raw		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals and pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	12	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products		Catering	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	1	0	0	1
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	17	1	0	1	0
Milk, cows - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	6	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	1	1	0	0
Nuts and nut products		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	13	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	3	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	4	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	10	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	1	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - pre-cut		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	2	0	0	0	0

4.2.4. *Campylobacter* spp. in animals

A. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – broiler - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, the monitoring for *Campylobacter* spp. was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. This program focused on antimicrobial resistance and not on prevalence. A sampling plan was calculated to obtain a representative sample of 170 *C. jejuni* isolates from broiler flocks all over Austria during the whole year. Based on the prevalence of *C. jejuni* in previous years, 542 flocks had to be sampled. Sampling was performed in the 4 broiler slaughter facilities, where >80% of all Austrian broilers are saughtered.

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: randomized sampling plan according to the number of slaughtered broiler flocks in the 4 slaughter facilities in 2013.

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program

At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified Charcoal Cefoperazone Deoxycholate agar plates (mCCDA) being incubated in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were subcultured on blood agar plates and incubated for another 48 hours in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 37 ± 1 °C. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining. Species identification was done using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were stored at -80 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *Campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter*—a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected in 306 out of 530 (57.7 %) tested slaughter batches. *C. jejuni* was found in 46.4 % of samples, *C. coli* in 11.3 %. Poultry meat combined with mistakes in kitchen hygiene seems to be the most risky food for humans acquiring an infection with *C. jejuni/coli*.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Campylobacter* spp. in animal – turkey - at slaughterhouse –official sampling – objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, the monitoring for *Campylobacter* spp. was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. That program focused on antimicrobial resistance and not on prevalence. Per year, about 270 nationally produced flocks were slaughtered in Austria. The program in turkeys was done for the first time and no data about the prevalence of *C. jejuni* was available therefore it was foreseen to sample all fattening flocks at the two national premises where turkey are slaughtered.

Due to too high costs of the sample transports from the slaughter houses to the laboratory on Thursdays and Fridays, and to ensure sample processing within that same week, not all of the slaughtered fattening flocks could be sampled. In order to obtain as many as possible *C. jejuni*-isolates it was decided to sample additional subsequent slaughter batches of flocks, if *C. jejuni* was not isolated after the first sampling. Veterinarians were assigned to take the samples; per flock the veterinarians chose 10 animals whose caeca were collected. All available flocks following economical considerations were sampled (objective sampling).

Frequency of the sampling

Rearing period: no program

Before slaughter at farm: no program
At slaughter: each turkey flock after slaughtering

Type of specimen taken

Caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Rearing period: no program
Before slaughter at farm: no program
At slaughter: The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Case definition

At slaughter: A slaughter batch is considered to be infected with thermotolerant *Campylobacter* following isolation of *Campylobacter jejuni* or *C. coli* from the pooled caecal content.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

At slaughter: The pooled samples were examined by direct inoculation on modified Charcoal Cefoperazone Deoxycholate agar plates (mCCDA) being incubated in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 42 ± 1 °C for 48 hours. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were subcultured on blood agar plates and incubated for another 48 hours in a micro-aerobic atmosphere at 37 ± 1 °C. *Campylobacter*-like colonies were identified by observing their characteristic motility and morphology under the microscope and the production of catalase and oxidase and gram staining.. Species identification was done using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). All *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates were stored at -80 °C. For quality control *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 and internal control isolates *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* were used. Data analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not performed in Austria.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Different strategies are in discussion, e.g. a quick test for identification of *Campylobacter* infected flocks at farm.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

None

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A *Campylobacter* platform called “*Campylobacter*—a concern to everyone” was launched in June 2012. Experts in the fields of human and veterinary medicine, food as well as representatives from industry, several authorities, poultry health service, trade organizations, etc. are assembled to ventilate on possible and plausible strategies against *Campylobacter* in the Austrian broiler production chain, including the impact of *Campylobacter* on human health in Austria.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Emphasis should be placed on education of the people for a better care in kitchen hygiene.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

Findings of *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* in animals do not need to be reported to authorities in Austria.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The epidemiological unit is the turkey flock. Due to the fact that several flocks were sampled 2–3 times, the microbiological result of the first sample from one flock was used to calculate the prevalence of *Campylobacter*. In the course of this monitoring thermotolerant *Campylobacter* were detected in 104 out of 135 (77.0 %) tested slaughter batches. *C. jejuni* was found in 49.6 % of samples, *C. coli* in 27.4 %.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 84 Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in animals, 2014

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive	<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>	<i>Campylobacter coli</i>
Broiler flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	VEMI Graz	slaughter batch	530	306	246	60
Turkeys - fattening flocks	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - caecum - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	10 intestines per slaughter batch	VEMI Graz	slaughter batch	135	104	67	37

*VEMI Graz: AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz

4.2.5. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter* spp.

A. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in humans

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

A sentinel surveillance program for *Campylobacter* isolates from human infections was installed in October 2006. On a monthly basis, the first 10 isolates collected at each of four designated diagnostic laboratories serving different provinces in Austria are sent to the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter* for speciation analysis and antimicrobial susceptibility testing by broth microdilution method.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Stool specimens were plated on *Campylobacter* blood-free selective agar at 37°C or 42°C for 48 hours under microaerobic conditions, and organisms were identified as *Campylobacter* spp. by oxidase testing and cell morphology. Isolates were speciated by biochemical methods and/or molecular methods as well as matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility microtitre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex, UK).

Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin!

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, 462 isolates of *Campylobacter* (411 *C. jejuni*, 51 *C. coli*) were tested for their antimicrobial susceptibility using broth microdilution method. Compared to 2013, increases in resistance rates were observed for both, *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* to quinolones, ampicillin, and tetracycline; resistance to erythromycin was low.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

The quinolone and ampicillin resistance rates of *C. jejuni* isolates from humans correspond with the resistance rates found in isolates from broiler meat and from broiler flocks, whereas the tetracycline resistance rate corresponds with the rates found in isolates from turkey meat and from turkey flocks.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The sentinel surveillance system will be continued. Results are published annually in the Report of the National Reference Centre for *Campylobacter* and in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *coli* in poultry meat

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

Frequency of the sampling

Isolates from poultry meat (broiler and turkey) isolated in the course of the national food surveillance programs that were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter* were tested for antimicrobial susceptibility using broth micro-dilution method.

Type of specimen taken

Food surveillance programs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Described in chapter: Thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in food

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed at the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz. *Campylobacter* isolates from broiler and turkey meat were tested.

Methods used for collecting data

All informations concerning the tested food and results of the antimicrobial testing were analysed using Microsoft® Excel2010.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

Described in chapter thermotolerant *Campylobacter* in broilers.

Broth microdilution susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter* spp. isolates was done using customised Sensititre® susceptibility micro titre plates (TREK Diagnostic Systems Ltd., East Grinstead, West Sussex UK). Briefly, *Campylobacter* spp. strains were subcultivated on Columbia blood agar and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. Inocula from fresh cultures were prepared by suspension in physiological saline to obtain a turbidity equivalent to that of a McFarland standard 0.5. The suspension was added to Mueller Hinton bouillon for a final concentration of approximately 500,000 cfu/ml and incubated for 48 hours at 37 °C in a microaerobic atmosphere. *Campylobacter jejuni* ATCC 33560 was used as control.

The number of isolates that are fully sensitive and the number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 and > 4 antimicrobials for *Campylobacter* includes only resistance to tetracycline, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, gentamicin, and streptomycin.

Preventive measures in place

None

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Samples from food animals were monitored for antimicrobial residues according to a randomized sampling scheme (BMGF-74320/0003-IV/B/7/2010, Rückstandsuntersuchung-Durchführungserlass 2007).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A project has been started to assess the appropriate method for collecting data on antimicrobial usage in animals. Results of this study are expected for 2015.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Nil

Notification system in place

No notification system for resistant isolates in place.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, *C. jejuni* isolated from broiler and turkey meat showed very high resistance rates to ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, and ampicillin (only from turkey meat), and high resistance rates to ampicillin (from broiler meat), and tetracycline. Resistance rates in *C. coli* from broiler and turkey meat

were very high for ciprofloxacin, nalidixic acid, ampicillin, and tetracycline though data from turkey meat have to be interpreted with caution due to the low number of samples analysed.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

See chapter AMR in humans

Additional information

Results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

C. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2014, the AMR-monitoring for *C. jejuni* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. The target was to obtain 170 isolates of *C. jejuni* from 170 broiler flocks (= epidemiological unit). The sampling plan was calculated by the department for Statistics of the AGES based on the prevalence of *C. jejuni* of the last years (33.9%), i.e. 542 flocks had to be tested. In Austria about 80% of all fattened broiler flocks are slaughtered in 4 slaughterhouses. Proportionally to the number of slaughtered flocks in each slaughter house the samples (140, 219, 164, and 19 flocks sampled) were distributed equally over the whole year. The sampling plan (objective sampling) specified the number of sampled flocks per week and slaughter house. Veterinarians were assigned to take the samples, arbitrarily choosing flocks, depending on the number of flocks to be sampled per week and on the number of slaughter days at the respective slaughter house; per flock (slaughter batch) the veterinarians chose 10 animals whose intestines were collected.

Stratification procedures per animal population

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Randomisation procedures per animal population

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Frequency of the sampling

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Out of 246 flocks *C. jejuni* were isolated. The testing for antimicrobial susceptibility was performed with each isolate after isolation. Because the number of *C. jejuni* was higher than expected the susceptibility testing was ceased during the year until the total number of isolates was available. Based on the already

tested isolates, the number of isolates per calendar quarter was calculated to ensure that the isolates of the last quarters were not significantly under-represented and that the number of tested isolates did not exceed too much the number of isolates required (n=170). In total, 193 isolates were susceptibility tested, 40, 62, 54, and 37 isolated per quarter.

According to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU all unique strains isolated in the course of the control program (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to broth micro-dilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter "*Campylobacter* spp. in animals"

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Laboratory for *Campylobacter*, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 2).

Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 2).

Control programs/strategies in place

The control program is a national program, based on the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and co-financed based on Commission Implementing Decision 2013/653/EU.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Result of the investigation

Wild type population of *C. jejuni* in broilers has decreased during the last 11 years of the national AMR-monitoring from 45% to 20%, although the proportion of multiresistant isolates remained very low. The highest resistance rates could be found to chinolones (very high), ampicillin, and tetracycline (high) with a tendency of increasing resistance rates to the first two substances mentioned.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See above (results)

Relevance of the findings in feedingstuffs/animals/foodstuffs to human cases

In *C. jejuni* from humans, similar high resistance rates as in broiler isolates can be found to chinolones, ampicillin and tetracycline, with increasing resistance rates in the last years.

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

D. Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2014, the AMR-monitoring for *C. jejuni* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. The target was to obtain 170 isolates of *C. jejuni* from 170 turkey flocks (= epidemiological unit). Per year, about 270 nationally produced flocks were slaughtered in Austria. The program in turkeys was done for the first time therefore no data about the prevalence of *C. jejuni* were available; it was foreseen to sample all fattening flocks at the two national premises where turkeys are slaughtered.

Due to too high costs of the sample transports on Thursdays and Fridays from the slaughter houses to the laboratory, and to ensure sample processing within that same week, not all of the slaughtered fattening flocks could be sampled. In order to obtain as many as possible *C. jejuni*-isolates it was decided to sample additional, subsequent slaughter batches of flocks, if *C. jejuni* was not isolated after the first sampling. Veterinarians were assigned to take the samples; per flock, the veterinarians chose 10 animals whose caeca were collected. All available flocks following economical considerations were sampled (objective sampling).

Stratification procedures per animal population

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Randomisation procedures per animal population

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Frequency of the sampling

See chapter "description of sampling design"

Type of specimen taken

Caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each caecum was pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

One *C. jejuni* isolated per turkey flock was used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU. In total, 73 isolates were available and all isolates were tested.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

See chapter "*Campylobacter* spp. in animals"

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National Reference Laboratory for Campylobacter, AGES Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 2).

Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Control programs/strategies in place

The control program is a national program, based on the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and co-financed based on Commission Implementing Decision 2013/653/EU.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health
(http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Result of the investigation

Twenty percent of tested isolates belonged to the wild type population (no antimicrobial resistance detected to any antimicrobial tested). The proportion of multiresistant isolates was low. The highest resistance rates could be found to chinolones (very high), to ampicillin and tetracycline (high).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See above (results)

Relevance of the findings in feedingstuffs/animals/foodstuffs to human cases

No information available

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 85 Breakpoints used for antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli*, 2014

antimicrobial	<i>C. jejuni</i>			<i>C. coli</i>		
	ECOFF	Range tested		ECOFF	Range tested	
	concentration (µg/ml)			concentration (µg/ml)		
	wild type ≤	lowest	highest	wild type ≤	lowest	highest
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	2	0,12	16	2	0,12	16
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	4	0,5	32	4	0,5	32
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	16	2	64	16	2	64
Carbapenems - Imipenem	8	0,06	16	8	0,06	16
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	0,5	0,06	32	0,5	0,06	32
Macrolides - Erythromycin	4	0,25	128	8	0,25	128
Penicillins - Ampicillin	8	1	64	8	1	64
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	16	2	256	16	2	256
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	1	0,12	64	2	0,12	64

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* this includes resistance to ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, streptomycin, erythromycin.

Table 86 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni*, qualitative data, 2014

<i>C. jejuni</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat			broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates	411			102			13			193			73		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	411	0,2	1	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	411	1,2	5	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	2,1	4	73	1,4	1
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	411	0,2	1	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	411	0,0	0	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	411	71,0	292	102	71,6	73	13	92,3	12	193	75,1	145	73	63,0	46
Macrolides - Erythromycin	411	0,2	1	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	411	35,0	144	102	39,2	40	13	53,8	7	193	35,8	69	73	49,3	36
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	411	69,8	287	102	67,6	69	13	84,6	11	193	67,9	131	73	60,3	44
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	411	35,0	144	102	26,5	27	13	38,5	5	193	23,8	46	73	35,6	26
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	411	24,6	101	102	18,6	19	13	0,0	0	193	19,7	38	73	32,9	24
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	411	44,8	184	102	51,0	52	13	69,2	9	193	61,7	119	73	35,6	26
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	411	29,0	119	102	26,5	27	13	30,8	4	193	16,6	32	73	30,1	22
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	411	1,7	7	102	2,9	3	13	0,0	0	193	2,1	4	73	1,4	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	411	0,0	0	102	1,0	1	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	411	0,0	0	102	0,0	0	13	0,0	0	193	0,0	0	73	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 87 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in humans, quantitative data, 2014

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>																				
		matrix	human																				
		sampling context	sentinel																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		411	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	411	0,2	1				210	173	25	2						1							
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	411	1,2	5						325	75	5	1			2	2	1						
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	411	0,2	1								248	118	38	6	1								
Carbapenems - Imipenem	411	0,0	0				341	68	2														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	411	71,0	292				50	60	8	1	1	3	14	178	67	23	6						
Macrolides - Erythromycin	411	0,2	1						22	153	172	60	3							1			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	411	35,0	144							13	43	120	91	34	23	41	46						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	411	69,8	287									38	67	17	2		4	44	232	7			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	411	35,0	144				56	147	34	30	3			1	1	9	26	104					

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 88 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler meat, quantitative data, 2014

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>																				
		matrix	broiler meat																				
		sampling context	monitoring																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		102	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=<0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	102	0,0	0				52	46	4														
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	102	0,0	0						84	18													
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	102	0,0	0								63	27	12										
Carbapenems - Imipenem	102	0,0	0			88	14																
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	102	71,6	73			15	10	4				7	46	17	3								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	102	0,0	0					3	47	43	7	2											
Penicillins - Ampicillin	102	39,2	40							8	12	21	21	7	10	12	11						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	102	67,6	69								9	20	2	2			10	58	1				
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	102	26,5	27					14	44	15	2	3			2		2		20				

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 89 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey meat, quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent		<i>C. jejuni</i>	
matrix		turkey meat	
sampling context		monitoring	
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		13	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	13	0,0	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	13	0,0	0
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	13	0,0	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	13	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	13	92,3	12
Macrolides - Erythromycin	13	0,0	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	13	53,8	7
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	13	84,6	11
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	13	38,5	5
			=< 0.008
			0,015
			0.03
			0.06
			0.12
			0.25
			0.5
			1
			2
			4
			8
			16
			32
			64
			128
			256
			512
			1024
			2048
			>2048
			n
			9 3 1
			12 1
			7 5 1
			8 4 1
			1 1 9 1 1
			2 7 3 1
			1 4 1 2 5
			2 1 10
			4 2 2 1 1 3

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 90 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>																							
matrix	broiler flock																							
sampling context	AMR-monitoring																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	193																							
	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																							
antimicrobial	total units tested N	micro-biological resistant %R	n	= < 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	193	0,0	0					91	82	18	2													
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	193	2,1	4							151	35	3		1	2		1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	193	0,0	0									105	73	13	2									
Carbapenems - Imipenem	193	0,0	0				167	26																
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	193	75,1	145				28	13	7		1		11	92	33	6	2							
Macrolides - Erythromycin	193	0,0	0						17	76	85	15												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	193	35,8	69								12	31	47	34	13	23	20	13						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	193	67,9	131									21	32	7	2		5	19	103	4				
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	193	23,8	46					38	68	31	10	4		2	1	5	5	29						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 91 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter jejuni* in turkey flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2014

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. jejuni</i>																			
		matrix	turkey flock																			
		sampling context	AMR-monitoring																			
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		73	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	73	0,0	0																			
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	73	1,4	1																			
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	73	0,0	0																			
Carbapenems - Imipenem	73	0,0	0																			
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	73	63,0	46																			
Macrolides - Erythromycin	73	0,0	0																			
Penicillins - Ampicillin	73	49,3	36																			
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	73	60,3	44																			
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	73	35,6	26																			

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 92 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli*, qualitative data, 2014

<i>C. coli</i>	humans			broiler meat			turkey meat		
	51			45			6		
antimicrobial	total units tested			total units tested			total units tested		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	51	0,0	0	45	0,0	0	6	0,0	0
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	51	19,6	10	45	11,1	5	6	16,7	1
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	51	2,0	1	45	0,0	0	6	0,0	0
Carbapenems - Imipenem	51	0,0	0	45	0,0	0	6	0,0	0
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	51	80,4	41	45	88,9	40	6	100,0	6
Macrolides - Erythromycin	51	5,9	3	45	11,1	5	6	0,0	0
Penicillins - Ampicillin	51	54,9	28	45	73,3	33	6	50,0	3
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	51	80,4	41	45	88,9	40	6	100,0	6
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	51	66,7	34	45	60,0	27	6	50,0	3
Number of multiresistant isolates	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	51	11,8	6	45	17,8	8	6	0,0	0
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	51	21,6	11	45	42,2	19	6	50,0	3
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	51	51,0	26	45	35,6	16	6	33,3	2
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	51	13,7	7	45	2,2	1	6	16,7	1
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	51	2,0	1	45	2,2	1	6	0,0	0
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	51	0,0	0	45	0,0	0	6	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 93 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in humans, quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent		<i>C. coli</i>																					
matrix		human																					
sampling context		sentinel																					
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	51	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																					
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	51	0,0	0				3	29	19														
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	51	19,6	10						8	30	3			2	5	3							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	51	2,0	1								10	30	9	1		1							
Carbapenems - Imipenem	51	0,0	0				15	35	1														
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	51	80,4	41			4	6				1	5	16	11	8								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	51	5,9	3					2	22	6	10	6	2									3	
Penicillins - Ampicillin	51	54,9	28									9	14	14	3	2	9						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	51	80,4	41									9	1				25	16					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	51	66,7	34				3	9	3	1	1						34						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 94 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in broiler meat - quantitative data, 2014

		zoonotic agent	<i>C. coli</i>																							
		matrix	broiler meat																							
		sampling context	monitoring																							
Number of isolates available in the laboratory		45	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																							
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	N	%R	n	=<0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
						n																				
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	45	0,0	0						3	24	18															
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	45	11,1	5								8	29	3			1	1	2	1							
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	45	0,0	0											6	30	8	1									
Carbapenems - Imipenem	45	0,0	0						15	26	4															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	45	88,9	40						4	1					8	19	12		1							
Macrolides - Erythromycin	45	11,1	5							6	13	6	14	1					1	1	3					
Penicillins - Ampicillin	45	73,3	33											2	5	5	19	4		10						
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	45	88,9	40												2	3			3	26	11					
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	45	60,0	27							9	6	3							3	24						

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

Table 95 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *Campylobacter coli* in turkey meat - quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent		<i>C. coli</i>																				
matrix		turkey meat																				
sampling context		monitoring																				
Number of isolates available in the laboratory	6	Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																				
			=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
	N	%R	n																			
Aminoglycosides - Gentamicin	6	0,0	0				4	2														
Aminoglycosides - Streptomycin	6	16,7	1					1	3	1			1									
Amphenicols - Chloramphenicol	6	0,0	0							1	4	1										
Carbapenems - Imipenem	6	0,0	0			2	4															
Fluoroquinolones - Ciprofloxacin	6	100,0	6								1	2	2	1								
Macrolides - Erythromycin	6	0,0	0					3	2	1												
Penicillins - Ampicillin	6	50,0	3									3	2				1					
Quinolones - Nalidixic acid	6	100,0	6														3	3				
Tetracyclines - Tetracycline	6	50,0	3				1	1	1								3					

N = number of isolates tested, %R = percentage resistant isolates, n = number of resistant isolates

4.3. Listeriosis

4.3.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Listeriosis can be regarded as a relatively rare infectious disease in Austria with an annual incidence between 0.1 and 0.25 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in the years 1996 to 2007. In 2008 a total of 31 culturally verified human cases of listeriosis were recorded for Austria (incidence 0.38 per 100,000 inhabitants), four of them were associated with pregnancy. In 2009 a further increase had to be assessed, 46 cases what corresponds to an incidence of 0.6. Two cases were associated with pregnancy. In 2010, a reduction to 34 cases could be observed and also in 2011, n = 24 (incidence of 0.29). In 2013, 36 cases were notified (EMS). In 2014, 49 cases were notified in the EMS, 47 in the NRC-L. The incidences are similar to those of most other western European countries (0.2–0.9). In 2014, lethality was reported in 12 cases (24.5 % of cases). Due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. According to the NRC-L, isolates from 47 cases were typed, the 30-day lethality was 24 % (12 cases). This high fatality rate and the sometimes severe permanent disabilities demand every effort to ascertain potential food-associated outbreaks as early as possible.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although raw milk soft and semi-soft cheeses, ready-to-eat meat products, and smoked salmons are likely candidates as vehicles for infections. The source of an infection often remains unclear.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A monthly report is sent to the Ministry of Health by the National Reference Center, whereas outbreaks are reported immediately. Restrictions tightened to sell unpasteurised milk in remote areas (Alps).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

More widespread information for pregnant and immunocompromised persons should be provided.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send those strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.3.2. Listeriosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Listeriosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases as well notified to the EMS as typed in the NRC-L.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following three symptoms:

- Listeriosis of newborns defined as Stillbirth or at least one of the following five in the first month of life:
 - Granulomatosis infantiseptica
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Dyspnoea
 - Lesions on skin, mucosal membranes or conjunctivae
- Listeriosis in pregnancy defined as at least one of the following three:
 - Abortion, miscarriage, stillbirth or premature birth
 - Fever
 - Influenza-like symptoms
- Other form of listeriosis defined as at least one of the following four:
 - Fever
 - Meningitis or meningoencephalitis
 - Septicaemia
 - Localised infections such as arthritis, endocarditis, and abscesses

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally sterile site
- Isolation of *Listeria monocytogenes* from a normally non-sterile site in a foetus, stillborn, newborn or the mother at or within 24 hours of birth

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the laboratory criteria
- or
- Any mother with a laboratory confirmed listeriosis infection in her foetus, stillborn or newborn

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are Gram stained. Specimen from normally sterile sites are inoculated in blood culture broth or thioglycollate broth and Columbia blood agar plates, vaginal swabs are plated only directly on Columbia blood and colistin-nalidixic acid (CNA) agar. *L. monocytogenes* is identified by catalase and Api Listeria test.

Stool samples were examined after cold enrichment in Fraser enrichment broth and streaked onto selective chromogenic agar plate and Columbia blood-agar. All isolates obtained in Austria are sent to the National Reference Center for confirmation, subtyping by PCR and PFGE and comparison.

Notification system in place

Notification of listeriosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

History of the disease in chapter general evaluation.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In the EMS, 49 cases of listeriosis were notified (as of March 2, 2015); due to the fact that an isolate is not sent to the NRC-L for each notified case, the case numbers reported from the NRC-L may differ. EMS data correlate with the notification data of the medicating physician and the diagnosing laboratory. In the NRC-L, isolates from 47 cases were typed.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Listeriosis is a rare disease, but not a rare bacterium, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, including pregnancy and immunosuppression. Although dairy products and salmon are likely candidates as vehicles for the bacterium, the source of an infection often remains unclear.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health (MOH). The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 96 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2014

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	49	0,58
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	19	0,22
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	7	0,08
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	17	0,20
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (PCR)	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> unknow SG	2	0,02
Deaths	9	0,11
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	4	0,05
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	2	0,02
Congenital cases	5	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	2	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	1	

Data source: EMS as of March 2, 2015

Table 97 Listeriosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC-L), 2014

Listeriosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
Cases	47	0,55
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	19	0,22
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	7	0,08
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	17	0,20
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> (PCR)	2	0,02
Deaths	12	0,14
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	5	0,06
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	0,02
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c	1	0,01
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	4	0,05
Congenital cases	5	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2a	2	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2b	2	
<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b	1	

Data source: National Reference Centre for Listeria as of February 24, 2015

Table 98 Listeriosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2014

	<i>Listeriosis</i>			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2a			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1,2b			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 1/2c			<i>L. monocytogenes</i> 4b		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	5	1	4	2	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	1
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25 to 44 years *	4	2	2	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
45 to 64 years	11	8	3	3	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	3	1
65 years and older	29	18	11	12	7	5	3	2	1	1	1	0	11	8	3
	49	29	20	19	10	9	7	3	4	2	2	0	17	12	5

Data source: EMS as of March 2, 2015

4.3.3. *Listeria* spp. in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e.g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological

criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

At the production plant

The producer is responsible for the process hygiene. The frequency of sampling therefore depends on the critical control points of the specific product.

At retail

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

pasteurized and raw cows' milk, pig meat products, bovine meat products, fishery products, smoked fish, fruits and vegetables, etc.

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25g

Diagnostic/analytical methods used at the production plant or at retail

Bacteriological method ISO 11290-1:2004 and ISO 11290-2:2005

For further investigations all isolates from foodstuffs are sent to the National Reference Laboratory for Listeria in Graz. This includes the isolates from process hygiene controls at the production plant, self monitoring as well as all isolates from regularly testing at retail.

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

All isolates from foodstuffs and process hygiene controls from any laboratories within Austria are gathered and typed at the National Reference Laboratory for Listeria. In a first step the species *Listeria monocytogenes* is confirmed by different selective media (e. g. Palcam agar, Ottoviani Agosti agar, Rapid L.mono agar) and/or API, matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time of flight (MALDI TOF) is available.

A serogroup-specific PCR according to Doumith et al. is performed routinely (Doumith et al.

Differentiation of the major *Listeria monocytogenes* serovars by multiplex PCR. *J Clin Microbiol* (2004); 51, 3819-22). Finally, typing is realized with PFGE to answer type specific questions.

In the case of an outbreak the data of the outbreak strain are compared with the existing data base.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Follow-up surveillance programs; a folder was created by the AGES in cooperation with the Austrian Medical Chamber: Pregnancy – infections transmitted via food. This folder is available in German, Turkish and Serbo-Croatian (<http://www.ages.at/themen/krankheitsreger/listerien/>) and was distributed to all gynaecologists. The folder contains advices to prevent food-borne infections during pregnancy, including listeriosis, toxoplasmosis, campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis as well as mycotoxicosis. The Federal Ministry of Health published folders on their webpage (<https://www.verbrauchergesundheit.gv.at/lebensmittel/buch/hygieneleitlinien/hygieneleitlinien.html>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, gynaecologists and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Listeria monocytogenes was not detected in samples of pasteurised cows' milk (0/3), in raw cows' milk (0/30). Concerning pasteurised cows' milk no *Listeria* has been detected for five years (2010-2014). In total 595 cheeses were tested and *L. monocytogenes* could be detected in 6 samples. In 3 of 23 (13.0 %) pig meat products samples and in 2 out of 96 samples (2.1 %) from bovine meat products cooked, ready to eat and paté (campaign A-016-14) *L. monocytogenes* was qualitatively found (quantitatively: 1-time <100 cfu/g). 8 out of 252 samples (3.2 %) of red meat products were found positive in 25g and 1-time <100 cfu/g, and of red meat products, fermented sausages 12 out of 189 (6.3 %), both categories included samples from campaign A-801-14. 5.9 % of all samples from fishery products (8/135) revealed a contamination with *L. monocytogenes* (1-time <100 cfu/g, the others below detection limit). 1 out of 23 smoked fish samples (4.3 %) were found positive for *L. monocytogenes* below detection limit. Other processed food products, including the samples from campaign A-802-14, added up to 279 samples of which 12 samples were found positive (4.3 %), 5-times <100 cfu/g, the others below detection limit.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in the chapter foodborne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-020-14: *Listeria* spp. in food – bakery products - pastry or cakes (containing raw cream) - at catering - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at restaurants, cafes etc., preferably from buffets or from glass cabinets.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - June

Type of specimen taken

Cakes or pastry, with special focus on products with "raw" fillings (not baked).

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: at least 200g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

58 samples tested: *Listeria* was not detected in any sample

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*.

Austrian food experts do not recommend further specific campaigns on cakes and pastry containing raw cream, due to the low rate of positive results.

Campaign A-023-14: *Listeria* spp. in food – vegetables - leaves & vegetables - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

Vegetables, especially salad (pre-cut, ready to eat), pre-cut vegetables and sprouted seeds (6 samples)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: at least 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria* spp. in 25g

Results of the investigation

55 samples tested: *Listeria* was not detected in any sample.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*, VTEC, Hepatitis A Virus.

Austrian food experts do recommend further specific campaigns, focussing on microbiological hazards in food of non-animal origin.

Campaign A-036-14: *Listeria* spp. in food – fruits - frozen or ready-to-eat - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - September

Type of specimen taken

Berries (frozen and ready-to-eat) and pre-cut melons (ready-to-eat only) have been sampled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

60 samples tested: *Listeria* was not detected in any sample

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*, pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (VTEC), Norovirus and Hepatitis A Virus.

Austrian food experts suggest further campaigns concerning food of non animal origin and microbiological hazards. Therefore in 2015 another campaign in fruits and vegetables is planned.

Campaign A-016-14: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) – meat products cooked, ready-to-eat and pâté - at retail and at processing plant - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets and at processing plants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: March to June

Type of specimen taken

Red meat products cooked, ready-to-eat and pâté

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

96 samples tested: qualitative method: 2-times positive, quantitative method: 2-times <10 CFU/g

Additional information

None

Campaign A-021-14: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Dairy products (excluding cheeses), not specified - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk - at processing plant - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at processing plants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May to June

Type of specimen taken

Pasteurized milk and dairy products (fermented and non-fermented) for consumption in schools and kindergartens

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

41 samples tested: qualitative method: 1-time positive, quantitative method: <10 CFU/g

Additional information

Similar results to the campaign A-017-13 from last year were 42 samples were tested, none positive (qualitative and quantitative). As these products are produced in very small milk processing plants and are consumed by children a follow-up of this campaign is recommended in 2016.

Campaign A-801-14: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) – meat products and fermented sausages – at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February to March

Type of specimen taken

Red meat - meat products and fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

95 samples tested: qualitative method: 2-times positive, quantitative method: 2-times <10 CFU/g

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and VTEC.

Campaign A-802-14: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods – chilled - at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: April to June

Type of specimen taken

Ready-to-eat salads with or without mayonnaise, sprouts

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

52 samples tested: qualitative method: 2-times positive, quantitative method: 2-times <10 CFU/g

Additional information

39 samples (containing eggs) were also tested for Salmonella spp.

Campaign A-803-14: *Listeria monocytogenes* in food – Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk - at retail and wholesale - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail and wholesale outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: September to November

Type of specimen taken

Soft and semi-soft cheeses made from pasteurised cow's milk

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *L. monocytogenes* in 25g

Results of the investigation

52 samples tested: none positive

Additional information

None

Table 99 *Listeria monocytogenes* in milk and milky products, 2014

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g	
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0	
		EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		15	0	15	0	15	0	0	
	Retail	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0	
		EU		7	0	7	0	7	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0	
	Retail	AT		17	0	17	0	14	0	0	
		EU		8	0	8	0	8	0	0	
		XE		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
		XX		45	1	45	1	45	0	0	
Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0		
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		36	0	36	0	36	0	0	
		AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0	
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0	
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0	
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	3	0	0	
		EU		5	0	5	0	4	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		41	0	41	0	41	0	0	
	Retail	AT		18	0	18	0	18	0	0	
			campaign A-803-14	31	0	31	0	31	0	0	
		EU	campaign A-803-14	47	1	47	1	47	0	1	
	Wholesale	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0	
			campaign A-803-14	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	
		EU		11	0	11	0	11	0	0	
			campaign A-803-14	9	0	9	0	9	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		76	1	76	1	76	0	0	
		Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
			EU		3	1	3	1	3	0	1
			XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 94 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		14	0	14	0	14	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
EU			3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		16	0	16	0	16	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	10	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		12	1	12	1	12	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - hard - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk	Processing plant	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses)	Processing plant	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
		EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 94 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - butter	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		43	1	43	1	43	1	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - buttermilk	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - chocolate milk	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - cream	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy desserts - chilled	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	EU		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		76	0	76	0	75	0	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	13	0	0
		EU		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - dairy products, not specified - ready-to-eat - made from pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT	campaign A-021-14	41	1	41	1	41	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - fermented dairy products	Processing plant	AT		58	0	58	0	57	0	0
	Retail	AT		14	0	14	0	14	0	0
		EU		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
EU			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - ice-cream	Catering	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		21	1	21	1	10	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	4	0	3	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
Wholesale	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - probiotic drinks	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dairy products (excluding cheeses) - yoghurt	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, cows - pasteurised milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		10	0	10	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		17	0	17	0	15	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk - intended for direct human consumption	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, goats - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Milk, sheeps - raw milk	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

Table 100 *Listeria monocytogenes* in other foods, 2014

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for <i>L. monocytogenes</i>	Units tested with detection method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	<i>L. monocytogenes</i> >100 cfu/g
Bakery products	Catering	AT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		14	0	14	0	14	0	0
	Retail	AT		13	0	13	0	10	0	0
		EU		8	0	8	0	7	0	0
	XX		3	0	3	0	3	0	0	
Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Bakery products - cakes	Catering	AT		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		5	0	5	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		43	4	43	4	40	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - cakes - containing raw cream	Catering	AT	campaign A-020-14	22	0	22	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-020-14	3	0	3	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-020-14	3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Bakery products - pastry	Catering	AT		11	0	11	0	11	0	0
		AT	campaign A-020-14	27	0	27	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-020-14	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-020-14	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		11	0	11	0	9	0	0
	Retail	AT		86	1	86	1	84	0	0
EU			4	0	4	0	4	0	0	
Beverages, non-alcoholic	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Cereals and meals	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans	Catering	XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Crustaceans - unspecified - cooked	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Egg products	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Egg products - dried	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Egg products - liquid	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured	Border inspection activities	XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Fish - raw	Catering	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		12	0	12	0	10	0	0
		EU		11	1	11	1	6	0	0
		XE		1	1	1	1	1	0	0
XX			46	3	46	3	46	3	0	

Table 95 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fish - raw - frozen	Retail	XX		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fish - smoked	Retail	AT		13	1	13	1	8	0	0
		EU		8	0	8	0	2	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified	Catering	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		10	2	10	2	10	1	0
	Wholesale	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - ready-to-eat	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fishery products, unspecified - smoked	Catering	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
		EU		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
	Retail	AT		28	0	28	0	28	0	0
		EU		39	3	39	3	39	0	0
		XE		7	2	7	2	7	0	0
		XX		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XE		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Fruits	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
		EU		9	0	9	0	9	0	0
		XE		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Fruits - non-pre-cut	Retail	AT	campaign A-036-14	11	0	11	0	0	0	0
				1	0	1	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-036-14	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
		XE	campaign A-036-14	1	0	1	0	0	0	0

Table 95 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Fruits - non-pre-cut - frozen	Retail	AT	campaign A-036-14	7	0	7	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-036-14	7	0	7	0	0	0	0
		XE	campaign A-036-14	4	0	4	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-036-14	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits - pre-cut - ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	campaign A-036-14	12	0	12	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-036-14	11	0	11	0	0	0	0
		XE	campaign A-036-14	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fruits - products	Processing plant	AT		7	0	7	0	5	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	campaign A-016-14	34	1	34	1	34	0	0
	Retail	AT	campaign A-016-14	55	1	55	1	55	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat products - pâté	Processing plant	AT	campaign A-016-14	3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT	campaign A-016-14	4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	Catering	XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - fresh	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products	Processing plant	AT		12	1	12	1	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	1	2	1	1	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		7	1	7	1	7	1	0
Meat from pig - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		5	0	5	0	4	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	EU		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat preparation	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Meat from turkey - meat products	Processing plant	AT		9	0	9	0	0	0	0

Table 95 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but <= 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Meat from wild boar - meat products	Game handling establishment	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Game handling establishment	AT		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Retail	AT		6	1	6	1	6	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Wholesale	EU		2	0	2	0	2	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products	Catering	AT		7	0	7	0	7	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		45	1	45	1	43	0	0
	Retail	AT		19	0	19	0	19	0	0
			campaign A-801-14	24	1	24	1	24	0	0
		EU	campaign A-801-14	10	2	10	2	10	0	0
			XX		6	0	6	0	6	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Catering	AT		17	0	17	0	17	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		60	3	60	3	59	0	0
	Retail	AT		54	1	52	1	53	1	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
		XX		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Farm	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		25	4	25	4	25	0	0
	Retail	AT		71	6	71	6	71	0	0
			campaign A-801-14	50	1	50	1	50	0	0
		EU	campaign A-801-14	17	0	17	0	17	0	0
			XX		15	0	15	0	15	0
Wholesale	EU		4	1	4	1	4	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - pâté	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		EU		4	0	4	0	4	0	0
Other food	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		21	0	21	0	18	0	0
	Retail	AT		9	0	9	0	4	0	0
EU			1	0	1	0	1	0	0	
Other food of non-animal origin	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT		13	1	10	1	9	0	0
		XX		3	1	3	1	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		10	1	10	1	7	0	0
	Retail	AT		52	0	46	0	30	0	0
		EU		8	0	8	0	2	0	0
		XX		96	5	96	5	96	5	0

Table 95 cont.

Food	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Details	Total units tested	Total units positive for L.monocytogenes	Units tested with detection method	L. monocytogenes presence in x g	Units tested with enumeration method	L. monocytogenes > detection limit but ≤ 100 cfu/g	L. monocytogenes >100 cfu/g
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - ices and similar frozen desserts	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - noodles	Retail	AT		2	1	2	1	2	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - pasta	Processing plant	AT		18	0	18	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		4	0	4	0	0	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sandwiches	Retail	AT		8	1	8	1	8	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - sushi	Retail	AT		10	0	10	0	6	0	0
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified - ready-to-eat foods - chilled	Retail	AT	campaign A-802-14	44	2	44	2	44	0	0
		EU	campaign A-802-14	5	0	5	0	5	0	0
		XX	campaign A-802-14	3	0	3	0	3	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads	Catering	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		12	0	12	0	8	0	0
	Retail	AT		14	1	14	1	8	0	0
Ready-to-eat salads - containing mayonnaise	Processing plant	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings	Processing plant	AT		1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
Sauce and dressings - mayonnaise	Processing plant	AT		6	0	6	0	6	0	0
	Retail	AT		3	0	3	0	0	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables	Catering	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	Retail	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
			campaign A-023-14	19	0	19	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-023-14	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
		XX		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	AT		2	0	2	0	2	0	0
		EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
Vegetables - non-pre-cut	Retail	AT	campaign A-023-14	17	0	17	0	0	0	0
		EU	campaign A-023-14	13	0	13	0	0	0	0
		XX	campaign A-023-14	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Vegetables - products	Catering	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Processing plant	AT		8	0	8	0	8	0	0
	Retail	AT		1	0	1	0	1	0	0
	Wholesale	EU		1	0	1	0	1	0	0

4.4. Verotoxic *Escherichia coli*

4.4.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In 2014, 130 laboratory confirmed cases were notified to the EMS; this number was similar as in 2013 (130 cases), 2012 (127 cases), and 2011 (129 cases). In the years 2007 to 2010 less cases were reported annually, between 88 to 103 cases. Out of the 130 cases, 14 cases of HUS were notified to the EMS.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2014, the prevalence of verocytotoxic *E. coli* isolated from animals remained similar compared to last years. Out of 32% of samples from cattle (2013: 33%, 2012: 35%, 2011: 39%) and out of 60% of samples from sheep (2013: 72%, 2012: 65%; 2011: 68%) VTEC could be isolated. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), in cattle O157 (2 x) and O26 (2 x), and O26 (1 x) from sheep, respectively were isolated.

The relevance of findings of VTEC in faeces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines and sheep. Meat samples of game show a higher prevalence of VTEC.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

An Austrian wide monitoring program on the trends of VTEC prevalence in bovine animals and sheep was implemented according to the directive 2003/99/EC of the European Parliament and the Council of 17 November 2003 in the National Orders. The sampling was carried out throughout 2014.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Increased awareness and information should be made available for parents, paediatricians and general practitioners in regard to food safety and the prevention of infection.

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.4.2. Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of VTEC cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS and typed in the NRL-VTEC.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

STEC/VTEC diarrhoea

Any person with at least one of the following two symptoms:

- Diarrhoea
- Abdominal pain

HUS

Any person with acute renal failure and at least one of the following two:

- Microangiopathic haemolytic anaemia
- Thrombocytopenia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following three:

- Isolation of Shigatoxin/Verotoxin (STEC/VTEC) producing *E. coli*
- Detection of *vtx1* or *vtx2* gene(s) nucleic acid
- Detection of free shigatoxins.

Only for HUS the following can be used as laboratory criterion to confirm STEC/VTEC:

- *E. coli* serogroups specific antibody response

Isolation and additional characterisation by serotype, *eae* genes, and subtypes of *stx1/stx2* should be performed if possible

Case classification

Possible case of STEC-associated HUS

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria for HUS

Probable case of STEC/VTEC

• Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link or a laboratory confirmed case without clinical criteria

Confirmed case of STEC/VTEC

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

1. Detection of *E. coli* O157 (most prominent serotype in HUS cases):

- Bacteriology: Isolation of O157 colonies on Sorbitol-MacConkey agar (or CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey agar) after incubation for 24 hours at 37 °C (or 41°C). O157 is confirmed via the *E. coli* O157 Latex Test.

- Serology: This method is constantly used at the German HUS-"Konsiliarlabor"; anti-O157 antibodies of IgG and IgM types can be distinguished.

2. Detection of Verotoxin (VTEC)-producing strains (used at the National Reference

Laboratory/Center for EHEC/VTEC/STEC): Stools are enriched overnight in a medium containing mitomycin C (EHEC Direct Medium, Heipha, Heidelberg, Germany). Enriched cultures are plated on selective agar (CT-Sorbitol-MacConkey, Enterohemolysin, and Sorbitol-MacConkey). After incubation for 18-24 hours at 37°C a representative mixture of the viable cells were subjected to PCR reactions analyzing *stx1*, *stx2*, *eae* and *Ehly* (Reischl et al. (2002), Journal of Clinical Microbiology, p. 2555-2565). Isolates are gained via colony picking and pathotyped with the same PCR scheme. Isolate identification is further confirmed by conventional biochemical tests (VITEK or Api 20E, bioMerieux, Marcy-l'Étoile, France).

All EHEC/STEC/VTEC isolates obtained in Austria are to be sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation, subtyping and comparison. All Shiga toxin producing *E. coli* are serotyped with *E. coli* antisera (*E. coli* antisera, Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark). Comparison of the isolates is done by Pulsed-Field-Gel-Electrophoresis.

Notification system in place

Notification of VTEC according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

See History of the disease

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See History of the disease

Relevance as a zoonotic disease

HUS is a rare complication of *E. coli* infection; however EHECs themselves are not rare, which means that a systemic disease develops only under certain particular predispositions, most of which are currently unknown. Although raw or undercooked meat and unpasteurised dairy products are likely candidates to transfer the bacterium to humans, the actual source of infection often remains unclear. The importance of hand hygiene after animal contact should be always considered.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 101 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases	unknown
HUS	14	0,17	9	5	0
- caused by O157 (VT+)	2	0,02	0	2	0
- caused by other VTEC	9	0,11	6	3	0
- unknown serovar	3	0,04	3	0	0
VTEC infect. (except HUS)	107	1,26	94	6	7
- caused by O157 (VT+)	25	0,30	20	1	4
- caused by other VTEC	71	0,84	65	3	3
- unknown serovar	10	0,12	8	2	0
HUS status not known	10	0,12	8	1	1
VTEC gesamt	131	1,55	111	12	8

Data source: EMS/NRL as of May 27, 2015

Table 102 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* infections in human - age distribution (EMS/NRL), 2013

age groups	all VTEC infections			HUS		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	18	13	5	3	2	1
1 to 4 years	61	38	23	6	3	3
5 to 14 years	14	10	4	3	2	1
15 to 24 years	8	3	5	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	15	9	6	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	10	3	7	1	0	1
65 years and older	4	0	4	0	0	0
Gesamtergebnis	130	76	54	14	7	7

Data source: EMS/NRL as of May 27, 2015

4.4.3. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e.g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Fresh meat, meat preparations, fruits, vegetables etc.

Defintion of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The sample is analyzed according to ISO/TS 13136.

There is no further testing for negative PCR results in the bacterial enrichment.

If the bacterial enrichment is PCR-positive, it is streaked on to solid media. At least 50 colonies are tested for the presence of *stx1* and/or *stx2*. The Shigatoxin producing *E. coli* is sent to the National Reference Center for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* (VTEC) in Graz where the presence of the *stx*-genes, *eae*-genes and additional virulence factors is tested by PCR.

Subsequently the VTEC is serotyped conventionally (antisera).

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

All isolates detected in food have to be sent to the National Reference Centre for *Escherichia coli* including verotoxin producing *E. coli* in Graz, where the isolates are further analysed and stored.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions taken.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Results of the investigation

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

In 2014, 811 samples of animal origin, 200 samples of non-animal origin and 15 samples of other processed food products and prepared dishes were tested for VTEC. 7 out of 211 (3.3%) samples from milk, milk products and cheeses (all from cows', sheeps' or goats' milk) were positive for VTEC. Five of the positive findings were cheeses made of raw milk or low heat-treated milk from sheep (3 of the 5 positive findings) and from goats (2 of the positive findings) at the processing plant. Raw milk from cows at retail was tested 16 times for VTEC, and in one sample VTEC O55:H12 has been isolated.

126 samples of fresh meat of several animals (bovine animals, deer, pig, rabbit, sheep, wild boar,) were tested for VTEC resulting in 19 positive samples (15.1%). The highest prevalence of VTEC was detected in fresh meat from deer (venison) in 35.1% (13 out of 37) and fresh meat from wild boar (2 positive samples out of 10). 464 samples of different meat products, meat preparations, mixed meat etc. were tested for VTEC showing 1 positive.

All vegetables, fruits, herbs (200 samples) and other processed food products and prepared dishes were negative for VTEC.

Relevance of the findings in foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of human infection)

The relevance of these findings is delineated in foodborne outbreaks.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Campaign A-801-14: VTEC in food – Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) – meat products and fermented sausages – at retail - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail outlets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February to March

Type of specimen taken

Red meat - meat products and fermented sausages

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 25g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of VTEC in 25g

Results of the investigation

95 samples were tested for VTEC: none positive

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella* spp. and *Listeria monocytogenes*. In this year's campaign we observed better results than in 2012 (campaign A-804-12) where 2 samples were tested positive for VTEC.

Campaign A-023-14: *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic – Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in food – vegetables-leaves & vegetables - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: May - July

Type of specimen taken

Vegetables, especially salad (pre-cut, ready to eat), pre-cut vegetables and sprouted seeds (6 samples)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: at least 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*

Results of the investigation

52 samples tested for pathogenic *E. coli* (VTEC): VTEC was not detected in any sample.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*, *Listeria*, Hepatitis A Virus. Austrian food experts do recommend further specific campaigns, focussing on microbiological hazards in food of non-animal origin.

Campaign A-036-14: *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic – Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in food – fruits - frozen or ready-to-eat - at retail - monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at retail.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: July - September

Type of specimen taken

Berries (frozen and ready-to-eat) and pre-cut melons (ready-to-eat only) have been sampled

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 250g

Definition of positive finding

Detection of *stx1*- and/or *stx2*-positive *E. coli*

Results of the investigation

57 samples tested for pathogenic *E. coli* (VTEC): VTEC was not detected in any sample.

Additional information

Samples were also tested for *Salmonella*, *Listeria*, Norovirus and Hepatitis A Virus.

Austrian food experts suggest further campaigns concerning food of non animal origin and microbiological hazards. Therefore in 2015 another campaign in fruits and vegetables is planned.

Table 103 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic - Verotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	VTEC O8:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O8:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O55:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O139:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O182:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive					
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Cheeses made from cows milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - hard - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	35	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	25 Gram				Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from cows milk - unspecified		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	16	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from goats milk - soft and semi-soft - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
					25 Gram	Gram	11	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses made from sheeps milk - soft and semi-soft - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from pasteurised milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from mixed milk from cows, sheep and/or goats - fresh - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cheeses, made from unspecified milk or other animal milk - unspecified - made from raw or low heat-treated milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Crustaceans		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 98 cont.

Food	Sampling Details		Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	VTEC O8:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O8:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O55:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O139:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O182:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive						
	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin																																			
Meat from bovine animals - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	21	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	33	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from bovine animals - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from deer (venison) - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	12	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	13	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0		
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from deer (venison) - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - fresh	Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - meat products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from other animal species or not specified - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from pig - fresh	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Table 98 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC)	VTEC O8:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O8:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O55:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O139:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O182:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive				
Meat from pig - meat preparation - intended to be eaten cooked	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from pig - meat products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from pig - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from poultry, unspecified - meat products - raw and intended to be eaten raw	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from rabbit - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat from sheep - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from sheep - meat preparation	Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - fresh	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat from wild boar - meat products	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Retail	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products	Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	10 Gram	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - cooked, ready-to-eat	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - fermented sausages	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Game handling establishment	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Meat, mixed meat - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked	Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 98 cont.

Food	Sampling Details		Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sample Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	VTEC O8:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O8:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O55:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O139:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O182:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive								
	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage																																								
Meat, mixed meat - minced meat - intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0					
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	28	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos)		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	campaign A-801-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - cooked ready to eat		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	campaign A-801-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - raw but intended to be eaten cooked		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Milk from other animal species or unspecified - raw milk		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Milk, cows - raw milk		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	16	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Milk, cows - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

Table 98 cont.

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxinogenic E. coli (VTEC)	VTEC O8:H9 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O8:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O55:H12 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O74:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:H25 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O88:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O91:H14 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O103:H2 - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O139:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O142:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O153:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O182:Hrough - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H30 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive					
Milk, goats - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Milk, goats - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Milk, sheeps - raw milk	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Milk, sheeps - raw milk for manufacture - intended for manufacture of raw or low heat-treated products	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Other food	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Other processed food products and prepared dishes	Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	1 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		XX	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Spices and herbs	Farm	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables	Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		XX	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		XX	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	campaign A-023-14	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables - non-pre-cut	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	17	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Vegetables - pre-cut	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Vegetables - products	Catering	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		XX	10 Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	25 Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

4.4.4. Pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in animals

A. Verotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* in cattle (bovine animals)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

The monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in slaughtered cattle was continued. The sampling was stratified based on the number of processed animals per abattoir in Austria. The date of sampling was randomized over the year 2014. Sampling was performed in the 13 abattoirs which processed more than 80 % of Austria's cattle in 2013. 135 slaughtered bovines were sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was distributed randomly over the period of the study from January to December 2014.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at slaughter

A part of the intestine containing rectum and anus.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at slaughter

The sampling was performed by qualified veterinarians who carry out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration, a part of rectum and anus was sampled. After cooling down to 4 °C, the sample had been sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz the same day, in a polystyrene box along with cooling packs. In the laboratory, a swab from the rectum-anal mucosa was incubated in a selective broth.

Case definition

Animals at slaughter

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verocytotoxic *E. coli* irrespective of intimin) from its recto-anal mucosa.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at slaughter

In a first step the samples were screened for the presence of genes encoding verotoxins (*vtx*) via PCR, secondly positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation. At first, the swab was enriched using EHEC Direktmedium containing mitomycin C for 18 to 24 hours at 37 °C on a shaker. The process was followed by testing the enrichment for the presence of *vtx1* and *vtx2* (Reischl U. et al. 2002: Real-Time Fluorescence PCR Assays for Detection and Characterization of Shiga Toxin, Intim and Enterohemolysin Genes from Shiga Toxin-Producing *Escherichia coli*. Journ of Clin Microb, 40, p 2555-2565). Sediment of positive enrichments were plated on sorbitol MacConkey (SMAC) -, on cefixime tellurite sorbitol MAC (CT-SMAC) -, and on enterohemolysin agar and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Of these 3 selective agar plates altogether five suspect colonies were cultered on sheep blood agar COS. Afterwards the genomes of pure culteres were investigated in the above mentioned real time PCR for harbouring the genes for verotoxin 1, verotoxin 2, intimin and enterohemolysin. The serotyping of VTEC was carried out by the National Reference Center for VTEC in the AGES Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

No notification system in place.

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from bovine remained high (32 %); we hypothesize that this is due to a high sensitivity of PCR, the sampling material (recto-anal swabs) and the improvement in the VTEC isolation techniques especially the use of the enterohemolysin-agar. Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), four isolates were detected in samples from cattle (2 x VTEC O157, 2 x VTEC O26).

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in feces seems to be low because VTEC are found only in a very low prevalence on meat samples from bovines.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) in animal – Sheep

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Monitoring program on the prevalence of VTEC in sheep at farm:

The monitoring in 2014 was directed towards sheep at farms. 133 sheep (out of 133 different farms) had to be tested, calculated on a population of sheep of 350,000 in Austria in 2013. The sampling had been stratified on the number and size of sheep holdings in Austrian provinces.

Frequency of the sampling

Animals at farm:

The sampling was done after blood sampling in course of the *Brucella melitensis* control program.

Type of specimen taken

Animals at farm:

Recto-anal swabs

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Animals at farm

The swab was sent in transport medium cooled down to 4 °C in a polystyrene box after adding cooling units to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz.

Case definition

Animals at farm

An animal is considered to be infected with VTEC following the isolation of VTEC (verocytotoxic *E. coli* irrespective of intimin) from one of the samples tested.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Animals at farm

In a first step the samples were screened for presence of verotoxin genes by PCR, secondly the positive samples were processed for VTEC isolation, see chapter cattle. The serotyping was carried out by the National Reference Laboratory for VTEC in the AGES-Institute for Medical Microbiology and Hygiene (IMED) in Graz.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Harmonization of methods with regard to all possible VTEC serotypes.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

The food business operator is referred to his responsibilities according to Reg. 178/2002, Art. 19.

Notification system in place

No notification

Results of the investigation

See table.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The prevalence of isolated VTEC from sheep remained high (60 %) but lower than in 2013 (72 %). Concerning the 5 most important VTEC serotypes for humans (O157, O26, O103, O111 and O145), one VTEC O26 was isolated from sheep in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance of findings of VTEC in/on sheep seems to be low because sheep meat is consumed well-done.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 104 Verocytotoxic *Escherichia coli* in animals, 2014

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin gene positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O104:H7 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O109:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O112ab:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O113:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:H4 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O113:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O116:HNM - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O128abc:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O146:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O148:HNM - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O149:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O157:H7 - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O157:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O166:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O166:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	
Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VENMI Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	135	87	43	2	0	1	0	0	2	2	1	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Sheep - mixed herds	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	VENMI Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	133	100	80	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	5	7	1	1	0	0	7	2	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

Table 104 cont.

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin gene positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O166:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O174:H2 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O174:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O176:H4 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O176:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O177:HNM - eae positive vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O178:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O179:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O181:H49 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O181:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O183:H18 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O185:H28 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O22:H8 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O22:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O22:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O26:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O5:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O5:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O5:HNM - eae positive vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O6:H10 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	
Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VENI, Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	135	87	43	2	0	3	0	1	1	0	0	1	3	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	2	0
Sheep - mixed herds	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	VENI, Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	133	100	80	0	1	0	2	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	11	0	2	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

Table 104 cont.

animal species	sampling context	Sampling stage	Source of information	Sampling unit	units tested	Verotoxin gene positive	units with VTEC isolated	VTEC O 157	VTEC O6:H10 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O6:H34 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O75:H8 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O76:H19 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O76:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O79:H19 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O81:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC O81:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O82:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H16 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O87:H16 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:H21 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC O91:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H18 - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H2 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:H28 - eae negative vtx1 negative vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative	VTEC Orough:HNM - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 positive	VTEC Orough:Hrough - eae negative vtx1 positive vtx2 negative
Cattle (bovine animals) - unspecified	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at slaughterhouse - animal sample - mucosal swab (rectum-anal)	VENM Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	135	87	43	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	2	0	0
Sheep - mixed herds	Monitoring - official sampling - objective sampling	at farm - animal sample - mucosal swab	VENM Graz, NRL VTEC Graz	Animal	133	100	80	0	1	0	3	3	3	1	0	1	1	1	1	7	1	0	0	3	0	1	0	1	

In some samples more than 1 VTEC-isolate could be identified.

4.5. Tuberculosis

4.5.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Human tuberculosis has steadily declined during the last decades. Commission Decision 1999/467/EC of 15 July 1999 declared bovine herds of Austria officially tuberculosis-free.

In humans the number of tuberculosis cases is decreasing. Cases of *M. bovis* or *M. caprae* are very seldom and reactivations of past infections. All *M. caprae* cases in humans in the last years showed different molecular typing patterns than the *M. caprae* isolated from cattle; therefore no human cases could be attributed to the recently cases in bovines.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Bovine tuberculosis poses no public health problem in Austria. Sheep, goats and pigs are free of bovine tuberculosis. Although in spring 2008 infective lung tuberculosis caused by *M. caprae* was diagnosed in one slaughtered cattle. All cattle of that holding were culled following an intra cutan testing showing several positive reactors. Two more cattle holdings with several reactors were culled and some single reactors in contact holdings. In 21 cattle out of 14 holdings *M. caprae* was isolated in 2008. In 2009 again 6 cattle out of 3 holdings were bacteriologically confirmed and in 2010 eight cattle were identified as infected with *M. caprae* and 2011 three cases were found to be positive for *M. caprae*. In 2013, ten bovines out of five herds were infected with *M. caprae*. In 2014, 11 bovines out of 10 herds were diagnosed with *M. caprae*. Since several years a reservoir of *M. caprae* in red deer in an Austrian region has been confirmed and cattle are exposed to the bacteria in the summertime grazing on contaminated pastures in the Alps.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings of *M. bovis* in animals, although *M. caprae* was detected. In 2014, the single human case of *M. caprae* was a person with place of birth and nationality other than Austria; the molecular typing results confirmed that this case is epidemiologically not linked to the *M. caprae* cases in animals in Western Austria. The single human *M. bovis* case was detected in a male person of 65 years or older.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2011 a new regulation has been implemented to control *M. caprae* in red deer (BGBl. II Nr. 181/2011). The regulation (Rindertuberkuloseverordnung, BGBl II 2008/322) obliges the intracutan testings (using simultaneously bovine and avium tuberculin) of all cattle and goats that are kept together with cattle in given districts due to the epidemiological situation.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

Nil

4.5.2. Tuberculosis in humans

A. Tuberculosis due to *Mycobacterium bovis* in humans

Case definition

Definite: A case with isolation of *M. tuberculosis* complex (except *M. bovis* BCG) from any clinical specimen.

Other than definite: A case that meets the clinical criteria above but does not meet the laboratory criteria of a definite case.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Definite: Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen, Auramin-Rhodamin stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material
- Culture: After decontamination of the homogenised sample material in NALC-NaOH and centrifugation, the sample material is transferred in parallel on Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing glycerol and PACT and Stonebrink agar containing PACT and MGITmedium. The media are incubated at 37 °C for up to 8 weeks. Confirmation of the species by Amplicor (Roche)
- Other than definite: A skin test and an X-Ray of the thorax are performed.

Notification system in place

The person who diagnoses (laboratory/hospital/general practitioner) has to notify definite (*M. tuberculosis* and *M. bovis*) and other than definite cases (this excludes radiologists) to the local health authority (Federal Law BGBl. 127/1968: Tuberkulosegesetz, as amended; Epidemiegesetz 1950, as amended). *M. bovis* is notifiable since 2004 (National Regulation BGBl. Nr. 254/2004: Anzeigepflichtige übertragbare Krankheiten 2004).

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The National Reference Center for tuberculosis (NRC-T) has been nominated since 1995. Since 1998 all data are compiled in a national database.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One case each of *M. bovis* and *M. caprae* were identified; the human *M. caprae* cases were epidemiologically not linked to the cases in cattle; the *M. bovis* case was identified in a person (65 years of age or older) and was maybe a case of reactivation, because in Austria *M. bovis* has not been detected in bovines since years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

The relevance is inconsiderable.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure and the annual report of the National Reference Center for tuberculosis.

Table 105 Tuberculosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (NRC), 2014

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	cases with nationality other than Austria	cases with place of birth other than Austria
Tuberculosis	428	5.03	253	288
<i>M. bovis</i>	1	0.01	0	0
<i>M. tuberculosis</i>	410	4.82	245	280
<i>M. caprae</i>	1	0.01	1	1
<i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)	15	0.18	6	6
Other species (<i>M. africanum</i>)	1	0.01	1	1
Reactivation of previous cases	-*	-	-	-

* Available data unreliable

Data source: National Reference Center for tuberculosis as of Mai 26, 2015

Table 106 Tuberculosis in humans - age distribution (NRC), 2014

Age group	Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. bovis</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. caprae</i>			Tuberculosis due to <i>M. tuberculosis</i> complex (not differentiated)		
	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F	All	M	F
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	5	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	75	52	23	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	149	89	59	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1
45 to 64 years	99	68	31	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	5	3
65 years and older	79	53	26	1	1	0	1	1	0	4	2	2
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	410	266	143	1	1	0	1	1	0	15	8	7

Data source: National Reference Center for tuberculosis as of Mai 26, 2015

4.5.3. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animals

A. *Mycobacterium bovis* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine tuberculosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Council Directive 64/432/EWG from June 26, 1964, Austria has the status Officially Tuberculosis Free Member State declared in the Commission Decision 1999/467/EC from July 15th, 1999, replaced by Commission Decision 2003/467/EC from June 23rd, 2003. Therefore, as of May 2000 the nationwide intradermal testing has been suspended and the disease is now monitored as a part of ante- and post mortem inspection of all bovine animals and goats (which were kept together with bovines) slaughtered.

According to the national Regulation “Rindertuberkuloseverordnung” (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all *Mycobacteria* belonging to the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex are compulsory notifiable. The Rindertuberkuloseverordnung shall apply to bovine animals and to goats, which are kept together with bovine animals.

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to the monitoring system of ante and post mortem inspection of slaughtered animals, samples are taken from carcasses which show pathological-anatomical alterations, characteristic for tuberculosis at slaughterhouse. Laboratory examination and diagnosis is done by the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Mödling).

Type of specimen taken

Organs/tissues: Sampling is carried out according to Annex 4 of the Rindertuberkuloseverordnung).

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The alterations and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the national reference laboratory for tuberculosis in animals (AGES Mödling).

Case definition

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung – Tuberculosis is defined as an infection with *Mycobacteria* of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Live bovine animals and goats: Intracutan testing (simultaneous testing using bovine and avium tuberculin): The test is performed according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964 and the national Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no.322/2008). A reactor is an animal which is not negative (either doubtful or positive) to intradermal testing.

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture is performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for tuberculosis in animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörensen Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37°C ± 1°C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Identification of *Mycobacteria* species and genotyping of strains is undertaken using molecular biological methods, such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR), DNA-striptechnology, restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), spoligotyping and MIRU-VNTR (mycobacterial interspersed repetitive unit – variable number tandem repeat) analysis.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Subsequent to the detection of *M. caprae* – positive cases in wild red deer in specific areas of the provinces Tyrol and Vorarlberg the BMG (Federal Ministry of Health) has ordered annual testing of cattle and goats kept together with bovines in specific risk areas (special testing zones and special monitoring zones according to § 1 (4) and (5) of Rindertuberkuloseverordnung using the simultaneous intradermal test.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

According to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung (BGBl. II no. 322/2008) all live animals suspected being infected shall to be killed for diagnostic purposes. All animals of the holding of origin of such animals shall be tested immediately (simultaneous intradermal test) and epidemiologic investigations shall be carried out. The status of disease freedom of holding which is suspected of being infected is suspended and subsequently withdrawn in case of confirmation of the disease and the holding is banned immediately after suspicion. Milk from such holdings shall be used for human consumption only according to the specifications laid down in Annex III, Section IX, Chapter I of the Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 laying down specific hygiene rules for food of animal origin or shall be used after boiling for feeding the animals of the affected holding only. The status of freedom of disease of an infected holding is regained after culling of all animals tested positive and disinfection under official control.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

See "Other preventive measures in place".

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

See "Control program/mechanisms - The control program/strategies in place".

Notification system in place

The notification of bovine animals and goats kept together with bovines suspected of being infected shall be compulsory.

Results of the investigation

In 2014, *M. bovis* was not detected in cattle. In total, 11 bovines from 10 herds were diagnosed as infected with *M. caprae*.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *M. bovis* in cattle. In total 11 bovines from 10 herds were infected with *M. caprae*. Due to the fact that *M. caprae* is endemic in wildlife deer in certain areas of the Western parts of Austria (and South-Western parts of Germany), the testing of animals according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung within special testing zones and special monitoring zones will be carried on for the time being.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

In case of the suspicion of the disease in a holding, all measures which shall be taken according to Rindertuberkuloseverordnung shall be notified in written to the zoonosis coordinator of the province affected by.

Additional information

M. caprae is differentiated in Austria. The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure. See also the publication: Fink M, Schleicher C, Gonano M, Prodingner WM, Pacciarini M, Glawischnig W, et al. 2015. Red Deer as Maintenance Host for Bovine Tuberculosis, Alpine Region (http://wwwnc.cdc.gov/eid/article/21/3/14-1119_article).

B. *Mycobacterium* spp. in animal - all animals - at slaughter – Control programme - mandatory - official sampling (all slaughtered animals except those mentioned above)

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to the federal law on monitoring zoonoses and on pathogenes of zoonoses (BGBl. I no. 2005/128) following shall be subject to monitoring:

-tuberculosis caused by *M. bovis*

-tuberculosis – except *M. bovis* – according to the epidemiological situation

According to federal law “Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I no. 13/2016) and the Regulation „Tierseuchen-Untersuchungspflicht-Verordnung BGBl. II no. 90/2007) all animals which are to be slaughtered shall be subject to ante and post-mortem inspection.

Samples from animals suspected of being infected are taken at slaughter. Tissues of slaughtered animals which are visibly altered, seen by the unaided eye.

Frequency of the sampling

Continuous post-mortem inspections of each slaughtered animal

Type of specimen taken

Other: Macroscopic tuberculous alterations and lymphnodes

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The altered tissue and lymph nodes are excised and sent to the laboratory

Case definition

According to the Regulation (EC) no 654/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Staining: Ziehl-Neelsen stains are performed on histological preparation and smears of the sample material.

Culture performed in the AGES National Reference Laboratory for Tuberculosis in Animals in Mödling - After decontamination of the homogenised sample material (2g, homogenised, add 10 ml buffer) in NALC-NaOH 1% (25 min), neutralization (Sörens. Buffer sol.) and centrifugation (3500g, 20 min), the sample material is transferred on commercial media (heipha/biotest: Loewenstein-Jensen agar containing antibiotics (PACT) and Stonebrink agar containing pyruvate and PACT). The media are incubated at 37° C ± 1° C up to 12 weeks. MTC species are identified with the GenoType MTBC assay (Hain Lifescience GmbH, Nehren, Germany).

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is prohibited.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

See other chapters.

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

The control strategy is based on the compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection of all animals slaughtered.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No need at the moment

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Measures are taken according to the Regulation (EC) no 654/2004, Annex I, Chapter IX lit. E

Notification system in place

The detection of tuberculosis is notifiable.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No cases in Austria in 2014. See previous chapter "A".

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

No cases in Austria in 2014. See previous chapter "A".

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 107 Bovine tuberculosis in countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing for eradication programme, 2014

Member State: Austria..... Date of the report: 2.04.2014..... Year: 2014.....

The official post-mortem examination for all slaughtered bovine animals is implemented: Yes

Region (¹)	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds*		Infected herds*		Routine tuberculin testing		Number of tuberculin tests carried out before the introduction into the herds (Annex A(1)(2)(c) third indent (¹) of Directive 64/432/EEC)	Number of animals with suspicious lesions of tuberculosis examined and submitted to histopathological and bacteriological examinations	Number of animals detected positive in bacteriological examination (* <i>M. bovis</i>)
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Interval between routine tuberculin tests (²)	Number of animals tested			
Austria	65,209	195,3201	65,199	99.985	10	0.015	a und g	57,485	49	36	11 (<i>M. caprae</i>)
Total	65,209	195,3201	65,199	99.985	10	0.015	a und g	57,485	49	36	11 (<i>M. caprae</i>)

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Use the following letter codes: (a) no routine tests; (b) tests once a year; (c) tests every two years; (d) tests every three years concerning 24 month-old animals; (f) tests every 4 years; (g) others (please give details) Sonderuntersuchungs- bzw. überwachungsgebiet.

*Additional information: In 2014, 11 bovines out of 10 herds were diagnosed with *M. caprae* (*M. caprae*: officially free herds: 99.985 %; infected herds: 0.015%): The control program is identical to the program to control *M. bovis*.

Table 108 Tuberculosis in other animals, 2014

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Mycobacteriaspp.</i>	M. bovis	M. caprae
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	282,625	0	0	0
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	55,894	0	0	0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - census sampling	compulsory ante-mortem and post-mortem inspection	CVS	animal	5,409,578	0	0	0
Cattle	at farm – animal sampling	Control and eradication programme - official sampling - selective sampling	tuberculin testing in special tuberculosis examination and control areas	CVS	animal	57,485	11	0	11

*TBC-Sonderuntersuchungsgebiete sowie TBC-Sonderüberwachungsgebiete

CVS: Central veterinary services

4.6. Brucellosis

4.6.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In Austria, human brucellosis cases are considered to be an imported infectious disease. The Austrian cattle, sheep and goat population bears the status Officially Brucellosis Free (OBF) and Officially *Brucella melitensis* free (OBmF).

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

One human case was identified in 2014. This case was an imported case. The number of brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

No findings in Austria, OBF and OBmF

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and blood-samples in cattle (Bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continuation of the existing control programs

Additional information

If zoonotic agents listed in the national Zoonoses Act are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.6.2. Brucellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of Brucellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with fever

AND at least one of following seven symptoms:

- Sweating (profuse, malodorous, specially nocturnal)
- Chills
- Arthralgia
- Weakness
- Depression
- Headache
- Anorexia

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Isolation of *Brucella* spp. from a clinical specimen

- *Brucella* specific antibody response (Standard Agglutination Test, Complement Fixation, ELISA)

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Serological examination: Serum samples are tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from CVL-Weybridge. Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (VLA Weybridge) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and SAT.

- Bacteriological: Multiple blood samples are inoculated in blood culture broth over several consecutive days. The incubation lasted 4 to 6 weeks, once per week medium is transferred on *Brucella* agar and incubated 5-10 % CO₂ atmosphere (Anonymus: Standardisierung und Qualitätssicherung in der mikrobiologischen Diagnostik. Richtlinien. Bundesministerium für Soziale Sicherheit und Generationen. ISBN 3-84123- 126-0, Wien, 2001, pg. 56).

- The genus is identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species is identified by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.)

Notification system in place

Notification of Brucellosis according to the Federeal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is OBF and OBmF. All cases reported in Austria are epidemiologically linked to travel in endemic countries or to foreign workers from endemic countries.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

This zoonosis has no relevance in Austria.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 109 Brucellosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	Imported cases	Unknown status
<i>brucellosis</i>	1	0.01	0	1	0
<i>Brucella</i> spp.	1	0.01	0	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL (as of 2.03.2015)

Table 110 Brucellosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRL), 2014

Age group	brucellosis			<i>Brucella</i> unspecified		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	-	-	-	-	-	-
1 to 4 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
5 to 14 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
15 to 24 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
25 to 44 years	1	1	-	1	1	-
45 to 64 years	-	-	-	-	-	-
65 years and older	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age unknown	-	-	-	-	-	-
All age groups	1	1	0	1	1	0

Data source: EMS/NRL (as of 2.03.2015)

4.6.3. *Brucella* in foodstuffs

Due to the fact that Austria is OBF and OBmF, food is not investigated for *Brucella* spp.

4.6.4. *Brucella* spp. in animals

A. *Brucella abortus* in bovine animals

Status as officially free of bovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

Upon the request of the Commission Decision of July 15th 1999, CD 1999/466/EC, as amended, by the Council Directive 64/432/EEC of 26 June 1964, Austria achieved the status: officially brucellosis-free for bovine herds.

A new national regulation has been implemented concerning the examination of milk- and blood-samples in cattle (Bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In milk producing holdings and non-milk producing holdings a risk based blood sampling plan was performed.

Abortion or premature birth: Abortive material and blood of the cow is sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

Holdings with and without milk production: A risk based sampling plan has been calculated stratified according to the different provinces bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). In case of not-negative bulk milk samples, blood samples in the affected holding were investigated. If blood serology does not show a definitive negative result diagnostic slaughtering of the affected animal has to be carried out.

- Abortion or premature birth in connex with epidemiological investigation: must be notified to the district veterinarian (§§ 7 and 25 bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Tissues from the aborted fetus and blood from the affected cows are sampled immediately post abortion and tested for brucellosis by microbiological and serological methods.

Type of specimen taken

Bulk milk

Blood samples

Aborted fetus

Diagnostic slaughtering: organs and lymph nodes of the genital tract; udder and accessory lymph nodes; fetus (stomach, lungs); retropharyngeal lymph node.

Abortion or premature birth: Tissue and blood samples from the animal that had an abortion.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Bulk milk sampling and inholdings without milk production blood samples are taken according to the sampling plan (bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013). Samples are sent to the laboratory.

334/2013). Samples are sent to the laboratory.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted tissue and blood samples sent to the NRL.

(all based on: bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013).

Case definition

An animal is considered to be positive for *Brucella abortus*, in case of positive blood-serological test result and the epidemiological situation of the herd indicates the possibility that a *Brucella* infection has been introduced to the herd or in case of bacteriological isolation. If a single animal reactor is detected in the holding, tracing back is an important tool to get more information about the animal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bulk milk: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE.

Blood samples: Testings according to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and the manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals of the OIE: Routinely single serum samples or serum pools (5 sera in one pool) were tested in the Indirect-ELISA (I-ELISA) using the three OIE ELISA Brucella Standard Sera (OIE ELISAwPSS, OIE ELISAsPSS, OIE ELISAnSS) and the OIE *Brucella abortus* Positive International Standard Antiserum (OIEISS) to calibrate the method (Commission Regulation 535/2002/EC of 21 March 2002 amending Annex C to Council Directive 64/432/EEC and amending Decision 2000/330/EC). Following a positive or suspected test result in the IELISA single serum samples were tested in the Complement Fixation Test (CFT), Rose Bengal test (RBT) and two ELISAs for verification.

Participation in international ring trials: Participation in international ring trials (AHVLA, ANSES) with ELISA, CFT, RBT and Serum Agglutination Test (SAT). The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for those Austrian Veterinary Institutes which are involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnosis.

Abortion or premature birth: Aborted material was tested bacteriologically as described above.

Bacteriology: Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10% CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species was differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

All serologically inconclusive or positive blood samples were sent to the National Reference Laboratory for confirmation respectively exclusion of serological cross reactions with other bacteria like *Yersinia enterocolitica*.

Vaccination policy

Vaccination is not allowed (§ 6 bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013)

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Control programme according to the National Regulation bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013) . Abortion or premature birth: compulsory notification according §§ 7 and 25 bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No actions, because OBF

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to the bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013.

Notification system in place

Abortion or premature birth; Notification of abortions in connex with epidemiological investigations: Bovine health surveillance and monitoring regulation, Federal Law Gazette II no. 334/2013 and Venereal diseases act, Federal Law Gazette no. 22/1949 as amended; The livestock owner has to notify the abortion within 24 hours to the mayor (Gemeinde). The mayor has to forward the notification to the district veterinarian (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde) . If the cow is being treated by a veterinarian or the veterinarian has been informed about the abortion, then the veterinarian has to notify to the official authority (Bezirksverwaltungsbehörde).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

OBF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. Brucella melitensis in sheep and goats

Status as officially free of ovine brucellosis during the reporting year

The entire country free: Yes

Additional information

According to Commission Decision Nr. 93/52/EWG, as amended, Austria has the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free (ObmF).

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples were examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a target prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling was performed by the competent authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it had delegated this responsibility. Samples were taken in the holdings. Aborted material and blood samples from the animal were also investigated.

Frequency of the sampling

Mainly the sampling was performed during the cold season, between November and May when the animals were kept in the stables.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples according to a sampling plan.
- Clinical cases: Aborted material and blood samples from the affected animal.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and aborted material are taken within the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be infected with *B. melitensis* in case of bacteriological isolation or positive serological test result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- Routinely single serum samples were tested in the Indirect ELISA. Confirmation of suspected or positive results was performed by the Complement Fixation Test (CFT) with reference standard antisera from AHVLA and ANSES. Participation in international ring trials on Brucellosis with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all national Veterinary Institutes. Bacteriology: Smears of the samples were stained by Stableforth's method. Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

According to BGBl. II 184/2002 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, § 4, Impfverbot) vaccination is not allowed.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Monitoring program and investigation of abortions

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

To maintain the status officially brucellosis (*B. melitensis*) free, according to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002) a representative number of samples have to be examined with a confidence level of 95 % to detect infected holdings at a prevalence of 0.2 %. Sampling is performed by the appropriate authority or under its supervision, by bodies to which it has delegated this responsibility. Samples are taken in the holdings. Notification and clarification of each clinical case by bacteriology and serology.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

ObmF

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to BGBl. 2002/184 (*Brucella melitensis*-Überwachungsverordnung, of 14 May 2002, § 3, Ausmerzung von Reagenten) reactors have to be culled, the carcasses have to be incinerated in an incineration plant.

Notification system in place

Notification of brucellosis or a suspicion of brucellosis according to BGBl. 391/1995 (*Brucellose-Verordnung*).

Results of the investigation

See tables

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

ObmF

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

D. *Brucella suis* in animal – Pigs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

According to Guideline 64/432/EEC as amended.

Frequency of the sampling

Targeted, following abortion and in positive cases contact holdings.

Type of specimen taken

- Monitoring: Blood samples;
- Clinical cases: Abortion material and blood samples from the affected animal; tissues: according to decree 74700/0132-IV/B/5/2008

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Individual blood samples and abortion material are taken from animals in the holdings and sent to the laboratories.

Case definition

An animal is considered to be serologically positive for brucellosis following one/more positive CFT Complement Fixation Test (CFT) and RBT Rose Bengal test (RBT) results (*B. abortus* used antigen). A bacteriological isolation may also be possible as in the case of *B. suis*.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

- *Brucella* ELISA and CFT are used.
- Participation in international ring trials: Brucellosis European Ring Trial 2000 and 2002 (AHVLA and ANSES) with ELISA, CFT and RBT. The National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis, Institute for Veterinary Disease Control in Moedling organized the national Brucellosis Ring Trials for all Veterinary Institutes.

Bacteriology:

- Smears of the samples are stained by Stableforth's method.
- Columbia agar (bioMérieux) and Columbia agar (BD) containing selective additives (Oxoid) were used. After inoculation the media were incubated for 5 days at 37 °C in an atmosphere containing 10 % CO₂. The genus was identified by microscopic examination, catalase-, oxidase- and the slide agglutination test using *Brucella* antiserum. The species were differentiated by CO₂ requirement, H₂S formation, urease activity, growth on media containing standard concentrations of basic fuchsin or thionin and agglutination with monospecific antisera and by PCR (Real-time detection of *Brucella abortus*, *Brucella melitensis* and *Brucella suis*. 2001: Redkar et al., Mol Cell Probes. 2001 Feb;15(1):43-52.).

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

No mandatory measures but notification is required.

Notification system in place

B. suis has been a notifiable disease since 1993 according to BGBl 1993/756, Tierseuchen-Anzeigepflichtverordnung, as amended.

Results of the investigation

There was no case of *Brucella suis* in 2014.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Due to the results of the passive monitoring in pigs we conclude that there is no need for an active monitoring program.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 111 Bovine Brucellosis data from countries and regions that do not receive European Union co-financing (non co-financed), 2014

Member State: Austria Date of report: 2.04.2015..... Year: 2014.....

Region ⁽¹⁾	Total number of existing bovine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance ⁽²⁾						Investigations of suspect cases								
			Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Serological tests			Examination of bulk milk samples			Information on abortions			Epidemiological investigation					
	Herds	Animals					Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of bovine herds tested	Number of animals or pools tested	Number of infected herds	Number of notified abortions whatever cause	Number of isolations of <i>Brucella</i> infection	Number of abortions due to <i>Brucella abortus</i>	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of suspended herds	Number of positive animals		Number of animals examined microbiologically	Number of animals positive microbiologically
Austria	65,209	195,3201	65,209	100	0	0	1,328	11,326	0	1,389	1,391	0	413	0	0	375	3	0	0		
Total	65,209	195,3201	65,209	100	0	0	1,328	11,326	0	1,389	1,391	0	413	0	0	375	3	0	0	32	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Table 112 Ovine and caprine brucellosis - data from countries that do not receive co-financing for control or eradication programme, 2014

Member State: Austria..... Date of report: 2.04.2015..... Year: 2014.....

Region (1)	Total number of existing ovine/caprine		Officially free herds		Infected herds		Surveillance (2)			Investigations of suspect cases				
	Herds	Animals	Number of herds	%	Number of herds	%	Number of herds tested	Number of animals tested	Number of infected herds	Number of animals tested with serological blood tests	Number of animals positive serologically	Number of animals examined micro-biologically	Number of animals positive micro-biologically	Number of suspended herds
Austria	22,481	502,362	22,481	100	0	0	1,583	20,145	0	8	0	0	0	0
Total	22,481	502,362	22,481	100	0	0	1,583	20,145	0	8	0	0	0	0

Source of information: Central Veterinary Services, Provincial Veterinary Services

(1) Detailed regional information is required, unless the officially free status has been granted to the whole territory of the Member State.

(2) Please give details.

Total number of existing ovine/caprine herds: Number is less than in Table 1 (Susceptible animal populations) because mixed farms are deducted from the sum.

4.7. Yersiniosis

4.7.1. General evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is not considered a major food borne illness in Austria. The incidence of human disease is low when compared to salmonellosis or campylobacteriosis and has been stable over the last years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

The sources of infections are unclear. Neither studies on sporadic cases nor scientific outbreak investigations were performed in Austria so far.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

None

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.7.2. Yersiniosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of yersiniosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least one of the following five symptoms:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Vomiting
- Abdominal pain (pseudoappendicitis)
- Tenesmus

Laboratory criteria

- Isolation of human pathogenic *Y. enterocolitica* or *Y. pseudotuberculosis* from a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Sample material is plated directly on cefsulodin-irgasan-novobiocin (CIN) agar and incubated for 18 hours at 30 °C. Suspicious colonies are identified in an Api 20 E reaction and API 50 CHE reaction.

Y. enterocolitica is agglutinated with sera against serogroups O:3; O:5,27; O:9 and O:8. Biovar and pathogenicity are defined.

Notification system in place

Notification of yersiniosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Yersiniosis is the fourth most bacterial food borne pathogen in Austria although compared to salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, the number of notified cases are much lower.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of human cases has been similar in the last years.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

In Austria yersiniosis is much less identified than salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the FMH.

Table 113 Yersiniosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS/NRC), 2014

Yersiniosis	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population
pathogenic types	96	1,13
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 3	1	0,01
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4	83	0,95
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:5,27 biovar 2	1	0,01
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2	9	0,10
<i>Yersinia pseudotuberculosis</i>	2	0,02
apathogenic	10	0,11
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:Unknown biovar 1a	1	0,01
unknown pathogenicity	10	0,11
<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> , serovar and biovar unknown	9	0,10

Data source: EMS/NRC as of 11.2.2015

Table 114 Yersiniosis in humans - age distribution (EMS/NRC), 2014

age groups	<i>Yersinia</i> spp.			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:3 biovar 4			<i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i> O:9 biovar 2			<i>Yersinia</i> <i>pseudotuberculosis</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	2	2	0	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	28	16	12	21	10	11	2	1	1	1	1	0
5 to 14 years	21	15	6	15	10	5	1	1	0	0	0	0
15 to 24 years	14	9	5	13	9	4	1	0	1	0	0	0
25 to 44 years	24	9	15	19	7	12	4	2	2	0	0	0
45 to 64 years	13	5	8	11	4	7	1	1	0	1	0	1
65 years and older	4	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	106	58	48	83	43	40	9	5	4	2	1	1

Data source: EMS/NRC as of 11.2.2015

4.7.3. *Yersinia* in foodstuffs

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit)

regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method: EN ISO 10273:2003 in combination with the PCR Screening: ISO/TS 18867.

Results of the investigation

See table below

Table 115 *Yersinia* spp. in food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for <i>Yersinia</i>
Other processed food products and prepared dishes - unspecified		Retail	XX	single (food/feed)	25	Gram	42	0

4.7.4. *Yersinia* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not relevant in Austria therefore no testing.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

EU wide harmonized monitoring program.

Notification system in place:

Findings of *Yersinia* are not notifiable in animals.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No changes in recent years.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

The relevance has not been investigated.

Additional information

Nil

4.8. Trichinellosis

4.8.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

No documented autochthon human infestations since several years.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of cases reported to the EMS. No documented autochthone human infestations in 2014.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

In 2014, no cases in farmed animals, although two wild boars diagnosed infested with *Trichinella*, one from Austria with *T. pseudospiralis*, one carcass imported from Poland with *T. spiralis*.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

No new measures implemented

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Reconsider the necessity of routine *Trichinella* meat inspection in pig carcasses

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.8.2. Trichinellosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of trichinellosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with at least three of the following six symptoms:

- Fever
- Muscle soreness and pain
- Diarrhoea
- Facial oedema
- Eosinophilia
- Subconjunctival, subungual and retinal haemorrhages

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following two:

- Demonstration of *Trichinella* larvae in tissue obtained by muscle biopsy
- *Trichinella* specific antibody response (IFA test, ELISA or Western Blot)

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot

Notification system in place

Notification of trichinellosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

The last autochthonous cases have been reported in 1970

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

No relevance in Austria

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry of Health. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 116 Trichinellosis in human - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2013

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Imported cases	Unkown
Trichinellosis	0	0.00	0	0
<i>Trichinella spiralis</i>	0	0.00	0	0

Data source: EMS as of February 12, 2015

4.8.3. *Trichinella* spp. in animals

A. *Trichinella* spp. in pigs

Number of officially recognised *Trichinella*-free holdings

Categories of holdings officially recognised *Trichinella*-free

Officially recognised regions with negligible *Trichinella* risk

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

General

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered pigs except pigs slaughtered by the farmer for his own consumption; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

General

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered pig

Type of specimen taken

General

Muscles: Diaphragm (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

General

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

General

Trichinella spp. detected with one of the given methods

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

Nil

Preventive measures in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004, as amended.

The contingency plan in place

Results of the investigation including description of the positive cases and the verification of the *Trichinella* species

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings of *Trichinella* in farmed animals.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

B. *Trichinella* spp. in horses

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Targeted sampling of all slaughtered horses; the sampling is performed by competent authorities; the samples are taken at slaughterhouses; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered horse

Type of specimen taken

Muscles from tongue, masseter, diaphragm and neck.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella sp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Vaccination policy

Nil

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

Results of the investigation

No findings in horses.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

No findings in horses.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

C. *Trichinella* spp. in animal - wild boars

Monitoring system**Sampling strategy**

Sampling of all hunted or harvested wild boars; the sampling is performed by hunters with special knowledge about trichinella investigation or by competent authorities; the sampling is stratified by geographical regions depending to the habitats of wild boar in Austria; samples are taken either immediately after shooting the animal or at the cold storage depots; the sampling is part of a monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

All farmed wild boars are controlled for trichinella.

Type of specimen taken

Diaphragm muscles (crus), tongue, masseter and abdominal muscles.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

A given weight of muscle is excised out of the carcass.

Case definition

Trichinella sp. detected with one of the given methods.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 2075/2005, magnetic stirrer method for pooled-sample digestion

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

Nil

Control program/mechanisms**The control program/strategies in place**

Lebensmittelsicherheits- und Verbraucherschutzgesetz (LMSVG, BGBl. I 2006/13, as amended),
Fleischuntersuchungsverordnung (BGBl II 2006/109 as amended)

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

According to Regulation (EC) Nr. 854/2004 as amended.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, *Trichinella* spp. was detected in two wild boars, one Austrian animal was infested with *T. pseudospiralis*, the second carcass was imported from Poland in which *T. spiralis* was detected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 117 *Trichinella* spp. in animals, 2014

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Sampling Details	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Trichinella</i> spp.
Pigs							
fattening pigs not raised under controlled housing conditions in integrated system	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	5,376,923	0
Domestic solipeds							
horses	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	943	0
Wild boars							
Wild boars	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official and industry sampling - census sampling		CVS	animal	26,218	2
Foxes							
				CVS	animal	9	0
Badger							
				CVS	animal	28	0

CVS: Central Veterinary Services

4.9. Echinococcosis

4.9.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Austria is a low risk country for both forms of echinococcosis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The number of echinococcosis cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases reported to the EMS.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Alveolar echinococcosis: Due to the infestation rates of red foxes in Austria (0-40 %) there is a relatively elevated risk for hunters, cat owners and farmers.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Tools for preventive serological screening of hunters (and also other persons) have been established to detect *Echinococcus multilocularis* infections in an early stage. The early detection of the infection is the prerequisite for a successful curative treatment.

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

If zoonotic agents that are listed in the national Zoonoses Act, are isolated from human specimen, food or animals the laboratories are obliged to send these strains to the respective national reference lab for typing and comparative analysis.

4.9.2. Echinococcosis in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

The number of *Echinococcosis* cases presented in this report reflects the number of laboratory confirmed cases notified to the EMS.

EU-Case definition

Clinical criteria

Not relevant for surveillance purposes

Diagnostic criteria

At least one of the following five findings:

- Histopathology or parasitology compatible with *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* (e.g. direct visualisation of the protoscolex in cyst fluid)
- Detection of *Echinococcus granulosus* pathognomonic macroscopic morphology of cyst(s) in surgical specimens
- Typical organ lesions detected by imaging techniques (e.g.: computerised tomography, sonography, MRI) AND confirmed by a serological test
- *Echinococcus* spp. specific serum antibodies by high-sensitivity serological test AND confirmed by a high specificity serological test
- Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* or *granulosus* nucleic acid in a clinical specimen

Case classification

Possible case

- NA

Probable case

- NA

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the diagnostic criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

ELISA and Westernblot technique, participant of the UK National External Quality Assessment Service for Microbiology, National Reference Laboratory for Echinococcosis.

Notification system in place

Notification of echinococcosis according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

- Alveolar echinococcosis has been known in Austria since 1897; annual incidence (1897- 2004): 0-6 cases, mean incidence: 2.4 cases/year (only autochthonous cases); geographic distribution in Austria: mainly in the western provinces (Vorarlberg, Tyrol, Salzburg), but cases have been reported in every province; outbreaks are not known.
- Cystic echinococcosis has been known in Austria at least since 1819; Cases of cystic echinococcosis have been registered in the Clinical Institute of Hygiene and Medical Microbiology (Medical University Vienna) regularly since the beginning of the 1980ies. Annual incidence (1984 - 2006): 20 - 60 cases; mean incidence: 31 cases per year, one third of patients are of Austrian origin; two thirds are from abroad. Geographic distribution in Austria is unknown; a few autochthonous infections could be observed mainly in the eastern and southern provinces (Lower Austria, Burgenland, and Styria); outbreaks are not known.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

- Alveolar echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: fox faeces (contaminated hands and fingers, vegetables, water).
- Cystic echinococcosis: We expect the future incidence to be low; sources of infestation: dog faeces, presumably in a very few foci (in or around farmers houses)

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Low incidence of both forms of echinococcosis

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure as well as via the monthly and yearly reports published from the Federal Ministry for Austria. The yearly report is published on the Website of the MOH.

Table 118 Echinococcosis in humans - species/serotype distribution (EMS), 2014

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	autochthonous cases	imported cases	unknown
Echinococcosis	14	0,15	7	5	2
<i>E. granulosus</i>	11	0.12	4	5	2
<i>E. multilocularis</i>	3	0.03	3	0	0

Data source: EMS as of February 23, 2015

Table 119 Echinococcosis in humans - age distribution (EMS), 2014

Age group	<i>E. multilocularis</i>			<i>E. granulosus</i>		
	all	m	f	all	m	f
< 1 year	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 to 4 years	0	0	0	0	0	0
5 to 14 years	0	0	0	1	0	1
15 to 24 years	0	0	0	1	0	1
25 to 44 years	1	1	0	5	2	3
45 to 64 years	0	0	0	4	2	2
65 years and older	2	1	1	0	0	0
Age unknown	0	0	0	0	0	0
All age groups	3	2	1	11	4	7

Data source: EMS as of February 23, 2015

4.9.3. *Echinococcus* spp. in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Targeted sampling of all in abattoirs slaughtered animals; the sampling is performed by competent authorities in course of the post-mortem meat inspection; the sampling is part of a permanent monitoring scheme.

Frequency of the sampling

Permanent post-mortem sampling of each slaughtered animal

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption

Case definition

Each carcass in which cysts, cystic or alveolar hydatids are detected in muscles or organs

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

All organs and muscles that were used for human consumption were visually inspected, palpated and cuttings were performed

Vaccination policy

No vaccination

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Post-mortem meat inspection act according to BGBl. 1982/522, Fleischuntersuchungsgesetz, as amended

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Cystic or alveolar echinococcosis in animals that are used for food production do not play a role for the infection of humans; it is primarily a hygienic problem.

Additional information

The public is informed about the results via the annual zoonoses brochure.

Table 120 *Echinococcus* sp. in animals, 2014

Animal species	Sampling Stage	Sampling Context	Source of information	Sampling unit	Units tested	Total units positive for <i>Echinococcus</i> spp.	<i>E. multilocularis</i>	<i>E. granulosus</i>	<i>Echinococcus</i> spp., unspecified
Cattle*	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	608,702	136			136
Sheep	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	144,520	129			129
Goats	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	4,479	0			0
Pigs	at slaughterhouse - animal sample	Control and eradication programmes - official sampling - census sampling	x	animal	5,376,923	0			0

* cattle including calves

All detected cysts are reported as echinococcus but not differentiated (could also be other species than *Echinococcus* spp.).

x: Central Veterinary Services

4.10. Toxoplasmosis

4.10.1. General evaluation

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. Samples from pregnant women (amniotic liquor) in Austria are tested in the Toxoplasmosis-Laboratory via PCR. If toxoplasma is detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up.

4.10.2. *Toxoplasma* in humans

Reporting system in place for the human cases

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable. To determine the incidence of primary gestational infections with *Toxoplasma gondii* and congenital toxoplasmosis in Austria, a nationwide prenatal serological screening program exists since 1974, the Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register. In Austria, *Toxoplasma* screening of pregnant women is part of the “motherchild-booklet” and covered by national healthcare providers and the Ministry of Health.

First-line serologic screening is scheduled within the first trimester, and analyses are performed by clinical laboratories. Seronegative women have to be retested bimonthly. In case of primary gestational infection (PGI), treatment is administered until birth.

Case definition

Women with seroconversions and potential infections were classified as having PGI. Infants were classified as follows: (1) congenital toxoplasmosis, determined by the persistence of anti-*Toxoplasma* immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies beyond the age of 1 year, positive PCR from amniotic fluid, or histopathological isolation of parasite; or (2) non-infected infants, with maternally transmitted antibodies, identified by negative *Toxoplasma*-specific IgG during the first year of life.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Since 1992, amniocentesis and *Toxoplasma*-specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) have been used for diagnosis in affected women and to determine treatment management. If *Toxoplasma* was detected, umbilical cord blood is tested as a kind of quality control. Serum samples were analyzed routinely by different automated test systems in clinical laboratories. In general, all institutions were certified for quality management according to the International Organization for Standardization from Quality Austria. Neonates from infected mothers are controlled as follow-up. In case of undetermined infection status, the in-house Sabin-Feldman dye test and immunoglobulin M immunosorbent agglutination assay (bioMérieux) were performed at the Reference Laboratory. The PCR analyses of amniotic fluid samples were only performed with the same protocol at the Medical University of Vienna

Notification system in place

Toxoplasmosis in humans is not notifiable.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

In this 17-year period, 1992-2008, congenital toxoplasmosis incidence of 8.45 (95% CI, 7.98–8.95) PGIs per 10,000 women, and 1.0 (95% CI, 0.84–1.18) per 10,000 births was reported. Incidence of symptomatic congenital toxoplasmosis was 0.12 per 10,000 live births. This resulted in a mean transmission rate of 13%. In detail, the transmission was <9% (95% CI, 2.9%–14.2%) In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth. Congenital toxoplasmosis was confirmed in 141 cases, resulting in a morbidity of 1.4% (95% CI, 0.83%–2.27%) and mortality of

0.6% (95% CI, 0.24%–1.20%). In 14 of 141 (10%) infected infants, the serological diagnosis was performed at birth.

Results of the investigation

In 2014, maternally infections were diagnosed in 87 cases, congenital toxoplasmosis in five cases.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register reveals a decrease of the incidence of congenital toxoplasmosis since the implementation of the mandatory prenatal screening compared with historical data. Prior to screening, the rate of congenital toxoplasmosis was 78 per 10,000 live births. In the 17-year study period, the authors of the study (see additional information) observed a decrease of congenital toxoplasmosis to 1 per 10,000 births. In addition, they found 9 per 10,000 PGIs per year.

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Toxoplasmosis is a relevant zoonotic disease, because infection only occurs via orally ingestion of oocysts after contact with cats and food contaminated with cat faeces or via consumption of cysts-containing undercooked or raw meat.

Additional information

The information about “*Toxoplasma* in humans” is taken from: Prusa AR, Kasper DC, Pollak A, Gleiss A, Waldhoer T, Hayde M (2015) The Austrian Toxoplasmosis Register, 1992-2008. Clin Infect Dis. 2015 Jan 15;60(2)

Table 121 Toxoplasmosis cases in pregnant and fetus (NRL), 2014

	N
Maternally infections	87
Congenital cases	5

Data source: NRL Toxoplasmosis as of April 3, 2015

4.10.3. *Toxoplasma* in animals

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Toxoplasma gondii* in animals. Sampling of cattle, sheep, goats or pigs is performed depending on clinical suspicion of toxoplasmosis and if ordered by the sender in cases after abortion. Other animal species are also occasionally sampled.

Frequency of the sampling

In case of clinical suspicion and abortion and if ordered.

Type of specimen taken

Blood, fetus, organ, faeces

Case definition

A case is defined as an animal that tested positive serologically ($\geq 1:40$) or if the pathogen is detected microscopically or by PCR. The animal is the epidemiological unit.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic methods used for serology is the direct agglutination test. Organs are tested by real time PCR and/or histology and/or immunohistochemistry (IHC).

Vaccination policy:

No vaccination

Control programme/ mechanisms:**The control programmes/ strategies in place**

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Notification system in place:

Toxoplasmosis is not notifiable in animals.

Results of the investigation

see table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection:

Nil

Additional information

Nil

Table 122 Toxoplasmosis in animals, 2014

animal species	sampling context	sampling details	Analytical method	sampling unit	Source of information	Units tested	Total units positive for Toxoplasma
sheep	privat sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	10	2
sheep	privat sample	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	2	0
goat	privat sample	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	32	6
bovine	clinical investigation	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	4	0
sheep	clinical investigation	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	4	2
sheep	clinical investigation	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	2	0
wild boar	clinical investigation	organs	real time PCR	animal	AGES IVET	42	8
goat	clinical investigation	blood	direct agglutination	animal	AGES IVET	10	3
fox	clinical investigation	organs	histology	animal	AGES IVET	2	2

4.11. Rabies

4.11.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Rabies in humans was a major public health issue in the 1960s.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In 2014, there were no case of rabies detected in humans or animals in Austria.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

In 2014, due to official rabies free status in Austria (since 28.9.2008) oral vaccination of foxes has been suspended; monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union" (<http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/doc/67e.pdf>).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

Nil

4.11.2. Rabies in humans

Case definition

Clinical criteria

Any person with an acute encephalomyelitis

AND

At least two of the following seven symptoms:

- Sensory changes referred to the site of a preceding animal bite
- Paresis or paralysis
- Spasms of swallowing muscles
- Hydrophobia
- Delirium
- Convulsions
- Anxiety

Laboratory criteria

At least one of the following four:

- Isolation of Lyssa virus from a clinical specimen
- Detection of Lyssa virus nucleic acid in a clinical specimen (e.g. saliva or brain tissue)
- Detection of viral antigens by a DFA in a clinical specimen
- Lyssa virus specific antibody response by virus isneutralisation assay in serum or CSF

Laboratory results need to be interpreted according to the vaccination or immunisation status

Case classification

Possible case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria

Probable case

- Any person meeting the clinical criteria and with an epidemiological link

Confirmed case

- Any person meeting the clinical and the laboratory criteria

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Liquor, smears from pharynx, swab from conjunctivae biopsy at the nape of the neck and serum were examined in the fluorescent antibody test (FAT), immunohistochemistry and RT-PCR (Ito M., Itou T., Sakai T., et al. (2001). Detection of Rabies Virus RNA isolated from several species of animals in Brazil by RT-PCR. Journal of Veterinary medicine Science 63(12): 1309-1313.).

Notification system in place

Notification of rabies according to the Federal Epidemic Act (BGBl. 186/1950 Epidemiegesetz, as amended): All physicians and laboratories have to notify.

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Nil

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance as zoonotic disease

Nil

Table 123 Rabies in humans, 2014

	Cases	Incidence/100,000 population	Autochtone cases	Imported cases
Rabies	0	0	0	0
Human exposure	0	0	0	0

Data source: EMS as of February 12, 2015

4.11.3. Lyssavirus (rabies) in animals**A. Rabies virus in animal - wildlife****Monitoring system****Sampling strategy**

According to the degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012) monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect).

Frequency of the sampling

Monitoring is carried out on indicator animals (foxes, badgers, racoons, racoon dogs found dead, victims of road traffic or clinical suspect), according to EFSA's recommendation "Development of harmonised schemes for monitoring and reporting of rabies in animals in the European Union".

Type of specimen taken

Brain (brain stem and/or hippocampus)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Whole animals or heads of the dead animals are sent to the laboratories; sometimes brain tissue (derived from other laboratories). Brain tissue (e.g. 1 cm²) is examined.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody test (FAT) shows a positive signal.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Due to official status rabies free no vaccination of foxes.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place

Fuchs-Tollwutbekämpfungsverordnung 2010 BGBl II 2010/329, Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76 TSG-DVO zum IV. Abschnitt Wutkrankheiten; degree Überwachung der Tollwut 2013 (BMG-74600/0309-II/B/11/2012).

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Probably the reduction of the number of the animals (foxes) for investigation.

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42, and vaccination of the fox population.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Austria is declared as rabies free since 28.9.2008.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

B. Rabies virus in animal - all animals except wildlife

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Sampling is targeted when animals are observed with central nerval symptoms or after biting a person. The suspicious animal is killed or euthanized and the carcass or head is sent to the laboratory.

Frequency of the sampling

If a case is suspected

Type of specimen taken

Brain (hippocampus and brain stem)

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

Routinely 2 parts from the brain will be taken: hippocampus and brain stem.

Case definition

An animal is considered positive if the fluorescent antibody tests (FAT) or the rabies tissue culture infection test or the mouse inoculation test show a positive result.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The routine test was the fluorescent antibody test (FAT).

RTCIT (rabies tissue culture infection test) was performed on mouse neuroblastoma cells.

MIT (mouse inoculation test) will be only performed on demand, not for routine confirmation

Vaccination policy

Voluntary vaccination of pets.

Other preventive measures than vaccination in place

No measures

Control program/mechanisms

The control program/strategies in place is the Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42; Tierseuchengesetz-Durchführungsverordnung 1909/178 as amended: BGBl 1955/76.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42. If a rabies suspicious pet bites a person, the person is treated.

Notification system in place

According to Tierseuchengesetz TSG RGBI 1909/177 as amended, BGBl I 2002/65 IV. Abschnitt, §41, §42

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Nil

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

On 28th of September 2008, Austria has been declared free of rabies.
2013 oral vaccination of foxes was suspended all over Austria.

Table 124 Rabies in animals, 2014

Animal species	Sampling stage	Sampling context	sampler	Sampling strategy	Sample type	Units tested	Total units positive for Lyssa virus (rabies)
Badgers - wild	Hunting	monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	18	0
Badgers - wild	Hunting	monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	5	0
Bats	Unspecified	monitoring - passive	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	83	0
Cats - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	30	0
Cattle (bovine animals)	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	7	0
Deer - wild - red deer	Hunting	monitoring - passive	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Deer - wild - roe deer	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Dogs - pet animals	Unspecified	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	34	0
Foxes - wild	Hunting	monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Selective sampling	animal sample - brain	94	0
Foxes - wild	Hunting	monitoring - passive	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	140	0
Hares - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Marten - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	15	0
Rats	Unspecified	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	3	0
Rodents - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Solipeds, domestic	Farm	Clinical investigations	Official sampling	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0
Wolves - wild	Hunting	Unspecified	Not applicable	Suspect sampling	animal sample - brain	1	0

Immunofluorescence antibody test (IFAT)

Data source: NRL Rabies as of 2.03.2015

4.12. Q-Fever

4.12.1. General evaluation of the situation

No information

4.12.2. Q-fever in humans

Not notifiable in Austria, therefore no data available

4.12.3. *Coxiella burnetii* in animals

Not notifiable in Austria

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

There is no official surveillance for *Coxiella burnetii* in animals.

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

The diagnostic method is the complement fixation reaction, detecting phase 1 and phase 2 antigens. Organs are tested by real time PCR or immunohistochemistry (IHC) and swabs by real time PCR.

Vaccination policy

No vaccination.

Control programme/ mechanisms

The control programmes/ strategies in place

Nil

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Nil

Notification system in place

Q-fever in animals is not a notifiable disease

Results of the investigation

There is no official surveillance program therefore no representative results for Austria are available.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Q-fever in humans is not a notifiable disease. In Austria the number of sheep per holding is low (3.9 animals per holding in average) compared to countries that have a problem with Q-fever; therefore no change of the epidemiological situation in Austria is expected.

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Nil

Additional information

Nil

5. Information on Specific Indicators of Antimicrobial Resistance

5.1. *E. coli* Indicators

5.1.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from different slaughtered animals was started in Austria in 2004. In 2014, the AMR-monitoring for indicator *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

In poultry (broiler and turkey flocks), the proportion of wild types was low (20% and 30%). In 2014, multi-resistance was observed in 28% of all isolates tested in both, isolates from broiler and turkey. Very high resistance rates were found to quinolones in isolates from broilers, high rates to ampicillin and tetracyclines in isolates from turkey and to sulphonamides in isolates from broiler. From broiler, two isolates showed resistance to 3rd generation cephalosporines, and from turkey two isolates showed resistance to cefotaxim, only one of the two to ceftazidime. Three isolates (2 from broiler and one from turkey) were confirmed as ESBL-producing isolates (positive clavulanate synergy with both ceftazidime and cefotaxime), one isolate showed negative results in the clavulanate synergy test with both ceftazidime and cefotaxime.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health (http://www.bmgfj.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Additional information

The results are published annually in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

5.1.2. Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolates

A. Antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* in broiler flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2014, the AMR-monitoring for indicator *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. The target was to obtain 170 isolates of *E. coli* from 170 broiler flocks (= epidemiological unit). Commensal *E. coli* can be expected in every caecum but isolation rate is not 100%. Therefore 181 slaughter batches should be tested to obtain easily 170 *E. coli*-isolates. Based on a randomized sampling plan, 181 of all samples (n=542) that were analysed for *C. jejuni* were also used to isolate *E. coli*. Proportionally to the number of slaughtered flocks in each of the 4 slaughter houses the samples (47, 73, 55 and 6 flocks sampled) were distributed equally over the whole year. The sampling plan (objective sampling) specified the number of sampled flocks per week and slaughter house. Veterinarians were assigned to take the samples, arbitrarily choosing flocks, depending on

the number of flocks to be sampled per week and on the number of slaughter days at the respective slaughter house; per flock (slaughter batch) the veterinarians chose 10 animals whose intestines were collected.

Stratification procedures per animal population

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Randomisation procedures per animal population

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Frequency of the sampling

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Type of specimen taken

Intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration the whole intestines of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory a caecum of each intestinal convolute was identified, some content of each caecum pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *E. coli*.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

Out of 179 flocks *E. coli* were isolated. The testing for antimicrobial susceptibility was performed in the national reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for medical Microbiology and Hygiene in Graz with 176 isolates after isolation. According to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU all unique strains isolated in the course of the control program (identical strains from one epidemiological unit only once) were subjected to microdilution susceptibility testing.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Suspect *E. coli* colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1 and Table 4).

Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1).

Control programs/strategies in place

The control program is a national program, based on the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and co-financed based on Commission Implementing Decision 2013/653/EU.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Result of the investigation

In 2014, 20% of *E. coli* from broilers turned out to be wild types (no antimicrobial resistance detected to any of the antimicrobials tested). Since 2010, the proportion of wild types have doubled. Multi-resistance was observed in 28% of all isolates tested. Since 2010 a decrease of multi-resistant isolates has been detected (2010: 41% multi-resistant). Very high resistance rates were found to quinolones, high rates to sulphonamides. Two isolates showed resistance to 3rd generation cephalosporines. The testing with panel two (according to CID 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 4) confirmed the 2 ESBL-producing isolates (positive clavulanate synergy with both ceftazidime and cefotaxime). For the last years (since 2010) a decrease in resistance rates to quinolones has been observed (from 80%–60%), to the other substances neither an increase nor a decrease could be observed.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See above (results)

Relevance of the findings in feedingstuffs/animals/foodstuffs to human cases

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

B. Antimicrobial resistance of *E. coli* in turkey flocks

Description of sampling designs

In 2014, the AMR-monitoring for *E. coli* was performed according to CID 2013/652/EU. The target was to obtain 170 isolates of *E. coli* from 170 turkey flocks (= epidemiological unit). Per year, about 270 nationally produced flocks were slaughtered in Austria. The program in turkeys was combined with the sampling for *C. jejuni*, where samples from all 270 flocks should be collected at the two national premises where turkeys are slaughtered. Two out of 3 flocks sampled were foreseen to be tested also for commensal *E. coli*. Due to too high costs of the sample transports on thursdays and fridays from the slaughter houses to the laboratory, and to ensure sample processing within the same week, not all of the slaughtered fattening flocks could be sampled. Veterinarians were assigned to take the samples; per flock, the veterinarians chose 10 animals whose caeca were

collected. All available flocks following economically considerations were sampled (objective sampling).

Stratification procedures per animal population

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Randomisation procedures per animal population

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Sampling strategy used in monitoring

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Frequency of the sampling

See chapter “description of sampling design”

Type of specimen taken

Caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch.

Methods of sampling (description of sampling techniques)

The sampling was performed by official veterinarians carrying out the post-mortem inspection. At time of evisceration caeca of 10 animals per slaughter batch were taken and wrapped in a sterile plastic bag. Using a polystyrene box cooled samples (4 °C) were sent to the AGES Institute of Medical Microbiology and Hygiene, Department for Veterinary Microbiology (VEMI) in Graz. In the laboratory some content of each caecum was pooled and cultured by direct plating onto selective medium suitable for *E. coli*.

Procedures for the selection of isolates for antimicrobial testing

One *E.coli* isolated per turkey flock was used in the antimicrobial susceptibility testing according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU. In total, 125 isolates were available and all isolates were susceptibility tested.

Laboratory methodology used for identification of the microbial isolates

The intestinal contents are streaked onto the MacConkey-agar plates (Merck Nr. 1.05465) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. Suspected *E. coli* colonies are streaked onto a blood-agar (Oxoid Nr. CM0055, 5% Sheep blood) and incubated for 24 hrs at 37±1 °C. The confirmation of the identification of *E. coli* is done with an oxidase- (Merck Nr. 1.13300.0001) and spot indol test (Remel, Nr. R8309002).

Laboratory used for detection of resistance

National reference laboratory for antimicrobial resistance (NRL-AMR) at the AGES Institute for medical Microbiology and Hygiene, in Graz

Antimicrobials included in monitoring

All isolates were subjected to testing to the panel of antimicrobial substances according to Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 1 and Table 4).

Cut-off values used in testing

Cut-off values were applied as given in Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU.

Control programs/strategies in place

The control program is a national program, based on the Commission Implementing Decision 2013/652/EU and co-financed based on Commission Implementing Decision 2013/653/EU.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

The National Action Plan to control antimicrobial resistance, published on the homepage of the Federal Ministry of Health

(http://www.bmgfi.gv.at/cms/home/attachments/9/2/1/CH1318/CMS1416214760260/nap_amr.pdf).

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Nil

Measures in case of positive findings or single cases

No measures foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Notification system in place

No notification foreseen in case of resistant isolates.

Result of the investigation

In 2014, 30% of *E. coli* from turkey turned out to be wild types (no antimicrobial resistance detected to any of the antimicrobials tested). Multi-resistance was observed in 28% of all isolates tested, as in isolates from broiler flocks. High resistance rates were found to ampicillin and tetracyclines. Two isolates showed resistance to cefotaxime, only one of the two to ceftazidime. The testing with panel two (according to CID 2013/652/EU (Annex, Part A, Table 4) confirmed 1 ESBL-producing isolate (clavulanate synergy with both ceftazidime and cefotaxime were positive), the second isolate showed negative results in the clavulanate synergy test with both ceftazidime and cefotaxime.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

See above (results). Trends cannot be analysed because the program in turkey was performed for the first time.

Relevance of the findings in feedingstuffs/animals/foodstuffs to human cases

Not available because indicator *E. coli* are not examined in humans.

Additional information

Annual publication of the results in the Report on Antimicrobial Resistance in Austria (AURES).

Table 125 Breakpoints used for antibiotic resistance testing of *E. coli* in animals, 2014

		ECOFF	Range tested	
		concentration (µg/ml)		
antimicrobial		wild type <=	lowest	highest
panel 1	aminoglycosids - gentamicin	2	0,5	32
	amphenicols - chloramphenicol	16	8	128
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,25	0,25	4
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0,5	0,5	8
	fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	0,06	0,016	8
	glycylcyclines - tigecycline	1	0,25	8
	macrolides - azithromycin	16	2	64
	penicillins - ampicillin	8	1	64
	polymyxins - colistin	2	1	16
	quinolones - nalidixic acid	16	4	128
	sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	64	8	1024
	tetracyclines - tetracycline	8	2	64
	trimethoprim	2	0,25	32
panel 2	carbapenems - ertapenem	0,06	0,016	2
	carbapenems - imipenem	0,5	0,12	16
	carbapenems - meropenem	0,12	0,03	16
	cephalosporines - cefepim	0,12	0,06	32
	cephalosporines - cefotaxime	0,25	0,25	64
	cephalosporines - cefoxitin	8	0,5	64
	cephalosporines - ceftazidime	0,5	0,25	128
	clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	0,25	0,06	64
	clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	0,5	0,12	128
	penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	32	0,5	128

Number of fully-susceptible and number of isolates resistant to 1, 2, 3, 4 or >4 antimicrobials of different classes, excluding cross-resistance. For *E. coli* this includes resistance to ampicillin, cefotaxime/ceftazidime, meropenem, ciprofloxacin/nalidixic acid, tetracycline, gentamicin, colistin, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, chloramphenicol, tigecycline.

Table 126 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of *E. coli* in animals (qualitative tables), 2014

<i>E. coli</i>		broiler flocks			turkey flocks		
number of isolates		176			125		
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant		
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n	
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	176	2,3	4	125	0,0	0	
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	176	6,8	12	125	9,6	12	
carbapenems - meropenem	176	0,0	0	125	0,0	0	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	176	1,1	2	125	1,6	2	
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	176	1,1	2	125	0,8	1	
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	176	59,7	105	125	28,0	35	
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	176	0,0	0	125	0,0	0	
macrolides - azithromycin	176	0,6	1	125	0,8	1	
penicillins - ampicillin	176	28,4	50	125	48,0	60	
polymyxins - colistin	176	0,0	0	125	0,0	0	
quinolones - nalidixic acid	176	56,8	100	125	18,4	23	
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	176	33,0	58	125	19,2	24	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	176	29,0	51	125	40,8	51	
trimethoprim	176	22,7	40	125	12,0	15	
Number of multiresistant isolates		N	%R	n	N	%R	n
fully sensitive	176	21,0	37	125	33,6	42	
resistant to 1 antimicrobial	176	33,5	59	125	22,4	28	
resistant to 2 antimicrobials	176	17,0	30	125	15,2	19	
resistant to 3 antimicrobials	176	10,2	18	125	14,4	18	
resistant to 4 antimicrobials	176	8,5	15	125	10,4	13	
resistant to >4 antimicrobials	176	9,7	17	125	4,0	5	

antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant		total units tested	micro-biological resistant	
	N	%R	n	N	%R	n
carbapenems - ertapenem	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
carbapenems - imipenem	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
cephalosporines - cefepim	2	100,0	2	2	100,0	2
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	100,0	2	2	100,0	2
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	100,0	2	2	50,0	1
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	2	0,0	0	2	0,0	0

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 127 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in broiler flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent	E. coli
matrix	broiler flock
sampling context	AMR monitoring

antimicrobial	Number of isolates available in the laboratory 176		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
	total units tested	micro-biological resistant	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
	N	%R	n																				
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	176	2,3	4						107	63	2		1	1	1	1							
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	176	6,8	12										149	15	1	2	4	5					
carbapenems - meropenem	176	0,0	0												175	1							
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	176	1,1	2					174					2										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	176	1,1	2					174	1	1													
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	176	59,7	105	56	14	1	5	36	27	15	3	1	12	6									
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	176	0,0	0					95	75	6													
macrolides - azithromycin	176	0,6	1								7	66	81	21	1								
penicillins - ampicillin	176	28,4	50							8	53	61	4				50						
polymyxins - colistin	176	0,0	0							174	2												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	176	56,8	100									71	4	1	1	8	36	55					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	176	33,0	58										50	52	14	2					1	57	
tetracyclines - tetracycline	176	29,0	51								108	17				25	26						
trimethoprim	176	22,7	40					78	47	10	1					40							

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 127, cont.

zoonotic agent *E. coli*
 matrix broiler flock
 sampling context AMR monitoring

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		2		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
carbapenems - ertapenem	2	0,0		2																			
carbapenems - imipenem	2	0,0						1	1														
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0				2																	
cephalosporines - cefepim	2	100,0	2								1	1											
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	100,0	2												1		1						
cephalosporines - ceftaxitin	2	0,0										1	1										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	100,0	2								2												
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	2	0,0				2																	
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	2	0,0						2															
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	2	0,0												1	1								

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 128 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of E. coli in turkey flocks - at slaughter - quantitative data, 2014

zoonotic agent	E. coli
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		125		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																			
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																					
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048
				n																			
aminoglycosids - gentamicin	125	0,0	0						75	46	4												
amphenicols - chloramphenicol	125	9,6	12											111	2	3	2	4	3				
carbapenems - meropenem	125	0,0	0			125																	
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	125	1,6	2					123		1				1									
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	125	0,8	1						124				1										
fluoroquinolones - ciprofloxacin	125	28,0	35		64	25	1	2	14	4	2			8	5								
glycylcyclines - tigecycline	125	0,0	0					68	55	2													
macrolides - azithromycin	125	0,8	1								16	61	37	10	1								
penicillins - ampicillin	125	48,0	60							1	35	29						60					
polymyxins - colistin	125	0,0	0							124	1												
quinolones - nalidixic acid	125	18,4	23									92	8	2		2	3	18					
sulfonamides - sulfamethoxazol	125	19,2	24										28	55	16	2							24
tetracyclines - tetracycline	125	40,8	51									71	3		3	20	28						
trimethoprim	125	12,0	15					58	40	12							15						

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

Table 128, cont.

zoonotic agent	<i>E. coli</i>
matrix	turkey flock
sampling context	AMR monitoring

Number of isolates available in the laboratory		2		Dilution method (concentration (µg/ml)), number of isolates with a concentration of inhibition equal to:																				
antimicrobial	total units tested	micro-biological resistant																						
	N	%R	n	=< 0.008	0,015	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.25	0.5	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	>2048	
				n																				
carbapenems - ertapenem	2	0,0			1	1																		
carbapenems - imipenem	2	0,0						2																
carbapenems - meropenem	2	0,0				2																		
cephalosporines - cefepim	2	100,0	2									2												
cephalosporines - cefotaxime	2	100,0	2							1					1									
cephalosporines - ceftoxitin	2	0,0											1	1										
cephalosporines - ceftazidime	2	50,0	1						1		1													
clavulanate synergy with cefotaxime	2	0,0					1	1																
clavulanate synergy with ceftazidime	2	0,0						2																
penicillins, extended-spectrum - temocillin	2	0,0											1	1										

N = number of isolates tested, n = number of resistant isolates, %R = % isolates resistant

5.2. *Enterococcus* Indicators

5.2.1. General evaluation of the national situation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Resistance monitoring of faeces isolates from slaughtered animals was started in Austria from 2004 to 2012 but that program was suspended in 2013.

6. Food-borne outbreaks

Food-borne outbreaks are defined as two or more human cases of the same disease or infection where the cases are linked or are probably linked to the same food source. A situation in which the observed human cases exceed the expected number of cases and where a same food source is suspected, is also indicative of a food-borne outbreak.

A. Food-borne outbreaks

System in place for identification, epidemiological investigations and reporting of food-borne outbreaks

Presently, every district (n = 95) is responsible for outbreak investigation. However, food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one district or even more than one province (Austria = 9 provinces) are regulated by the Federal Zoonoses Act (Zoonosengesetz, BGBl. I, 128/2005 entered into force on 1. January 2006). The Federal Zoonoses Commission was founded to advise the Federal Minister to survey and combat the zoonoses in Austria. One target of the Zoonoses Act is to ensure that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation. It regulates, in case of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province that the governors of the affected provinces provide operative units to investigate possible or confirmed food-borne outbreaks. Data concerning epidemiological criteria, potential implicated food items and the source of an outbreak must be collected and adequate epidemiological and microbiological examinations must be conducted. Short reports summarize each outbreak and must be communicated to the Federal Commission for Zoonoses and to AGES.

Description of the types of outbreaks covered by the reporting:

Since there has not been a coordinated approach for outbreak investigation in most provinces, the large majority (80 of 96) of food-borne outbreaks are classified as household outbreaks. Coordinated investigation of outbreaks affecting more than one province - unhampered by district limits - could decrease the total number of outbreaks.

National evaluation of the reported outbreaks in the country:

In 2014, 96 food-borne outbreaks affecting 790 persons were reported. 121 persons were hospitalized and one person died. The total number of food-borne outbreaks decreased by 28 % compared to 2013. The average number of cases affected by an outbreak was 8.2 persons, ranging from two to 151 persons per outbreak. 13.5 % (16 % in 2013, 14 % in 2012) of the reported outbreaks were acquired abroad. 42 % of all food-borne outbreaks acquired in Austria were caused by *Campylobacter* spp. (n=40), 49 % by *Salmonella* spp. (n=47) and 57 % thereof by serotype Enteritidis (n=27) compared to (63 %) in 2013.

Relevance of the different causative agents, food categories and the agent/food category combinations

Campylobacter and *Salmonella* pose the most important agents causing 91 % of all food borne outbreaks (77 % in 2013, 93 % in 2012). Presently, the data quality does not allow conclusions on the relevance of different food categories.

Relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks

The data quality does presently not allow conclusions on the relevance of the different type of places of food production and preparation in outbreaks.

Evaluation of the severity and clinical picture of the human cases

15.3 % (19 % in 2013; 17.3 % in 2012) of patients affected by these food-borne outbreaks are reported as hospitalized; one death occurred in association with an outbreak (2011–2013 no lethal case).

Descriptions of single outbreaks of special interest

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, European Food Safety Authority. Multi-country outbreak of Salmonella Enteritidis infections associated with consumption of eggs from Germany - 25 August 2014. Stockholm and Parma: ECDC/EFSA; 2014. Available from: <http://ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications/Publications/salmonella-enteritidis-rapid-outbreak-assessment-270814.pdf>

Control measures or other actions taken to improve the situation

Improvement due to the implementation of the Federal Zoonoses Act e.g. the chain of command in terms of investigation of food-borne outbreaks affecting more than one province was implemented.

Additional information

The situation of foodborne outbreaks are published in the National Zoonoses Brochure.

Table 129 Food-borne outbreaks with food vehicle identified and strong evidence (EMS), 2014

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the Outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
3240	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	76	7	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	AT	Infected food handler
3394	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	86	0	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	General	Others	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Infected food handler
3479	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	146	1	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food chain or its environment - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Unknown	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Infected food handler, Cross-contamination
3208	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	
3273	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Bovine meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3361	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	Household / domestic kitchen	Take-away or fast-food outlet	Take-away or fast-food outlet	XX	Unknown
3367	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	44	14	0	Mixed food	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Cross-contamination, Inadequate chilling, Storage time/temperature abuse
3383	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	5	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Unprocessed contaminated ingredient
3335	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	151	25	1	Eggs and egg products	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	General	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	Residential institution (nursing home or prison or boarding school)	EU	Unknown
3376	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	3	0	0	Cheese	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	General	Household	Others	XX	Unknown
3522	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	2	1	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Symptoms and onset of illness pathognomonic to causative agent	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Unknown
3410	Salmonella - S. Goldcoast	1	2	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Descriptive epidemiological evidence	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3538	Salmonella - S. Stanley	1	80	19	0	Turkey meat and products thereof	Analytical epidemiological evidence, Detection of causative agent in food vehicle or its component - Detection of indistinguishable causative agent in humans	General	Others	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Data source: EMS as of March 11, 2015

Table 130 Food-borne outbreaks with no food vehicle identified or weak evidence, 2014

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
3234	Calicivirus - norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	School or kindergarten	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3203	Campylobacter - C. coli	1	2	0	0	Mixed food	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3375	Campylobacter - C. coli	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3180	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3198	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3200	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	3	0	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3207	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3209	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3215	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
3224	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3227	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown		XX	
3238	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3266	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
3276	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3282	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Eggs and egg products	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3284	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	3	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3293	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3295	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Pig meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Inadequate heat treatment
3311	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3312	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	AT	Inadequate heat treatment
3316	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3319	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3323	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
3330	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3334	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3384	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Others	XX	Unknown
3391	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3392	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	4	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3406	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3407	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3418	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3428	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown

Table 130 continued

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
3438	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3461	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3465	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3511	Campylobacter - C. jejuni	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3249	Campylobacter - Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3439	Campylobacter - Campylobacter spp., unspecified	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3569	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) - VTEC O145:HNM	1	6	5	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
3326	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) - VTEC Orough:H30	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3356	Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) - VTEC Orough:HNM	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3515	Leptospira - Leptospira spp., unspecified	1	2	2	0	Tap water, including well water	Unknown	General	Others	Water source	AT	Unknown
3221	Salmonella - S. Agona	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Household	XX	Unknown
3213	Salmonella - S. Cerro	1	4	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3283	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	1	3	1	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3287	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	1	2	0	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Others	XX	Unknown
3289	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis	1	2	1	0	Other foods	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3377	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - 6a	1	2	1	0	Dairy products (other than cheeses)	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Mobile retailer or market/street vendor	Mobile retailer or market/street vendor	XX	Unknown
3345	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 4	1	8	7	0	Eggs and egg products	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	XX	Unknown
3499	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 6c	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3329	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown
3331	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3353	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3364	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3413	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3467	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	3	1	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Take-away or fast-food outlet	Take-away or fast-food outlet	XX	Unknown
3487	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown

Table 130 continued

FBO Code	Causative Agent	Number of Outbreaks	Number of Human Cases	Number of Hospitalised	Number of Deaths	Food Vehicle	Nature of Evidence linking the outbreak with Food	Type of Outbreak	Setting	Place of Origin of Problem	Origin of Food Vehicle	Contributory Factors
3504	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 8	1	2	0	0	Broiler meat (Gallus gallus) and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3256	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 13a	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3387	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3455	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 14b	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3288	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3338	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3395	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3333	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 21c	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3398	Salmonella - S. Enteritidis - PT 29	1	2	2	0	Other, mixed or unspecified poultry meat and products thereof	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3433	Salmonella - S. Napoli	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3280	Salmonella - S. Paratyphi B	1	2	0	0	Fish and fish products	Unknown	General	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	Restaurant or Cafe or Pub or Bar or Hotel or Catering service	EU	Unknown
3442	Salmonella - S. Paratyphi B	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3314	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium	1	2	0	0	Other or mixed red meat and products thereof	Unknown	General	Others	Others	XX	
3490	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 1	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3299	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium - DT 193	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3202	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3290	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3443	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - DT 193	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3437	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - U 311	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3454	Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic - U 311	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Household	XX	Unknown
3245	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	1	2	2	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3399	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	1	3	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3400	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3401	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	1	2	1	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3432	Salmonella - Salmonella spp., unspecified	1	3	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Household	Unknown	XX	Unknown
3362	Shigella - S. sonnei	1	2	0	0	Unknown	Unknown	Household / domestic kitchen	Unknown	Travel abroad	XX	Unknown

Data source: EMS as of March 11, 2015

7. Information on specific microbiological agents

7.1. Staphylococcal Enterotoxins

7.1.1. Staphylococcal enterotoxins general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Staphylococcal food intoxication is not a major health problem in Austria. Nevertheless there are two staphylococcal food poisoning outbreaks documented in the last 10 years.

September 2006: Outbreak of an acute gastroenteritis in an Austrian boarding school caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* producing Enterotoxins A and D in rice. Afflicted were 113 persons/101 hospitalised because of vomiting and circulatory collapse. The rice had been contaminated by a kitchenstaff.

June 2007: Outbreak of staphylococcal food intoxication after consumption of pasteurized milk products. 166 children had fallen ill with abdominal cramps and vomiting caused by school milk products containing staphylococcal Enterotoxins A and D. The source of the contamination was three milk producing cows with subclinical mastitis.

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

The analysis of food samples consists of two steps, a prescreening to identify samples harbouring > 100,000 coagulase-positive staphylococci CFU per gram; in that case, a second screening step is applied directly in all types of food matrices according to the European screening method given by the EURL for coagulase positive staphylococci to detect staphylococcal enterotoxins (SE) types A to E. The direct testing for staphylococcal enterotoxins is done in case of outbreaks or when food was pasteurised or heated before the screening for coagulasepositive staphylococci.

Because it is not known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Hygiene is of utmost importance in food producing process and in the kitchen to prevent contamination with coagulasepositive staphylococci. Additionally precautions must be taken to ensure and control the effective maintaining of the refrigeration chain.

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Continue the efforts already started to improve harmonization of the detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins types A to E in food matrices.

Additional information

Not available

7.1.2. Staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

In 2014, foodstuffs were sampled all over Austria according to the the revision- and sampling plan given in the ordinance „Revisions- und Probenplan für das Jahr 2014 gemäß §31 LMSVG; Richtlinien über die Vollziehung der Überwachung des Verkehrs mit den durch das LMSVG erfassten Waren; Berichtsschema 2014“ (BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013) from the Federal Ministry of Health. This “Revisions- und Probenplan” is part of the multi-annual national control plan (2011-2015) according to the Art. 41ff of Regulation (EC) No 882/2004 and consists of two separated parts:

The revision plan (Revisionsplan) determines the number of food enterprises e.g. restaurants, dairies, retail outlets etc. that have to be visited and inspected. Every food business has to be inspected regularly. The inspection comprises sampling, hygienic investigations of the establishment and the employees, checking of HACCP concepts, control of manufacturing processes etc.

The sampling plan is comprised of scheduled (“Planproben”) and suspect samples (“Verdachtsproben”). In 2014, the sampling plan intended approximately 22,000 scheduled samples and only these numbers are used in this report (data from suspect samples are not shown). This yearly sampling plan determines the number of samples for each stage (retail, processing plants, primary production and monitoring) and for each food category that has to be investigated randomly.

If specific suspicions (e.g. colour deviation, temperature, etc.) initiate the sampling by officials, these samples are categorised as suspect samples. Moreover any follow up sampling (e.g. due to RASFF, monitoring, positive samples, further information, etc.) is defined as suspect sample as well as food samples from private persons or sampling due to outbreak situations.

In addition there are monitoring plans, so called campaigns, for specific food items (about 60-65 individual campaigns per year). In the course of those campaigns food items of special interest are investigated for defined parameters – amongst others zoonotic agents. In order to gain in-depth information the sampling takes place during a specified time frame . In 2014, 10 different food campaigns were conducted throughout Austria dealing with zoonotic agents (Schwerpunktprogramm 2014 BMG-75500/0206-II/B/13/2013). Each campaign is described in detail and results are depicted in the respective chapters per pathogen.

Further activities at food production facilities are made pursuant to Regulation (EC) no 178/2002 (e. g. traceability of food, feed, food-producing animals and all substances incorporated into foodstuffs must be established at all stages of production, processing and distribution). To fulfil these obligations, food business operators are required to apply appropriate systems and procedures, e.g. HACCP-concepts. One part is given by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs that indicates the minimal quantity of sampling (number of sample units and size of the analytical unit) regarding to specific microbiological hazards at the stage of products placed on the market within their shelflife and at a specific stage of production (e.g. before and/or after chilling).

Definition of positive finding

Detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E in food .

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Prescreening: Several food (e. g. icecream, meat, cheese, etc.) is tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci. If the number of detected staphylococci exceeds 100,000 CFU/g, the food matrices are further tested for staphylococcal enterotoxins A to E following the “European screening method of the EU-RL for coagulasepositive staphylococci, including *Staphylococcus aureus*” using commercially available ELISAs. A positive screening result leads to an identification of the toxin group by another ELISA or a RPLA (Reverse passive latex agglutination).

Positive isolates are sent to the National Reference Laboratory in Graz, where the Enterotoxins A, B, C1, C2, C3, D, E are identified via an ELFA (enzyme linked fluorescent assay). RPLA and ELISAs for further investigations on the enterotoxins may complete the analysis.

Results of the investigation

Because it is not exactly known how many and which samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci the results cannot be reported.

7.2. Cronobacter sakazakii

7.2.1. Cronobacter sakazakii in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Sampling distributed evenly throughout the year

Type of specimen taken

Infant formula

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

Bacteriological method ISO 22964:2006

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Table 131 Cronobacter sakazakii in food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sampling Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units positive for Cronobacter sakazakii
Infant formula		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	100	Gram	1	0
		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0
					100	Gram	2	0
		Wholesale	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0
					EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram

7.3. Histamine

7.3.1. Histamine general evaluation

History of the disease and/or infection in the country

Not available

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infection

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals, feedingstuffs and foodstuffs to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Recent actions taken to control the zoonoses

Not available

Suggestions to the European Union for the actions to be taken

Not available

Additional information

Not available

7.3.2. Histamine in foodstuff

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Not available

Frequency of the sampling

Not available

Type of specimen taken

Fish, fishery products, cheese

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg histamine per kg fish - fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

>400 mg histamine per kg cheese

Diagnostic/analytical methods used

High performance liquid chromatography with UV detection; (HPLC-UV)

Control program/mechanisms

Measures in case of the positive findings or single cases

Not available

Results of the investigation

See table

National evaluation of the recent situation, the trends and sources of infections

Not available

Relevance of the findings in animals to findings in foodstuffs and to human cases (as a source of infection)

Not available

Additional information

Not available

Campaign A-001-14: Histamine in food – alcoholic beverages - at processing plant - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Samples are taken at processing plants by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: January to April

Type of specimen taken

Beer, samples taken in small breweries located in taverns

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 10g

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg/kg for fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg/kg for fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

Results of the investigation

21 samples were tested for Histamine: total units in non-conformity: none

Additional information

None

Campaign A-010-14: Histamine in food – Fish - fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine – not enzyme matured and which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine – batch (food/feed) - at wholesale - Surveillance - official sampling - objective sampling

Monitoring system

Sampling strategy

Random sampling is done according to the sampling plan of the Ministry of Health. Batch samples are taken at wholesale markets by competent authorities.

Frequency of the sampling

Investigation period: February to March

Type of specimen taken

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine – not enzyme matured (e.g. tuna) and which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine (e. g. anchovy)

Methods of sampling

Sample weight: 10g

Definition of positive finding

>200 mg/kg for fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured

>400 mg/kg for fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine

Results of the investigation

33 samples were tested for Histamine:

Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine – not enzyme matured: total units in non-conformity: 2 (200 – 400 mg/kg)

Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine: total units in non-conformity: 1 (> 400 mg/kg)

Additional information

None

Table 132 Histamine in food, 2014

Food	Sampling Details	Sampling Stage	Sampling Origin	Sampling Unit	Sample Weight	Sampling Weight Unit	Total Units tested	Total Units in non-conformity	≤100 mg/kg	>100 to ≤200 mg/kg	>200 to ≤400 mg/kg	>400 mg/kg	
Beverages, alcoholic		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
	campaign A-001-14	Processing plant	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	21	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - Fishery products from fish species associated with a high amount of histidine - not enzyme matured		Border inspection activities	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX		single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0		
		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	0	0	1	
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	1	0	1	0	0	
		campaign A-010-14	Wholesale	AT	batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	0	0	0	0	0
				EU	batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	11	2	0	0	2	0
	XE			batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	
	XX			batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	4	0	0	0	0	0	
Fish - Fishery products which have undergone enzyme maturation treatment in brine		Retail	EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
		Wholesale	XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
	campaign A-010-14	Wholesale	AT	batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
	EU		batch (food/feed)	10	Gram	2	1	0	0	0	1		
Fish - unspecified - frozen		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	20	0	0	0	0	0	
			EU	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	13	0	0	0	0	0	
			XE	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Fishery products, unspecified - raw - chilled		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	3	0	0	0	0	0	
			XX	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	18	0	0	0	0	0	
Meat, red meat (meat from bovines, pigs, goats, sheep, horses, donkeys, bison and water buffalos) - meat products - fermented sausages		Retail	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Other processed food products and prepared dishes		Catering	AT	single (food/feed)	10	Gram	1	0	0	0	0	0	

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